

„Success factors of storytelling commercials“

by
Marcel Rohr

University of the West of Scotland

in cooperation with

Hamburg University of Applied Sciences

School of Business and Creative Industries

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BannerID: B00339153

Lead Supervisor: Dr. Ying Ding

Second Supervisor: Prof. Dr. Heike Jochims

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Abstract

Marketers are placing a greater emphasis on social media channels, namely YouTube. The importance of using narratives in advertising is increasing. Numerous studies have demonstrated that a favourable opinion of a product or brand is followed by a probable desire to purchase. Therefore, it is crucial for marketers to comprehend how to create commercials that positively influence the attitudes of their viewers. In this context, it is essential to be aware of the various design elements that induce the required attitude change in order to incorporate them into commercial design as effectively as feasible. The "Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement" served as a framework for analysing the present design aspects. The results of the Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis provide conclusive proof that the "Narrative Presence" construct is of highest importance in the process of creating commercials. The ability of the viewer to become immersed in the commercial's main character, to follow the plot from beginning to conclusion, and to experience enjoyment while watching have a significant impact on the viewer's attitude change when viewing the commercial. An in-depth investigation of the components that lead to the enjoyment of the commercial reveals that a consistent narrative, tension, background music, sympathy for the main character and empathy with the main character are among the most crucial. Due to the significance of brand impression on attitude change, this must be taken into account in the creation of storytelling commercials.

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1 Introduction

In recent years, the economic environment of many businesses has become increasingly dynamic and complicated. Also, as a result of the growing globalisation of the economy, the competitive pressure has expanded substantially. In addition, the quality of products in many industries is becoming increasingly comparable, making product-specific distinction nearly impossible; even with novel offerings, a market advantage is frequently eroded by the competition's swift response. Consequently, marketing communication difference is growing in importance.

To emphasise brand relevance and push customer behaviour in the desired direction, the demand for an effective, efficient, and unique method of marketing communication has increased dramatically in a period of rapid technological and societal change. Today's consumers are subjected to an overwhelming amount of stimulus and information. Therefore, Seth Godin (Godin and Gladwell, 2001) predicted in 2001 that disruption marketing will fail because it will no longer attract sufficient customer attention. Numerous technical advancements, such as the adaptation of algorithms to quality characteristics, the constant use of the internet via mobile internet, and the resulting "always on" mindset (Heinrich, 2016, p. 49), necessitate a rethinking of marketing communication. Traditional marketing platforms, such as television and print media, are becoming more irrelevant, particularly among younger generations (Franks, 2016). Customers are placing a growing number of expectations on businesses, which is altering consumer behaviour. Additionally, they are more knowledgeable, critical, and independent than ever before (Borst, 2017). This is apparent in purchasing behaviour as well. As termed by Google, the "Zero Moment of Truth," or the first time a customer interacts with a brand throughout the purchase decision process, is of critical long-term relevance in determining how a client perceives a brand. Therefore, it is vital to implement the appropriate marketing communication at this stage (Lecinski, 2014). Finally, companies must prioritise long-term connections with their consumers, such as through social media, to improve customer engagement and get crucial insights about their target audience.

All this indicates that it is more crucial than ever to target customers with relevant content. Customers are practically swamped with advertising and stimulation, a dilemma for businesses. In certain instances, advertising is viewed as a persistent and bothersome sound. Therefore, it is of the biggest significance for businesses to

stand out from the crowd with original content, which has the ability to alter attitudes and generate virality.

Everything begins with the initial touchpoint. A potential consumer has several interactions with a firm before making a purchase. The touchpoints before a purchase are especially significant since they determine whether a later purchase will be made. Advertising given to prospective consumers in the so-called pre-purchase stage must stimulate the activation process of the customer in order to grab his attention and ensure that the advertising is really digested by a person.

In today's pre-purchase period, social media is one of, if not the most significant channel for businesses. Through social media, businesses are able to separate out from the competition by implementing innovative content marketing strategies. Increasing numbers of research examine how commercials on social media should be created to affect potential buyers as positively as possible in relation to a product or brand. In addition, the design characteristics should facilitate a high level of virality. Storytelling commercials are ideally suited for this.

YouTube is an especially useful social media platform for marketers. YouTube had more than 2,6 billion users in 2021, making it the second largest social media network after Facebook. Marketers may utilise their company-owned YouTube channels to produce viral video content that can rapidly reach a large audience through sharing on other social media channels. This platform is the subject of this study because of its scale, but also because of its emphasis on content display and, thus, the potential for the generation of viral video content. Targeted combinations of so-called hygiene, hub, and hero content may be used to develop long-term consumer relationships on YouTube and viral content hits that can catapult brand and product exposure in a short period of time.

Content marketing is one of the most significant marketing techniques available today. Marketing's present difficulties may be addressed most effectively through content marketing. The latest technology innovations result in a tremendous sensory overload of stimuli for customers, which in turn results in marketing measures not being perceived at all or being perceived to a lesser degree. Some target groups can no longer be reached using traditional marketing methods such as radio and print advertising since they only operate on social media also sometimes exclusive to specific platforms. Consumer behaviour has likewise undergone a full transformation. Today's consumers are more connected and discerning than ever before. Attitudes

regarding a brand or a product now have a significant effect on customer purchasing behaviour. Through a long-term customer relationship, it is necessary to favourably affect this mentality.

Effective content marketing may result in the viral spread of advertising strategies. In his book *Zero to One*, Peter Thiel states, "The only sustainable growth is viral growth." (Thiel and Masters, 2014)

Attitudes are one of the most essential and intricate psychological structures. The scientific community is divided about whether and to what degree attitudes impact human behaviour. Several studies have demonstrated a correlation. Therefore, it is in the best interests of marketers to alter these sentiments. This method of altering attitudes is known as persuasion. Recent research indicates that narratives, in particular, can elicit this type of persuasion, since immersing the listener in a narrative has several consequences that increase the likelihood of altering attitudes. Consequently, narratives are the most effective marketing technique for influencing attitudes. In the marketing industry, this is known as storytelling.

This storytelling is precisely why some of the world's most well-known companies have grown so popular in the first place. In 1999, Nike was one of the first brands to produce a commercial with a narrative. The life of Michael Jordan was recounted in a one-minute television advertisement. Only at the very end of the commercial was the association with the Nike brand established with the slogan "Just do it" and the Nike logo. In addition, today's largest corporations are developed through the use of effective storytelling. Tesla is an illustration of this. Elon Musk was able to explain to the public the idea of a zero-emission future based on the use of entirely electric vehicles through deft and early storytelling. The brand was mocked by the competition for a long time, not least because of Elon Musk's grandiose storytelling pronouncements. Today, Tesla is the most valuable automotive company in the world based on market capitalization.

The concept of storytelling is also immensely relevant to scientific study. A search of the Scopus database produces 3,861 journal results for the years 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023 alone for the search term "Storytelling". In addition, a search for "Storytelling AND Marketing" returns 181 results for the years 2020, 2021, 2022, and 2023. As early as 2008, Woodside highlighted the importance of storytelling in marketing in his publication "When consumers and brands talk: Storytelling theory and research in psychology and marketing." Woodside is still actively exploring the topic 11 years later

(Woodside and Fine, 2019). And Jennifer Escalas remains active in this field of study after her first article connected to storytelling (Escalas, 2004, Berger et al., 2021). Storytelling is a research field that overlaps two scientific disciplines, notably marketing research and psychology. Numerous scientists' extensive research careers indicate that the fields of marketing and psychology still have unanswered topics to be investigated.

1.1 Statement of the issue

Traditionally, many research have focused on determining what motivates individuals to share digital advertisements and so produce virality. Increasing numbers of research have examined the psychological impacts of narratives and concluded that they have a favourable effect on viewers.

Few studies have examined the design elements (success factors) of successful commercials that favourably affect the viewer's attitudes in order to develop marketing suggestions. As a result, many commercials generated today are still based on subjective concerns and lack a scientific foundation.

Due to the lack of research in the field of narrative commercial design in social media, the purpose of this study is to determine how storytelling commercials must be developed in order to have a clearly good effect on viewers' attitudes.

1.2 The Study's Objectives

This results in two research objectives:

RO_1 = To highlight why content marketing and storytelling in particular are relevant marketing tools.

RO_2 = To identify which psychological theory regarding storytelling (narrative persuasion) can serve as a basis for the identification of success factors.

RO_3 = To evaluate which design features derived from psychological theory can be considered as success factors.

1.3 Research Questions

The aim is to clarify the following research questions:

RQ_1 = How should a storytelling commercial on YouTube be designed to successfully and positively influence the viewers' attitude towards the brand or the product?

RQ_2 = Do other factors or design features have a significant moderating influence on the impact of the success factors?

These research questions are examined based on several hypotheses.

1.4 Scope

The literature-derived hypotheses will inform the design of commercials that will be evaluated for their influence on attitude change. For these design elements, many narrative commercials were mapped. Thus, the influence of the many aspects may be analysed and comprehended in depth. In order to accurately answer the study questions, a questionnaire was performed online with the help of which commercials will just be shown to respondents. In the first phase, respondents were questioned about their perceptions of the particular brand after viewing the commercials. A subsequent commercial was then shown for the participants. After the commercial, the same questions asked about their attitudes as before the commercial. Accordingly, a noticeable shift in attitude caused by the commercial could be demonstrated. The study was carried out in Germany. There were 191 relevant replies available for evaluation.

1.5 Research method

Relevant to the selection of the research technique was the approach's capability to analyse the relevance of elements. Both reflective and formative elements must be capable of doing so. This is one of the reasons why the Partial Least Squares approach is employed to evaluate this study. The selection is explained in further detail in chapter three of the thesis.

1.6 Contribution

This study aims to address the gap in knowledge on the design elements of commercials that successfully induce attitude change through the use of narrative. For example, after Kang et al. (2020), Anaza et al. (2020) and Tseng and Huang (2016) demonstrated the positive effects of narratives in commercials, several studies have tried to investigate the design features of successful narrative commercials. There is no actual unanimity among the research, though. Multiple research indicate that emotionally conceived commercials are intended to have a greater commercial impact. Nonetheless, there are no set design criteria for how marketers should create their commercials. Moreover, no study has explored the relationship between design elements and attitude change. Thus, this research can significantly contribute to the

provision of clear design criteria for marketers' storytelling commercials, which have been proved to have a considerable influence on positive attitude change.

1.7 Thesis Structure

The second chapter establishes the required theoretical underpinnings for deriving hypotheses and research questions. The activation process within the customer journey and pertinent communication factors are examined, particularly in the context of new media. The area of content marketing is then discussed and its significance is emphasised, particularly in the context of YouTube. Additionally, the unique aspect of storytelling in marketing is addressed. Lastly, the pertinent psychological features of this study are investigated: Attitude and attitude change, as well as narrative persuasion as the psychological counterpart to storytelling in content marketing. In this area, the relevant theories are presented, which serve as the basis for the research. The chapter concludes with a literature review to identify the research gap and derive the relevant hypotheses and research questions.

The third chapter examines the research methods and study design. The employed stimuli and data gathering methods are explained. In addition, the sample's characteristics are provided. The Partial Least Square evaluation technique is described, along with its constituent computation stages. Finally, the research's findings are presented. In order to establish the validity of the results, the measurement and structural models are thoroughly analysed. The chapter concludes with a results summary.

This thesis finishes in chapter four with ramifications for corporate practise and academics. The limits of this thesis are then discussed.

2 Literature Review

This chapter defines and derives the fundamentals required for this project. To do this, the chapter is divided into seven sections. In the first section, the customer journey is described to clarify basically how this study will fit into the customer experience. In addition, the functioning of customer behaviour and the activation processes induced by certain advertising methods are discussed. The second section discusses communication structures. Various communication models are used to describe the psychological function of communication. These serve as a foundation for comprehending why advertising works and what processes it triggers in the recipient. The focus of the third section is content marketing. It explains why content marketing is essential for marketing success in the digital era. The importance of YouTube as a content marketing medium is also emphasised, as is storytelling as a content marketing strategy. Particularly, the linkage to YouTube and narrative is essential to this study. This is followed by a description of viral marketing and word-of-mouth, the anticipated outcomes of effective content marketing. Influencing variables for viral marketing are described, and the significance of content is clarified. While this issue is not examined in depth in this study, it is essential to have a fundamental grasp of it to comprehend why the successful production of YouTube commercials might result in a high level of virality. The fifth section of this chapter presents the psychological groundwork for this study. The concept of attitude is discussed, as is the process of modifying attitudes. For this purpose, the complicated issue of persuasion is presented using the subject's proven theories. The sixth section discusses narrative persuasion in relation to the issue of persuasion. This is the psychological perspective on storytelling. This section describes the prevalent models in this field, which serve as the foundation for this study. The literature review is presented in section seven. It is specified which studies were evaluated. In addition, a tabular description of each research is provided, detailing its scope, theoretical foundation, assessment technique, and outcomes. This also highlights the research gap that this study intends to fill.

2.1 Customer Journey and what behaviour it leads to

Before, during, and after the purchase of a product, the customer goes through a number of distinct phases. For many years, scientists have investigated the interrelationship of these separate stages. Along the entirety of the customer's journey, it is essential to provide an exceptional experience. The so-called customer experience.

Schmitt (1999) and Pine et al. (1999) were the first to point out the importance of customer experience. Marketing scholars have been slow to pick up on these developments in the marketing literature. Customer management has mainly focused on creating value from customers for companies (Gupta et al., 2004, Kumar and Shah, 2009), instead of creating value for customers (Kumar and Reinartz, 2016). The increasing focus on customer experience stems from the fact that customers now interact with companies across innumerable touchpoints in different channels and media, resulting in more complex customer experiences. Companies are faced with increasing media and channel fragmentation. In addition, customer-to-customer interaction via social media creates significant challenges and opportunities for businesses (Leeflang et al., 2013, Libai et al., 2010).

The customer experience is conceptualised as the journey a consumer takes with a firm throughout the buying cycle and across many touchpoints. The total customer experience is also known as a dynamic procedure. Customers perceive the transaction, from pre-purchase to actual purchase to post-purchase, as an integrated process. This occurs frequently and in a vigorous manner. This process is influenced by a customer's previous experiences, such as past purchases, as well as external influences. In this whole process, there are multiple relevant touchpoints for customers, but corporations only have control over a subset of them. This process is summarised in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Process Model for Customer Journey and Experience based on Lemon and Verhoef (2016)

This thesis focuses on the “Prepurchase Phase”. This phase is also of particular importance because it is the moment when the customer is confronted with the brand or product for the first time.

In the course of the customer journey, Lewis' AIDA (Attention, Interest, Desire, and Action) model from 1898 should also be mentioned, which can be seen as an impact stage model. AIDA is decoded into the terms “attention”, “interest”, “desire” and “action”. Here, a customer must pass through all four phases to reach the purchase decision. Translated into the AIDA model, this thesis deals with the attention phase, i.e., how do I get the necessary attention for my brand or product?

Among the relevant customer journey models, the Consumer Decision Journey (CDJ) model by Court et al. (2009) from McKinsey & Company should also be mentioned. This is a circular model that describes how consumers make their purchasing decisions. The phases are divided into: consider, evaluate, buy, enjoy and bond/advocate. Since these phases can overlap and repeat and additional aspects such as "customer loyalty", "customer retention" and "post-purchase experience" are depicted, the CDJ model has replaced most linear models.

The present study is difficult to map to this model because it focuses on the phase before consideration. As well described in the AIDA model, the attention phase is where the potential customer first encounters the brand or product. This is a crucial moment because, as with people, it is in these first moments that people form an opinion or have a certain attitude towards the brand or product. Or, if the brand or

product is already known, an attempt is made to influence this attitude at the beginning of a new customer journey. Most of the time, the content that is distributed in this phase serves a long-term purpose because a customer journey is a lengthy process that can last for years. During this time, brands repeatedly try to create a certain attitude towards the product or brand in the repetitive attention phase.

2.1.1 Consumer behaviour

The theory of consumer behaviour is an interdisciplinary field of research. It serves to characterise and explain customer behaviour so that marketing predictions and recommendations can be made based on this information. Generally speaking, theories are founded on a set of assumptions, sometimes known as if-then assertions. An essential element of the theory of consumer behaviour is the so-called stimulus-response (S-R) and stimulus-organism-response (S-O-R) approaches (details in chapter 2.2). They are founded on numerous hypotheses.

In marketing research, “advertising impact” is defined as the achievement of the desired response from the target group through advertising efforts. Advertising impact is a complex concept that cannot be quantified directly. Therefore, indicators must be utilised for measurement purposes. In the majority of advertising effect research, these so-called advertising impact indicators are separated into three components that indicate the psychological processes and responses of individuals: Cognitive, affective, and conative advertising impact (Maas, 2011, p. 521f). In addition, the “behavioural” or “action” component must be named here, which is directly connected to the other components. This component is due to Oliver (1999). In this way, the behavioural intentions of the individuals are to be distinguished from their actual behaviour.

The *cognitive* component essentially describes the processes of perception in the individual, such as attention, advertising recall, comprehensibility, and awareness. In more detail: An information processing system receives a stimulus input and processes the incoming information, i.e., it transforms and manipulates the incoming data to produce an output. This conception aims to reconstruct the processes of generating output information from input information (Newell and Simon, 1972). According to this, the cognitive component of advertising impact includes processes of perception and processing, as well as the storage and retrieval of information

(Lang, 2000). The cognitive processes can be based on previous information or knowledge or on recent experience with the product or brand (Oliver, 1999).

The *affective* component, on the other hand, describes the mental processes of the consumer's attitude. This encompasses, among other things, interest in a product or brand, appraisal and affinity for it, as well as the product or brand's final persuasiveness. Accordingly, the affective component comprises mental states of the consumer, such as emotions or moods (Solomon, 1993, Wirth, 2013, p. 227ff). Although emotions and moods are related to each other, they nevertheless represent different phenomena that can differ in their intensity, duration, and object orientation (Beedie et al., 2005).

The *conative* component in turn describes the intended behaviour of the individual, such as the purchase intention. Consequently, it depicts the behavioural intent that results from the cognitive and affective components. In prior advertising effectiveness studies, the conative component is typically quantified in terms of intents to act, such as purchase intention or product or brand preference (Vakratsas and Ambler, 1999).

The *action* component finally describes the actual or observed consumer behaviour. This stage is often also called "action control". In this phase, the motivated behavioural intention turns into a concrete desire to behave at this phase (Oliver, 1999).

Figure 2 Components of advertising impact based on Maas (2011, p. 522) and Oliver (1999)

When interpreting Figure 2, it becomes clear that attitude (the affective component) is the central component in the advertising effect. The design (cognitive component) of a commercial can impact attitudes, which in turn stimulate actual purchasing

behaviour (conative and active component). This is the reason why the purpose of this research is to investigate how content influences attitudes.

2.1.2 Activation Process

To comprehend how customers feel, think, and behave, it is necessary to comprehend the activating and cognitive (mental) processes occurring within an individual.

Figure 3 *Psychic determinants of the consumer process based on Esch (2017, p.42)*

Knowledge of consumers' activating and cognitive processes enhances the effectiveness of marketing strategies.

Understanding activating processes

Activating processes (see Figure 3) are processes associated with internal arousal and tension that drive human behaviour (Kroeber-Riel and Weinberg, 2009, p. 55 ff.). According to Kroeber-Riel and Esch (2004, p. 172), activation is described as "[...] a state of temporary or sustained inner arousal or alertness that results in the recipients turning towards a stimulus". They consist of (Kroeber-Riel and Weinberg, 2009, Trommsdorff and Teichert, 2011)

- Activation,
- Emotion,
- Motivation, attitude and satisfaction.

These variables are related as follows:

Figure 4 Attitude out of Activation based on Foscht et al. (2017, p.37)

At the course of the activation process, a consumer's attitude toward an advertised or sold product or service is formed.

Activation is the engine that drives human action and can be described as "excitement" or "inner tension." The activation level is a measure of the organism's willingness and performance (Kroeber-Riel and Weinberg, 2009, p. 61). The following three basic techniques can be used to trigger activation:

- Physically intense stimuli include large, loud and colourful stimuli.
- Emotional stimuli (e.g., images of people, especially faces, smiles of the saleswoman) also trigger activation and maintain a certain tension in the recipient. Particularly effective are key emotional stimuli (such as the childhood scheme or erotic images) that trigger biologically preprogrammed reactions in humans (Kroeber-Riel and Esch, 2011, p. 243 f.).
- Cognitively surprising stimuli are those that violate existing expectations and ideas of the recipient and thus lead to surprises, mental contradictions, or conflicts.

Emotion

Emotion is an activating process that is intended to explain the behaviour of consumers. Kroeber-Riel and Weinberg (Kroeber-Riel and Weinberg, 2003, p. 106) define emotions as "inner excitement processes that are felt as pleasant or unpleasant and more or less consciously experienced."

Emotions are directed inwards, towards the customer's own experience, but can be observed from the outside. According to Izard (Izard, 1971), there are ten essential emotions with distinct mime and gesture features. These basic or fundamental emotions are a part of the human experience. They have their origins in the evolution of man, culminating in a certain facial expression and subjective feeling. Fundamental emotions are mostly impacted by biology and less by the social environment. In certain civilizations, they have adapted to sociocultural situations and altered accordingly. These basic emotions are not usually experienced alone. By superimposing individual fundamental emotions, secondary emotions emerge, resulting in the development of distinct emotions. In addition to influencing facial expressions and body language, emotions can influence behaviour. Typically, they are automatic initiators of processes (Trommsdorff and Teichert, 2011, p. 64). These are crucial for marketing purposes.

Motivation

Emotions are the source of motivation. According to Kroeber-Riel et al. (2011, p. 56), motives are “emotions (and impulses) associated with a target orientation [...] in relation to behaviour.”

The motivation process is based on an emotion and thus also on activation. The terms “motivation” and “motives” are closely linked. While the motif is an enduring condition, motivation is a process that refers to updating the motif (Kroeber-Riel and Esch, 2011, p. 270). In this context, Maslow's needs pyramid should be mentioned. It is one of the best-known but also most controversial attempts to classify motifs. According to Maslow (Maslow, 1954), there are five distinct motif classes. Beginning at the base of the pyramid are primary necessities such as hunger and thirst. When the requirements of one class are satisfied, the needs of higher levels are pursued. This indicates that once the physiological or primary requirements are satisfied, the search for safety needs begins. This is followed by social needs, needs for appreciation and self-realization.

Attitude

Attitude is influenced by motivation, and consequently by emotion and activation. According to Kroeber-Riel et al. (2011, p. 56), attitudes are "motivations linked to a - cognitive - assessment of the subject".

Motivation and evaluation of an object, such as a car brand, must go hand in hand for the development of an attitude toward the object. Assuming that attitudes about organisations, products, or brands (hence referred to as items) drive purchasing behaviour, item attitudes are extremely important. For instance, if a certain model of a car brand is deemed desirable, the likelihood of purchasing it increases. This is reflected in the three-component theory as well. Furthermore, this is the reason why this study focuses on altering consumer attitudes. A more detailed description of attitudes and attitude change is provided in chapter 2.5.

The three-component theory (Rosenberg and Hovland, 1960) assumes that the attitude consists of the following three components:

- an affective component (the emotions and motivations associated with attitude),
- a cognitive component (experience and knowledge of a product) and
- a conative component (readiness for certain actions).

These three components are related, as shown below. According to Figure 5, the affective and cognitive adjustment components cause the conative component (here intention), which represents the intention to behave. The conative component in turn causes the actual behaviour. Behaviour in turn affects attitude, especially the affective and cognitive components.

Figure 5 Interaction between Attitude and Behaviour based on Rosenberg and Hovland (1960)

The three-component theory is founded on the attitude-behavior hypothesis (A-B hypothesis). It states that (purchasing) behaviour is influenced by attitude. The A-B theory is contentious due to the possibility of the reverse relationship (the behaviour influences the attitude). Nonetheless, it may be inferred that the greater the positive

attitudes regarding a product or brand, the greater the possibility of purchase. More detailed explanations will be provided in chapter 2.5.

The types of activation

A basic distinction is recognised in activation studies between tonic and phasic activation. Tonic activation characterises a person's longer-lasting state of awareness (degree of alertness) or activation level, and hence their overall performance. Phasic activation, on the other hand, refers to short-term changes in activation that are caused by a specific stimulus and so influence a person's performance in a specific context (Foscht et al., 2017, p.37). This study focuses primarily on phasic activation as a result of particular external stimulus influences, such as emotional advertising, and seeks to ascertain the short-term customer behaviour or their immediate response.

Activation in advertising effectiveness research

Research on the effectiveness of advertising is one of the primary applications of activation tactics. For many years, it has been debated the properties an advertisement must possess in order to elicit a certain activation in the customer, as well as the results of this activation. In advertising, activating stimuli are frequently employed to produce better information absorption, faster information processing, and longer-lasting information storage in the customer. Due to the plethora of products and brands available today, which frequently differ in quality just somewhat, the importance of standing out in order to catch the consumer's attention and pique his interest is growing (Foscht et al., 2017, p. 43). In order to obtain a stronger activation of the consumer and, eventually, to influence the consumer's behaviour, it is becoming increasingly vital to provide distinct or unique advertising (Duffy, 1962). In addition, a number of research have demonstrated that a consumer's activation level has a favourable effect on his perception, attitude, and behaviour (Berger and Milkman, 2012a, Yang and Smith, 2009). Consequently, various emotions can result in stronger behavioural intentions on the part of individuals, such as the intention to share a commercial up to and including the desire to purchase (Berger and Milkman, 2012a).

This thesis expands on prior research and using activation theory to explain the drivers of social media (YouTube) engagement among consumers.

2.1.3 Cognitive Processes

The three-memory model

A closer examination of the equations of emotion, motivation, and attitude demonstrates that cognitive processes increasingly augment the basic activation processes: Motivation contains more cognitive content than emotion, whereas attitude contains more cognitive content than both (Kroeber-Riel and Esch, 2011, p. 60). Cognitive processes are mental processes that involve the processing of information about the environment and the individual. This is the appropriate method for controlling and determining this behaviour. This chapter expands on the cognitive processes necessary to explain consumer behaviour.

Cognitive processes are divided into three sub-processes:

- Information intake,
- Information processing (perception and assessment) and
- Storage of information (learning and memory).

The three-memory model, which can be seen as a general model for the aforementioned processes' principles, will be presented first. In the so-called "three-memory model," information acquisition, processing, and storage are addressed. The three-memory model hypothesises that cognitive processes occur in three distinct memories, namely the sensory memory, the short-term memory, and the long-term memory.

These memories can be characterized as follows.

1. sensory memory (ultra-short time memory):

- perceives sensory impressions only briefly,
- large capacity and
- short memory duration (max. one second).

2. short-term memory (working memory):

- central unit of information processing,
- the new information is compared with existing experiences and classified into existing perception patterns,
- Information is either deleted or stored in the long-term memory and

- limited capacity (e.g. 20 information units can be recorded within five seconds).

3. long-term memory (long-term memory):

- Information is stored for the long term, knowledge is built up as a result,
- information cannot be deleted at first and
- knowledge is structured.

Recording of information

Information recording includes procedures that result in the storage of data in the working memory. There is a fundamental contrast between internal and exterior information recording. On the one hand, customers can store information in their own memory or actively seek it out. The information from the long-term memory is subsequently often transmitted to the working memory (e.g., previous experience with a product). During an active information search, the consumer can retrieve previously stored information from long-term memory. In passive internal information recording, the consumer may recall information from his or her memory by unintentionally.

Sometimes, knowledge from memory is insufficient to solve a consumer's difficulty with decision-making. The consumer then searches for further information in his environment, such as stores, friends, family, books, brochures, the Internet, etc. This sort of search is known as "external information gathering" since the customer explores external sources for information. Active and passive external information recording are distinguished in the context of external information recording. During external information recording, the information is initially stored in the sensory memory before being filtered and passed to the working memory.

For external active information searches, sales talks, advice from friends and acquaintances, publications, shop windows, advertisements, and the Internet are preferred (Kroeber-Riel and Esch, 2011, p. 306). The use of the source is related to the respective product, industry, or involvement.

In the context of passive information recording, customers do not actively search for information; rather, they passively record it. It can respond to information such as the top left and bottom right text of a website when seeing an advertisement out of habit. Or it can respond automatically to the colour of the advertisement, such as bright or

red parts. Information can also be passively recorded if, for instance, television advertisements related to the purchase of a product are accidentally broadcast.

Information processing

Perception is understood as a process of information processing. Kroeber-Riel and Esch (2011, p. 320) define perception as follows: "Perception is an information processing process through which the individual gains knowledge of himself and his environment."

The five senses are primarily responsible for perception in the narrower sense: sight, hearing, smell, taste, and touch.

Information storage

Long-term memory holds information. As soon as we obtain new information, it will be made available. The new information is then compared to the knowledge already stored. For marketing purposes, it is essential to comprehend how this information is stored in long-term memory. One can distinguish between the substance and structure of knowledge, which are explored in further depth below.

In the human memory, knowledge is preserved as information. One can refer to brands, firms, product categories, stores, advertising, how the product is purchased and how it is utilised, among other things. Schemata preserve knowledge content in the memory of a consumer. The definition of a scheme is as follows (Hoyer et al., 2013, p. 106): "Schema is the group of associations or associative network linked to an object or person."

There are schemes for product categories (e.g., automobiles), brands (e.g., Coca-Cola), branches (e.g., supermarket branches), sales representatives (cosmetics salesperson, automobile salesperson), businesses (e.g., Apple, Starbucks), locations (e.g., downtown Hamburg), and countries (e.g., USA, China). Consumers also develop schemes for themselves, which they may compare to the schemes of the things they purchase or utilise.

Example scheme of an electric car

The electric car is given here as an example of a product group's schematic. The media has provided the majority of individuals with knowledge and connotations regarding what they associate with an electric vehicle.

Table 1 Example schema of an electric car

Characteristic feature	Association
Attributes of an electric car	white colour, clumsy design
Advantages of an electric car	environmentally friendly, high driving dynamics, driving pleasure, quiet driving
Disadvantages of an electric car	short reach, long charging times, problems with safety in the case of accidents
People who use electric cars	innovative people for whom the environment is important, rather male, well educated, 30-50 years old, above-average income
Places where electric cars are used	in large cities such as Hamburg or Berlin

In marketing, branding and brand extension strategies can be utilised. The customer's existing knowledge is utilised, and new information is added to the customer's knowledge context.

The brain utilises both schemata and scripts (Hoyer et al., 2013, p. 108). These instructions are stored as knowledge in the human brain as sequences of acts or events. Most adults are able to operate a vehicle with an engine. Insert the key and turn it until the engine begins to run. Then, change into first gear and scan the area. When there are no other vehicles on the road, accelerate and release the clutch (if necessary, release the handbrake first). These scripts for driving an electric automobile are not yet available to the majority of drivers. It is necessary to understand how to drive and refill an electric vehicle. The absence of these scripts hinders the acceptability and growth of electric vehicles.

Structuring of knowledge

The structuring of knowledge defines how it will be arranged in the human mind throughout time. In long-term memory, information and schemes are grouped into categories. A memory-based classification of schemes occurs on multiple levels. At each level, products of the same category are categorised.

Learning

Learning produces knowledge, which is defined as follows: (Kroeber-Riel and Esch, 2011, p. 364): "Learning is understood as a relatively permanent change in behaviour due to experience or observation."

The consumer absorbs information and stimuli, processes them, and responds properly when learning. He has a variety of options regarding how to behave. Thus, learning can also be viewed as the link between stimuli and observable behaviour (reactions). Scientists have developed numerous hypotheses regarding how learning occurs. In respect to classical conditioning, Trommsdorff and Teichert (Trommsdorff and Teichert, 2011, p. 254) describe intuitive or emotional conditioning as follows: “In the process, an initially meaningless brand name is gradually linked firmly with a certain positive feeling. ... The object of conditioning is not the physical brand, but its symbolic representation, usually in the form of a name or logo.”

According to the principle of classical conditioning, a brand is emotionally charged in marketing when an emotionally designed image is routinely presented alongside the brand name or logo (for example, in an advertisement). After all, the brand name alone may evoke a positive reaction. The brand name derives from the conditioned stimulus that generates the conditioned reaction.

Forgetting

Learning causes the storage of information in long-term memory. However, not all of the information will be retained. Therefore, forgetting processes are important in marketing since they must be minimised. Brand names are an example of information that can be remembered for a very long time, while prices are an example of information that is more easily forgotten. Two theories should be disregarded (Trommsdorff and Teichert, 2011, p. 258):

- Fading theory: This theory assumes that a trace of memory slowly fades beyond recognition;
- Inference theory: this theory assumes that new traces of memory overlay old traces of memory and make it difficult to find old traces of memory.

Learning and subsequent amnesia are advantageous to marketing, especially advertising. Knowing this makes it easy to comprehend how to avoid forgetfulness. Repetition is known to slow the forgetting process. For example, a taught exercise is forgotten more slowly after five repetitions than after two repetitions (Kroeber-Riel and Esch, 2011, p. 407). Thus, efforts are made to progressively disseminate commercial messages.

2.1.4 Decision-making behaviour

This chapter explores in further detail the interaction between activating and cognitive processes. Purchase decisions are frequently influenced by both of these processes.

When it comes to the behaviour of decision-making, several business administration disciplines prefer to focus on the cognitive aspect. In decision theories, for instance, decision trees, capital values, genuine alternatives, and other tools that can aid in selecting the optimal option are discussed. Homo economicus is utilised by economics to analyse and predict market behaviour. Real-world business practises demonstrate that decisions that are commonly judged reasonable and, therefore, appear to be purely cognitive frequently incorporate emotional elements. For example, emotions and trust are just as crucial in business-to-business marketing as the usually cited analytic criteria. To obtain an accurate depiction of complex decision-making processes, it is vital to analyse both activating and cognitive processes in the context of their interaction.

Kroeber-Riel and Esch (2011, p. 411) propose a differentiation between four types of purchasing decision behaviour. They describe these four purchase decisions using the following processes:

- affective processes (activation and its interpretation),
- cognitive processes (mental control of the decision) and
- reactive processes (automatic reaction in certain situations).

Based on the extent to which emotive, cognitive, and reactive processes are engaged, four basic types of purchase decisions can be distinguished: extensive, limited, habitualized, and impulsive.

2.1.4.1 Processes with stronger cognitive control

Extensive purchasing behaviour

A purchase choice is governed by cognitive and emotive processes in extensive purchasing behaviour. First-time purchases are frequently of sophisticated and costly items, such as automobiles, real estate, smartphones, and digital cameras. Extensive purchasing decisions (search purchase) are characterised by the following characteristics (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011, p. 172):

- high demand for information,
- long decision period,
- the need to use criteria for product evaluation and selection, and
- Use of internal and external information sources for information search.

Extensive purchasing behaviour is most comparable to economic theories of behaviour. The fewer times a buyer has purchased a product, the more likely it is that there are no associated choice patterns. Therefore, an exhaustive search for information is required.

Limited buying behaviour

In contrast to large purchasing judgments, limited purchasing decisions are virtually totally governed by cognitive processes. Here, the consumer can already rely on his own experiences and established decision criteria to make a choice. A replacement for a smartphone can serve as an example (after already made experiences by a first purchase). The limited decision can be viewed as an intermediary step between extensive and habitualized purchasing behaviour: the process of information processing is not as pronounced as in extensive purchasing behaviour, nor is it as severely constrained as in habitualized purchasing behaviour.

The following characteristics can be attributed to limited purchasing behaviour (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011, p. 174):

- only a limited selection of alternatives is considered (so-called evoked set),
- proven assessment criteria are used,
- the selection follows the consumer's level of ambition - as soon as a product meets a level of ambition, the search is completed and a purchase decision is made.

2.1.4.2 Processes with less cognitive control

Habitualized buying behaviour

In habitualized buying behaviour, little activating or cognitive processes are engaged, and the customer behaves in a purely reactive manner. In this instance, purchase behaviour is founded on strongly established patterns of behaviour. The transaction occurs virtually automatically. Examples include the purchase of a cleaning product that was previously utilised in the home and the acquisition of everyday consumables

(e.g. coffee, butter). This typically entails the repurchase of the same products, services, or brands, or the selection of particular shopping venues.

The habitualized purchase decision is described as follows (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011, p. 178):

- prefabricated decision patterns,
- a clear preference for a single alternative,
- short decision duration,
- fast, low-risk purchases,
- Relevance especially for daily necessities.

In contrast to limited purchase decisions, in which the buyer chooses from an evocative set, habitualized purchase decisions typically involve a single alternative.

Three different causes are mentioned for habitualised purchase decisions (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011, p. 178 f):

- Personal tendency to habitualization: Habitualization is a personality trait in this case. People must simplify their lives, such as by purchasing a branded product. The inclination towards habituation increases with age and diminishes with social standing.
- Own experiences: After contentment with a purchase, a decision that was initially extensive can evolve into a habitual decision.
- Adoption of behavioural patterns in the context of socialisation processes: Individuals watch and mimic the behaviour patterns of others. This can occur, for instance, when other people's experiences are adopted, such as through recommendations. Typically, parents influence their children's purchasing behaviour.

Impulsive buying behaviour

Typically, impulsive purchasing behaviour is very emotional and reactive. Consequently, impulse purchases are characterised by a high activation rate and swift action. They are significantly less cognitively controlled than other purchasing decisions. Examples include impulse purchases prompted by point-of-sale displays or tasting stands in supermarkets.

Usually two different causes for impulse buying (impulse buying) are cited (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011, p. 180):

- Unique stimulus conditions, i.e., situational factors and the customer's subjective perception of them, initiate the purchasing process;
- Psychic activities, such as the quest of pleasure and the fulfilment of unique desires, might stimulate impulsive purchasing.

2.1.5 Involvement

Customer involvement is an important marketing concept that combines activation and cognitive processes. Trommsdorff and Teichert (Trommsdorff and Teichert, 2011, p. 48) even describe it as a key structure for marketing and marketing research. Meffert et al. (Meffert, 2012, p. 111) understand involvement as “the degree of 'Self-Participation' or the commitment of a person to take an interest in certain facts or tasks.”

Targeted activation becomes less important as the level of engagement of the target audience for marketing initiatives rises. However, the weaker the involvement, the greater the activation. Marketing frequently deals with consumers who are uninvolved. Exceptions to this rule are typically concrete decision situations and the corresponding active search for information via personal sales conversations, brochures, or the Internet. A highly involved consumer is strongly encouraged, for instance, to think or feel intensely about a product (Kroeber-Riel and Esch, 2011, p. 195). In practise, involvement is frequently synonymous with product involvement, or interest in a particular product category. This perspective is too limited and misleading. The involvement consists of multiple dimensions (Kroeber-Riel and Esch, 2011, p. 196, Trommsdorff, 2009, p. 47 ff.):

- Personal Involvement: People can be involved to varying degrees in the same situations based on their individual personality traits and characteristics (knowledge, experience, attitudes, motives, values).
- Product involvement: Consumer engagement with a product or product category varies according to price, perceived functional risks of purchase and use, and social risks (acceptance of a product within a social group).
- In connection with this, brand involvement is also considered, which is reflected in customers' interest in a brand.
- Situation involvement: Under time constraints, there is less concentration on something.

- Media involvement: Interest in print media is generally greater than in television, which is considered a classic low-involvement medium.
- Advertising media involvement: This results from the activation power of the marketing instruments used (= reaction involvement).

The scenario greatly determines the total involvement. Less involvement diminishes the certainty of an attitude towards behavior's consequence. In the event of low-involvement first purchases (such as the purchase of chewing gum), for instance, a product is purchased without consideration; the attitude is only created thereafter. Similarly, impulsive buying behaviour (purchase based on a secondary placement impulse) does not result in an attitude until after the purchase.

2.2 Communication

Marketing is built on the foundation of communication. The fundamental features of communication are described and modelled in this section. Digital communication, which is pertinent to this study, will also be discussed. This covers social media as well.

People encounter communication on a daily basis, however issues occur when attempting to describe or define communication. But, why is this definition so challenging? On the one hand, this is owing to the fact that the definitions of communication have evolved continuously over time. On the other hand, communication is a broad phrase that can encompass facial emotions and unsaid sentiments. Due to the emergence of new media, new communication routes have also emerged. Communication policy is one of the 4 Ps or marketing mix components (Product - Place - Price - Promotion). The purpose of communication policy is to plan, create, coordinate, and control the communication measures of the firm so that marketing and corporate objectives may be attained (Meffert et al., 2018, p. 632).

2.2.1 Communication - Characteristics and Definition

Based on Six et al. (Six et al., 2007), the following characteristics of communication can be identified:

- Communication refers to a process between at least two participants (these are called senders and receivers). An exception to this is intrapersonal communication (e. g. in the form of a monologue). The persons involved relate

to each other by exchanging signs and symbols (either directly, i. e. face to face or indirectly). A common repertoire of signs and symbols, their understanding as well as a common background of experience and knowledge is an important basis for successful communication.

- The message corresponds to the characters and symbols decoded by the sender and the recipient. The sent and received messages do not necessarily have to correspond (e. g. in case of misunderstandings).
- Both the sending and receiving of messages require appropriate means or modalities (e. g. during direct communication, facial expression and language or in the case of media-mediated communication, e. g. the corresponding radio link).
- Communication always takes place in a certain context. In addition to other factors, such as the prevailing communication rules, the respective communication climate can also influence the entire communication process and its results. The participants are not passive. However, not every activity is directly observable for us. You perform visible (e. g., a gesture) and invisible activities (e. g., impression formation from the person opposite).
- Communication has an interactive process character and is characterized by mutual influence. The degree of reciprocity is also related to the specific form of communication (e. g. direct individual communication vs. mass communication).
- Although communication always pursues a goal (e. g. search for entertainment or information), it does not always have to be done completely consciously. For example, a person who disagrees with a statement may involuntarily frown. In this way it can be stated that communication is always target-oriented, but not necessarily completely conscious.

Finally, it should be mentioned that a precise definition of communication cannot be formulated and lacks significance. It may be claimed that communication must possess the aforementioned qualities.

2.2.2 Communication psychology

Communication psychology refers to the study of communication's structures and processes. Social systems spanning from interactions between two individuals, so-called dyads (e.g., couples), families, work teams, and other groups to societal

settings are analysed (Frindte, 2001, p. 29 f.). Interpersonal communication and media communication are both investigated. Not just communication behaviour, but also its influencing elements and settings, as well as the outcomes or repercussions of communicative acts, are investigated (i. e. the communication results).

Communication outcomes are primarily individual and societal reality constructs, as communication with others impacts how one views his or her surroundings. The impact of the media on the person must be questioned in this setting. It generates a particular impression of reality for a substantial portion of the populace.

Communication psychology examines, explains, and predicts the processes and outcomes of communication in terms of psychological factors. To this end, the afflicted individuals' experiences, behaviour, and cognitions, as well as their surroundings and situational features, are taken into account. According to the investigated type of communication, communication psychology study may be classified into the psychology of direct communication and media-mediated communication.

2.2.2.1 Communication models

This chapter examines popular psychological models of communication that attempt to explain the communication process. These must be distinguished from generic communication models, which foster the communication issue by combining several economic sectors. Krauss and Fussell (1996) recognised four categories of psychological communication models based on an exhaustive review of the literature:

1. **Encoder/Decoder models:** The practise of encoding one's thoughts and attitudes through a medium or code is communication (language). Encoding is equivalent to coding. The media or codes are transmitted via a communication channel to a designated recipient. The media or codes must next be decoded by the receiver. This is referred to as decoding. The primary objective of such models (encoder/decoder models) is to acquire a comprehensive understanding of the encoding or encryption process and the simultaneous transmission of the decryption process, also known as decoding. At the same time, they wish to provide a solution regarding the optimal method of message transmission. Therefore, it is necessary to identify sources of interference to maintain optimal communication. Shannon and Weaver's model (Shannon and Weaver, 1949) and Schulz von Thun's model fit into this group (Schulz von Thun et al., 2000).

2. **Intentional models:** These models focus mostly on the communicator's intentions toward the recipient. Therefore, the topic of how communication might be successful is fundamental (i. e. how communicators and recipients can reach an agreement on what has been said). How is this to be accomplished? According to the Grice communication model (Grice, 1975), the dialogue maxims allocated to this category attempt to answer this question.
3. **Perspective transfer models:** Within these approaches, the goal is for communicators to put themselves in the perspective of their interlocutor or to be able to do so. This assumes that both parties are willing to place themselves in the other's shoes. Roger's rules for effective communication (Rogers and Roethlisberger, 1991) fall under this category. In the field of goal-oriented conversational psychotherapy, these models can be deduced from psychology.
4. **Dialog models:** This focuses on how both parties can reach realism in their communications. Watzlawick's axioms (Watzlawick et al., 2000) represent the effort to determine the process's fundamental properties.
5. **Computer Mediated Communication Models:** This phrase comprises many modes of human communication using networked computers, which can be synchronous or asynchronous and involve one-to-one, one-to-many, or many-to-many text, audio, and/or video interactions.

2.2.2.2 Communication model according to Shannon and Weaver

Probably the most well-known model in communication psychology was created by Claude E. Shannon and Warren Weaver in the 1940s. This model's foundation is essentially technical and was derived from information theories, both of which have a technological underpinning (they were mathematicians and telecommunications specialists). The model is not concerned with the message's substance, but rather its transmission and reception. The objective was to optimise technical transmission communication. According to Shannon and Weaver (1949), communication consists of six essential components. In the case of interference, seven components are present.

The communication procedure begins with the information source (the sender). Using a transmitter, the operator picks a message and transmits it in the form of signals (coder). The sent signals are picked up and decoded by the addressee (the receiver)

via a receiver device (the decoder). In spoken language, the source of the message is the brain, and the vocal chords generate the changing sound pressure (i.e., the signal) that is sent via the air (i. e. the channel). The process of signal transmission is susceptible to interference (e. g. noise). During the transmission process, the sender may mistakenly add items to the signal (i.e., the message). Noise arises. Possible sources of interference include, for example, sound distortion (for telephone communication), atmospheric interference (for radio transmission), and visual distortion (for communication via television). Transferred to direct communication, interference might arise because the channel (i.e., the air) is not entirely "silent".

Figure 6 Shannon and Weaver Communication model based on Shannon and Weaver (1949)

To communicate effectively, both parties must pay equal attention and possess the essential expertise. Consequently, identical character and semantic talents (e.g. a certain language). Additionally, the message's transmission should be as error-free as feasible, allowing for feedback or a response. According to Shannon and Weaver, errors in coding or decoding could account for a recipient's lack of or unexpected response (e. g. incorrect translation or ambiguity in different languages). For instance, an ambiguous phrase may be misunderstood by the recipient and consequently fail to elicit the desired response.

2.2.2.3 Communication model by Schulz von Thun

From an application standpoint, Schulz von Thun's communication model offers a high degree of applicability. This paradigm can be used to analyse one's own communication critically. There are still empirical gaps in the model. Watzlawick (Watzlawick et al., 1969) and Bühler (Bühler, 1934) provide the foundation for Schulz von Thun's model. According to von Thun, communication should always be regarded from four perspectives, both from the perspective of the sender and the recipient. A statement carries four simultaneous messages:

1. **Subject matter:** The core of a message is factual information which is to be transmitted to the recipient by the sender.
2. **Self-disclosure:** Through a message, the sender discloses information about him/herself. This can be done consciously for positive self-presentation or unconsciously as so-called self-discovery.
3. **Relationship statement:** The relationship between two people is revealed through communication. Even addressing a person reveals the relationship of two communication partners.
4. **Appeal:** Senders of a message want their message to have an effect on the recipient. The aim is for the recipient to do, think or feel something in particular.

Figure 7 Schulz von Thun communication model based on Schulz von Thun et al. (2000)

Analogue the following part of a communication has to be named on the receiver side:

1. Factual part (How should the facts of a message be understood?)
2. Self-disclosure part (What kind of person is the sender of a message?)
3. Relationship part (How does the message sender talk to the message receiver?)
4. Appeal part (what should the recipient of a message think or feel?)

When the intentions of the sender and the recipient do not align, communication issues develop. According to Schulz von Thun, the quality of communication depends on how successfully the decryption of the sender's intent succeeds. Schulz von Thun (Schulz von Thun et al., 2000) also hypothesises that one-sided receiving practises can result in communication disruptions.

2.2.2.4 Grice communication maxims

Grice (1975) defines communication as a cooperative action between a message's sender and receiver. The primary objective, according to Grice, is for the recipient to be able to comprehend the message in the best way possible. Thus, the communication objective can be achieved. There is a distinction between what is expressed and what is intended.

According to Grice, communication is impossible unless the sender and receiver share a common goal. On this basis, he explains his cooperation philosophy. Therefore, communication partners must coordinate their communications in accordance with Grice's four maxims, taking into account the conversation's objectives and duration. A violation of these maxims, according to Grice, results in ineffective and deceptive communication.

The following table shows these maxims (Grice, 1975):

Table 2 Grice communication maxims

The maxim of quantity
"Make an effort to provide the relevant facts!" Contribute as much information as is required for the specified objective, avoiding superfluous details. Violation of the maxim: speak too less or say too much
The maxim of quality
"Make an effort to make your input valid!" Don't say anything you think is wrong. Do not say anything without sufficient justification. Violation of the maxim: irony or questionable claim
The maxim of relevance
"Be relevant!" Say what pertains to the topic. Do not deviate from the topic in any way. Violation of the maxim: uttering irrelevant and unimportant matters
The maxim of clarity
"Be clear!" Avoid confusing and imprecise language. Avoid vagueness. Avoid verbosity. Focus on logical temporal sequences. Violation of the maxim: imprecise or confused discourse

2.2.2.5 Rules for successful communication according to Rogers

Carl Rogers has established standards for the execution of a perspective transfer in his rules of client-centered conversation therapy. The rules are fundamental for professional communication fields including counselling and therapy. However, they can also be used to traditional social connections. Rogers asserts that counsellors and therapists must possess three behavioural and personality attributes for optimal communication with their clients. These are the three qualities that define empathy, authenticity, and emotional appreciation.

A person's empathy makes it feasible for him to perceive himself in other individuals. Because of this, empathy is examined more closely. Other features are not elaborated upon. Two characteristics comprise the definition of empathy. It is necessary, on the one hand, to put yourself in the other person's shoes and feel his or her emotions. Conversely, it is a matter of conveying to the other party what you have understood. Rogers initially recognised the significance of relationship design in terms of posited therapist factors to the success of therapy (Rogers, 1961).

2.2.2.6 Communication model after Watzlawick

The communication model developed by Paul Watzlawick in 1969 is based on five assumptions. Unlike the sender-receiver model, this model is characterised by its dynamic nature and interactivity. Watzlawick states that communication occurs in a cycle. Consequently, not only the sender's message to the recipient, but also the recipient's response to the sender, is relevant. Watzlawick adds psychological processes in his model in this way. At the same time, neither the sender nor the receiver imposes conditions on the communication. According to this approach, not only do communication partners exchange information, but the sending and receiving is also governed by their respective interests.

Watzlawick summarizes the rules of human communication in five axioms:

1. Axiom to the impossibility of not communicating
2. Axiom on the content and relationship aspect of communication
3. Axiom for punctuating sequences of events
4. Axiom to digital vs. analog communication
5. Axiom to symmetrical vs. complementary communication

“From the first day of one's life, the human begins to learn the rules of communication, even though they are not necessarily made aware of by the actors.” (Watzlawick et al., 2000, p. 13). Disturbances in communication are attributed to violations of axioms (Watzlawick et al., 2000). Watzlawick sees a way for recognising and, if required, correcting communication difficulties in the field of metacommunication. The definition of metacommunication is communication regarding the current conversation. The five communication axioms outlined by Watzlawick et al. (2000) are as follows:

Axiom one: "You cannot not communicate." This axiom is founded on the observation that all interpersonal behaviour is communicative in nature (e. g. acting or not acting, silence, words or missing words). Thus, all behaviour constitutes communication. Can one behave poorly? No. Consequently, you cannot communicate. Watzlawick assumes that (intentional or not) communication occurs as soon as people recognise themselves.

Axiom two: "Every communication has a content and a relationship aspect" According to this axiom, we should divide communication into its substance (i.e., the "what" of the message) and its relational aspect (i.e., the "how" of the message), similar to how we split the human being into body and soul. The content is primarily communicated verbally and consists of purely factual information. The relational aspect, however, is communicated both vocally and nonverbally. It explains how the recipient is to interpret the factual information and how the sender defines the relationship between himself or herself and the recipient. The "what" and "how" of a message can sometimes be in direct opposition to one another, making effective communication more challenging. In the case of irony, for example, only facial expression, tone of voice, and context may typically disclose the communicator's intent. This makes it more difficult to recognise irony in text messages.

The distinction between the content and relationship levels has a considerable bearing on communication difficulties. These frequently alter the amount of relationship. They arise, for instance, when relationship-level issues are addressed at the content level or when there is a disagreement on the nature of relationship.

Axiom three: "Communication sequences are structured differently" From the perspective of objective observers, communication is circular. It is therefore a continual communication with no clearly defined beginning or end. What is the reason and what is the effect of communication partners' subjective interpretation? Watzlawick's constructivist stance posits that humans live in a reality produced by

their personal experiences and evaluations. Because we believe this subjective reality to be true, it dictates our actions. Problematically, interaction partners may assume a distinct reality.

According to Watzlawick, humans construct their reality as a punctuation of sequences of events, i.e., they assign special significance to specific events and, in a sense, view them as the cause and trigger for subsequent events in their lives. If individuals now justify or explain their own behaviour by reference to the behaviour of others, this might result in interaction disruptions. The interlocutor simply views his or her behaviour as a consequence of his or her activities.

Axiom four: "Human communication uses digital and analog modalities." Watzlawick makes a distinction between digital and analogue modes of human communication. The distinction between the two modalities relates directly to Axiom 2: Complementary digital and analogue communication methods (similar to content and relationship aspects). Typically, the relationship part of a communication is communicated analogously while the content aspect is transmitted digitally. In addition to intercommunication (i.e., digital modality), one must always consider body language, speech-style, and context (i.e., analogue modality). It is obvious that the two modalities are challenging to comprehend independently. A significant flaw of analogue mode is that it does not appear to be unambiguous. A person who smiles can, on the one hand, solicit sympathy and, on the other hand, communicate disdain. In contrast, the digital mode lacks an ideal lexicon for elucidating relationships. In addition, it is simpler to make a digital confession than it is to convey the same information via an analogy. Digital and analogue communication's ambiguity might interfere with interpersonal communication. Similarly to Axiom 2, if there is a gap between digital and analogue communication, there will be a communication disturbance.

Axiom five: "Interpersonal communication processes are either symmetrical (equivalent) or complementary, depending on whether the relationship between the partners is based on equality or difference." In complimentary relationships, the interaction process is determined by the complementary nature of the parties' respective behaviours. The foundation for this is the complementarity-oriented variety of the partners. People who strive for a balanced relationship, on the other hand, want to avoid inequities. Humans inhabit a variety of social positions and interactions. As a result, they alternate between symmetry and complementarity. Typically, institutions

or social settings impose acceptable behavioural standards (e. g., lecturer and student, customer and salesperson). Therefore, complementarity does not necessarily imply inferiority or passivity of a component. Typically, complementary partnerships are formed not by one individual imposing this type of relationship on another, but by the other individual accepting the role definition. Typically, when a position description shifts, the connection likewise shifts (e. g., student meets lecturer in the soccer club, whereby the previously complementary relationship now becomes-temporarily-symmetrical). On the other hand, extremely extensive and rigid complementarity is troublesome. Likewise, severe opposition to complementarity (such as the need not to be inferior) might result in symmetrical escalation.¹

2.2.2.7 Computer mediated communication models

In the early approaches to theoretical explanation, computer-mediated communication (CMC) was compared with interpersonal communication. Emails and online forums were compared to human contact in this context as a significantly less sophisticated type of text communication. It was attempted to explain why CMC communication partners typically considered each other superficially and did not permit social emotions. This is due to the high level of anonymity, which leads to diminished reactions compared to the real world. Famous theories of this time are the media richness theory by Daft and Lengel (1986), lack of social context cues hypothesis by Sproull and Kiesler (1986) and the social presence theory by Short et al. (1976).

In the 1990s, a novel theoretical approach on CMC emerged alongside the introduction of the Internet for private use and the rise in popularity of stories about facilitative online communities. These new theories offered opinions that were less restrictive. An influential theory of our time is Walther (1992) social information processing theory. This theory describes how CMC audiences gradually compensate for the lack of non-verbal signals on the Internet by employing verbal cues and interaction tactics in imaginative ways in order to encrypt and decrypt behavioral – emotional information throughout CMC. This theory was developed to explain how

¹ Symmetrical escalation: When striving for equality, there is sometimes the need to be "a bit more equal". A person tries to gain a slight advantage over the other person in an area that is important for his or her self-definition. In return, it will try to reduce the complementarity that has now arisen and possibly even gain a slight advantage. A "swinging up" of such a kind begins in relationship systems that have lost stability and become rivalries.

CMC audiences compensate for the absence of non-verbal signals on the Internet. Because of this, the degree to which impressions are created between communication counterparts as well as the closeness of CMC could be equivalent to that of direct interaction as long as adequate time and messages are shared. Walther (1996) 's hyperpersonal communication model is another widely influential model from this era; it predicts, but in a more hopeful manner, that text-only conversations may produce more favourable images of a counterpart and greater intimacy than face-to-face communication. This model predicts that producing messages drives communication partners to portray each other in the most favourable light. By utilising the CMC capacity to have better self-control, they are able to portray oneself in a more pleasant or appealing manner than is generally done or is possible in face-to-face interactions. Those receiving communication close the gaps in their opinions of their counterparts that the absence of audio-visual clues has created, thereby encouraging them to idealise their counterparts. This, according to Walther, can make CMC hyperpersonal, or more intimate than offline conversation.

The focus of early computer-mediated communication (CMC) concepts on privacy protection and restricted non-verbal signals was appropriate up until the year 2005 because CMC was primarily in writing and was mainly carried out in online discussion spaces and message groups among individuals whose identities were unknown to each other. Online communication has become more sophisticated as a result of the proliferation of internet platforms such as YouTube, Twitter, Facebook, WhatsApp, and Instagram. This has led to the incorporation of a wider variety of audio-visual platforms as well as the utilisation of connections that already exist. Individuals today make use of a great number of communication platforms, the majority of which are text-based and audio - visual in nature. Due to these advancements, comparing particular CMC services with one another or with direct communication has become increasingly difficult and, at times, less useful.

Through the usage of internet platforms such as Facebook, communication may occur via multipath channels inside a network, and the number of target groups may range from one to several. The development of social networking on the internet has made it feasible for anybody with access to the internet to function as a transmitter of information, i.e., a creator of content and a supplier of media. In light of the fact that a significant amount of the information that is communicated via social media is both intimate and self-referential, Castells (2007, p. 248) has identified a "new type of

socialised communication" which he refers "mass self-communication". Even though "its content is self-generated, its broadcast self-directed," (Castells, 2007, p.248) and it focuses largely on self-referential information, mass self-communication has the potential to reach an audience on a worldwide scale, much like mass communication. The implications of the idea of mass self-communication for CMC theories are profound. This is due to the fact that many CMC ideas lack the constraints that plagued some of the older media effects hypotheses. Typically, these two ideas presume that certain qualities of media or technologies have unidirectional effects on their viewers. Rather than focusing largely on communication between two or more individuals, CMC theories have frequently emphasised the consequences of particular CMC features for the recipients of those attributes. In media impacts and CMC theories, receiver effects are frequently conceptualised as effects. Observers have remarked that media users have been both creators and consumers of information and entertainment long before the advent of the Internet (Toffler and Alvin, 1980). According to the transactional media effects concepts, this indicates that the CMC technology not only gives users a fast and freely obtainable model for interpersonal interactions, but it also permits the development and issuing of content by a sender to have an effect not only on the receiver, but also on the sender. In other words, the CMC technology not only provides users with a rapid and easily accessible model for interpersonal transactions, but it also enables interpersonal transactions. The expression effect is the name given to the phenomena in which the acts that we take have an effect on ourselves (Pingree, 2007). Expression effects are a relatively new area of study in the realm of media impacts, and the processes remain poorly understood. The requirement for consistency, which leads to restricted media exposure, is a plausible reason for the preponderance of expression effects.

Due to the lack of study in this area, it is possible that the self-representation and self-concept of those involved in media communication might be affected by both intrapersonal (expression effects) and interpersonal (feedback) interactions (Van Der Heide et al., 2013). Furthermore, both transmitters and receivers possess behaviours which might impact the media consumption, attentiveness to the conveyed messages, and perception of such signals. (Walther et al., 2011).

Since this study examines advertising video ads on the advertising site YouTube, the CMC model serves as the fundamental communicative model. However, this model will not be investigated in depth as part of this investigation.

2.2.3 Classification of communication instruments

Within communication policy, numerous communication instruments that assist to transmit a marketing message to the intended audience can be defined.

Communication instruments describe the "[...] summary of different communication measures based on similar characteristics" (Meffert et al., 2018, p. 654). They can be divided into above-the-line measures and below-the-line measures (Meffert et al., 2018, p. 654). Above-the-line communication measures are those that allow for a broad, impersonal target group approach through mass media and are directly seen as advertising by consumers. This comprises traditional and new media advertising metrics, such as television, print, and social media advertising (Esch et al., 2016, p. 219). In contrast, below-the-line communication tactics try to contact the target audience personally through unique, unusual advertising techniques and are frequently not regarded as such by the target audience (Esch et al., 2016, p. 218f.). Below-the-line communication methods generally consist of more recent communication tools including sponsorship, public relations, and viral marketing (Esch et al., 2016, p. 219). Figure 8 depicts a summary and classification of communication measures within the marketing mix. This study pertains to Below-the-Line communication strategies, particularly social media activity. It focuses specifically on YouTube.

Figure 8 Types of communication within the Marketing-Mix based on Bruhn (2014)

In recent years, Paid-Owned-Earned-media categorization has grown increasingly prevalent (Gaiser and Theobald, 2017, p. 127). Paid media refers to any communication measures that a company records in exchange for payment with various advertising media, such as traditional advertising measures in television or print media, sponsoring activities, and online advertising (Stephen and Galak, 2012). Owned media, on the other hand, refers to any media activities that a firm produces on its own channels, such as press releases and contributions (Stephen and Galak, 2012). Both kinds, paid media and owned media, are within the company's authority (Stephen and Galak, 2012). The third type, Earned Media, refers to media activities that are not produced by the company itself but rather by third parties such as consumers or journalists (Stephen and Galak, 2012). Primarily, these comprise social media activities (e.g., postings in online communities/social media channels) and viral marketing (e.g., word-of-mouth referrals) (Stephen and Galak, 2012). Although marketing operations can help generate earned media, firms cannot directly influence or control earned media activities (Stephen and Galak, 2012). Companies should constantly strive to develop earned media through paid and/or owned media, because

earned media has the biggest impact on potential customers and can therefore have a long-lasting effect on their attitude towards a brand or a product, ultimately leading to a purchase decision. The Paid-Owned-Earned communication activities are illustrated in Figure 9. In accordance with the prior description of this research and the Paid-Owned-Earned paradigm, this research focuses on owned media, specifically social media activities, with an emphasis on YouTube.

Figure 9 Paid-Owned-Earned communication

2.2.4 Increasing importance of digital/new media

Since a change from product to communication rivalry has occurred over the past few years, communication policy and, by extension, advertising have played an increasingly vital part in the marketing mix (Homburg, 2020, p. 865). The increasing importance of communication policies is also reflected in the consistently rising gross advertising expenditures over the past few years. Figure 10 shows the development of gross investment in advertising in Germany from 1995 to 2021, with a significant increase from approximately EUR 13 billion in 1995 to roughly EUR 38 billion in 2021, i.e., annual gross investment more than doubled during this period. Consequently, advertising's influence on communication policies is expanding significantly.

Figure 10 Development of gross investment in advertising in Germany from 1995 to 2021 (in billions of euros) based on Nielsen (2022)

Comparing the advertising market shares of the various media in Germany (Figure 11), the relatively brief observation period from 2015 to 2020 reveals a clear redistribution of advertising market shares among the various media. In terms of advertising market share, traditional advertising channels such as newspapers and magazines, television, radio, cinema, and outdoor are stagnating or even declining. In contrast, there is a noticeable increase from approximately 30 percent to approximately 41 percent in digital advertising. Considering the concurrent rise in total advertising expenditures, this remarkable growth is even more remarkable.

Figure 11 Advertising market shares of the individual media in Germany from 2015 to 2020 based on DentsuAegisNetwork (2021)

This rapidly increasing significance of digital media causes a redistribution of the communication budget and a reevaluation of the importance of the various media in the communication mix (Gaiser and Theobald, 2017, p. 133). Despite the continued dominance of traditional forms of advertising (such as television and print ads), an increasing number of businesses are shifting their advertising budgets towards digital media. Digital advertising is required to reach today's always-connected, always-online potential customers across all channels. The younger the target audience, the more relevant digital advertising channels become.

In the past few years, social media has emerged as an important marketing communication tool within digital media (Felix et al., 2017). Consequently, and due to their high relevance to this research, social media will be examined as a significant factor in the subsequent chapter.

2.2.5 Communication with social media/new media

As was explained in Chapter 2.2.3, social media (activities, not advertisements) is a marketing communication tool and below-the-line media (see Figure 8). Kaplan and Haenlein (2010) define social media as „[...] a group of Internet-based applications that build on the ideological and technological foundations of Web 2.0 and allow the creation and exchange of user generated content. “

Web 2.0 describes a new Internet user behavior. The previous provider-to-consumer one-way communication on the Internet has vanished; users now generate their own

content and engage in direct dialogue with their environment and with businesses (Bender, 2011, p. 145).

Therefore, the integration of users into all Internet activities is a central characteristic. The emphasis has shifted from the content provided by companies and other institutions to the communication content created by users themselves. User Generated Content describes self-produced content (UGC). Internet-wide distribution of extremely heterogeneous user-generated content. They demonstrate some creative effort and are produced outside of a professional setting (Vickery and Wunsch-Vincent, 2007, p. 35).

Figure 12 Social media communication network model

Social media is a communication tool that enables instant and random multi-way exchanges, distinguishing it from traditional media in precisely these respects (Peters et al., 2013). In contrast to the latter, social media enables real-time communication, meaning that content can be provided and modified in real time, thereby facilitating a faster exchange of information. Social media also differ from traditional media in that any user can participate, whereas traditional media are exclusive to professional users (such as advertising or media agencies) (Kreutzer, 2021, p. 409). As shown in Figure 12, social media enables communication between companies and consumers

as well as between individual consumers (Mangold and Faulds, 2009). As a communication medium, they are significantly more consumer-driven and consumer-controlled than traditional media, where advertisers retain control (Hayes et al., 2016). Even if companies lack direct control over particular published content, they can attempt to influence consumer conversations (Mangold and Faulds, 2009).

Companies use social media for various purposes, including the distribution of digital advertising and promotions to interact with consumers in the context of customer service to further develop innovations and to authentically engage with customers (Smith et al., 2012). Here, businesses can pursue a variety of objectives, including increasing sales, enhancing brand image, and increasing consumer interaction with the product or brand. In addition to these proactive objectives, businesses can utilize social media for reactive purposes (Felix et al., 2017). They can, for instance, monitor social media posts and transactions and assess how consumers evaluate the brand or special actions (Schweidel and Moe, 2014). Additionally, consumers can utilize social media for their own purposes. Thus, they can communicate via social media channels and exchange opinions with other consumers on particular topics or provide product ratings (Jin and Phua, 2014). Social media enables an entirely new form of traditional word-of-mouth communication (further details in chapter 2.3), which is considerably simplified by social media platforms such as YouTube and Instagram. This can ultimately have an effect on the relationship between the company and the customer, as well as the company's brand image and the public's awareness of its product or brand (Jin and Phua, 2014).

Figure 13 illustrates the increasing global significance of social media based on the increasing number of users.

Figure 13 Number of active social media users worldwide from 2015 to 2021 (in billions) based on DataReportal (2021)

YouTube is discussed in greater detail in Chapter 2.3.3 as a social media platform pertinent to this research.

2.2.5.1 Entertainment on the Internet

Individual reception motives or modalities, such as immersion, escapism, relaxation, or parasocial interaction, occur with and without networking on the Internet in a manner very similar to that of traditional media (Bryant and Vorderer, 2013, McKenna et al., 2007). The primary distinction between offline and current forms of entertainment on the social web lies in the behavior and motivations of users. Users "receive" in traditional offline media and Web 1.0, but in the social web they also communicate, participate, and produce.

Figure 14 Entertainment on the Internet based on Schweiger and Beck (2019, p. 240)

The use of entertainment on the internet can be divided into three areas, as shown in Figure 14 (Schweiger and Beck, 2019, p. 240 f.):

- User activity: It is observed that users of the social web receive or generate a wide variety of offers. Users participate in communities and interact and communicate with one another. They produce their own content, such as posting their own videos on YouTube, customizing characters in computer games to their liking, exchanging ideas with others, and writing editorial contributions for blogs to entertain other users.
- Psychological processes: Therefore, active participation, such as the production of one's own content, is the medium for certain psychological processes. Among these are self-disclosure, self-efficacy, and self-expression. Users can only disclose information about themselves and reveal themselves if they produce their own content. Active participation in what occurs on the Internet fosters a sense of self-efficacy: users experience a sense of satisfaction, affinity, or enjoyment - all manifestations of entertainment - because they are able to make a difference and see that their contributions result in responses. In addition, they have the chance to work on their identity. Aspects of their self-concept can be manipulated, "polished up,"

and reimagined. The psychological processes described here are closely related to the satisfaction of the central intrinsic basic needs (Ryan and Deci, 2000) for the experience of competence (mediated, for example, by self-efficacy in an online game), autonomy (facilitated, for example, by perceived control in self-presentation in social media), and social connectedness (e.g. in the form of social support after self-disclosure in an online context). The fulfillment of these innate needs is a crucial element of the entertainment experience (Tamborini et al., 2010, Tamborini et al., 2011).

- Entertainment experience: In response to media consumption, entertainment experiences are remarkably consistent regardless of the medium. It can be quantified as behaviour (laughing), emotion (joy, sadness), or cognition, for example (affinity) (Vorderer et al., 2004).

The psychological processes are studied in greater detail below because they are of particular importance to this study. The scientific community is still divided about the precise definition of the concept of interactivity, which is a complicated construct (Liu, 2003, Liu and Shrum, 2002, Schweiger and Quiring, 2008). According to Liu and Shrum (2002), three dimensions of interactivity can be distinguished: (1) active control, (2) two-way communication, and (3) synchronicity. These fundamental aspects of interaction apply to the vast majority of Internet services. The value of interaction for the entertainment experience has been extensively examined within the video and computer gaming industries. The three aspects of interactivity defined by Liu and Shrum (2002) contribute significantly to the entertainment value of computer games.

The psychological concept of self-efficacy plays a significant role in the evolution of entertainment experiences in relation to media interactivity. It reflects the degree to which an individual feels able to meet the needs of a circumstance or display the required behaviour (Bandura, 1977).

Self-disclosure, i.e. the disclosure of one's own information to others (Cozby, 1973), is of utmost relevance for the entertainment experience on the Internet, as the exposure of private information is frequently a prerequisite for the use of many entertaining online offerings. According to studies, peoples in computer-mediated communication are often more willing to provide personal information than in direct face-to-face communication (Joinson, 2001, Tidwell and Walther, 2002). This increasing desire to disclose oneself is linked, in part, to a heightened sense of

anonymity and the improved perception of controllability in the Internet's communication environment (Joinson, 2001, Schouten et al., 2007).

Early research on self-presentation on the Internet may now be confirmed in the realm of social media, notably the need for individuals to promote themselves as likeable and competent (Barker, 2009, Raacke and Bonds-Raacke, 2008). Impression management generally refers to "impression control" (Schlenker, 1980). People attempt to manage and control their impact on others. The incentive to affect others' perceptions of one's image depends on the individual's goals, their valence, and the gap between their actual and ideal image (Leary, 1993, Leary and Kowalski, 1990). Goals may include material or societal objectives, as well as personal improvement, higher self-esteem, or even personal development. Self-presentation is a crucial aspect of managing one's identity.

Numerous research demonstrate that online self-expression is, in fact, a significant source of self-affirmation (Toma, 2016). Empirical findings on self-presentation in the social web reveal that the majority of self-presentation on Facebook and other sites is pretty genuine and not primarily based on self-idealisation (Back et al., 2010, Reinecke and Trepte, 2014).

2.2.5.2 Two-process theories of entertainment experience

Two-process theories (Vorderer and Hartmann, 2009, Vorderer and Reinecke, 2015) seek to incorporate the variety of entertainment variables in the online context. These compare the traditional definition of media entertainment as a positive affective state (Vorderer et al., 2004) with a second entertainment component. Two-process models that take the hedonic entertainment experience as the first process and the concept of intrinsic need satisfaction as the second process are applicable to the context of "Entertainment 2.0" (Tamborini et al., 2011). The Self-Determination Theory (Ryan and Deci, 2000) provides the theoretical foundation for these techniques. This theory recognises three intrinsic requirements as motivators of human behaviour: the need for competence, autonomy, and social connectedness. A growing number of empirical studies indicate that the use of interactive media is a potent source of satisfaction of these inherent wants, and that this need fulfilment is the primary driver of the entertainment experience (Reinecke et al., 2012, Sheldon et al., 2011). From the various communication models, particularly those involving the Internet and social media, it can be deduced that well-placed, recipient-specific advertising can initiate

interpersonal processes that result in people sharing advertising spots. This is because human behaviour is motivated by demonstrating skill, autonomy, and social ties.

2.3 Content Marketing

Content marketing has become one of the most popular marketing buzzwords. In addition, its prevalence is growing (Cespedes and Heddleston, 2018). Despite the fact that it has existed since the beginning of marketing, it was not previously viewed as a distinct field of marketing. It was predominantly interwoven into the advertisement. Around the end of the 1990s, the phrase "content marketing" was coined. Nonetheless, it was not resolved until 2008. It continues to evolve today (Cespedes and Heddleston, 2018). Social media proliferation has contributed to the emergence of content marketing. This coincides with an exponential rise in client affinity for social media. Customers no longer desired to be irritated by obtrusive advertising, especially in their privacy and thus not on social media (Dembosky and Bradshaw, 2011). The entry of advertising into social media was facilitated by relevant and engaging content. And the development of social media continues to expand (We Are Social, 2020).

"Content" is a market with demand (people's need for knowledge) and supply (providers' market offerings). This results in competition. Therefore, a demand must be satisfied - if possible, better than the competition. Therefore, marketers should also employ the "4 P" from traditional marketing, which were created for this situation. These factors include the product, distribution strategy (location), advertising (promotion), and price. The distinction between "content" and "advertising" is essential to comprehending the concept. Both "content marketing" and "advertising" address a demand or a need (the desire for information in relation to attention or for a product in relation to purchasing power, respectively) (the feeling of a lack or problem in connection with the desire to find a solution). The difference between "advertising" and "content marketing" is that "advertising" only promises to meet the needs, whereas "content marketing" actually meets the needs by delivering content with benefits and added value (such as a blog post with helpful tips or a video tutorial) to solve the problem.

2.3.1 Definition

Since content marketing is a relatively new issue in the field of marketing, there is no consensus on a single definition, but there are a variety of definitions. The only distinction is in the phrase. There is widespread consensus on the concept's meaning. Instead of advertising a product, content marketing is the dissemination of knowledge that is useful, problem-solving, entertaining, or otherwise beneficial to the consumer (Phillips, 2017, Content Marketing Institute, 2017).

Traditional marketing methods direct consumers' attention directly to the goods, whereas content marketing emphasises the publication of brand-relevant material. The contrast between content marketing and traditional marketing exemplifies content marketing. For instance, advertisements employ the so-called push tactic. Advertising messages are disseminated through gatekeepers such as magazines, the emphasis is on the goods, and the potential buyer is clearly persuaded to purchase. In contrast, content marketing employs the so-called pull strategy. The customer must approach the product. This occurs because the customer perceives an independent value addition in the marketing measures. He desires information, considers himself well-advised, and is interested in the provider's services. Traditional advertising focuses on the product and spreads messages (push strategy). With content marketing, the emphasis is on the customer, who should be drawn to the brand or product's themes (pull strategy).

"Content marketing" refers to marketing strategies that deliver content to the consumer via several channels while always keeping the target audience in mind. Instead of focusing solely on sales, content marketing seeks to give value to content. With the help of this emphasis, the user's attention will be drawn to the many touchpoints and purchase phases, and long-term communication with the target audience will be stimulated and maintained. The primary objective of content marketing is therefore to address a relevant audience with material that informs, entertains, and ultimately persuades.

There are numerous definitions of "content marketing" in the literature, each of which emphasises a subset of this marketing strategy. Joe Pulizzi, who notably shaped the phrase "content marketing," defines this marketing strategy as follows: "Content marketing is the marketing and business process for creating and distributing content to attract, acquire and engage a clearly defined and understood target audience - with

the objective of driving profitable customer action (Pulizzi, 2013, p. 9). According to Pulizzi, content marketing can be utilised for a variety of corporate objectives, including brand exposure, lead generation, and customer loyalty, but its ultimate goal is to influence the target audience's behaviour. "Good content marketing makes a person stop, read, think, and behave differently" (Pulizzi, 2013, p. 10).

Scott Gattis believes that content marketing is characterised by a tangible benefit to the targeted audience. "Rather than interrupting your audiences to pitch your product or service, content marketing focuses on delivering information that helps your audiences – helps them understand issues, helps simplify complex constructs or otherwise adds value by providing useful and relevant information. If traditional marketing is about selling, content marketing is about helping "(Gattis, 2014, p. 52).

Amanda Maksymiw emphasises the significance of content marketing for acquiring and retaining customers: "Content Marketing is the process of developing and sharing relevant, valuable, and engaging content to target audience with the goal of acquiring new customers or increasing business from existing customers." (Pulizzi, 2012).

Robert Rose highlights that content marketing serves to demonstrate a company's ability, quality, and experience, whereas advertising and traditional marketing just assert this: "Traditional marketing and advertising is telling the world you're a rock star. Content Marketing is showing the world that you are one." (Pulizzi, 2012).

Franca Borst underlines the process-oriented, long-term nature of content marketing: "Content marketing is a long-term, strategically sound communication discipline that encompasses the creation and regular, cross-media distribution of useful content for specific target groups, whereby the company or brand appears as a consultant, expert or entertainer in the digital world, creates trust and loyalty and ultimately supports the consumer in all phases of his purchasing decision process." (Borst, 2017, p. 396).

Claudia Hilker refers to the methodical approach of marketing and public relations in content marketing: "Recipients who are interested in a company and its products should be convinced with content in such a way that they eventually become customers. Thus the marketing communication methodically approaches PR, whose journalistically characterized beginning is based on topics." (Hilker, 2017, p. 2).

Michael Brenner emphasizes the effective interaction of different content channels and content types, which must be visible to the target audience at the moment of need: "Content Marketing is about delivering the content your audience is seeking in

all the places they are searching for it. It is the effective combination of created, curated and syndicated content.“ (Pulizzi, 2012).

There is a basic element shared by all definitions. This principle may be reduced to the concept that content marketing should constantly attempt to provide customers with more value. This additional value can take several forms, such as the material answering a specific client query or entertaining the consumer. Thus, a clear contrast can be seen between content marketing and traditional marketing, which seeks to capture attention through "interruptions" rather than the consumer value it provides. Traditional marketing attempts to promote a product or service by emphasising it. Content marketing, on the other hand, places the client at the centre and does not seek to sell directly; even if this is the overarching objective of the company, this objective is attractively wrapped and not aggressively targeted inside the content.

2.3.2 Importance of Content Marketing

2.3.2.1 *Extreme sensory overload*

In the 1990s, the average consumer encountered approximately one million marketing messages in his first two decades of existence. Today, this number exceeds 20 million (Ehrlich and Hildebrand, 2016). While click rates for internet banner advertising were still at 2 percent in 1995, the figure for picture ads was only between 0.1 and 0.2 percent in 2007 (Quesenberry, 2016, p. 40) , and other studies estimate that up to 50 percent of clicks on mobile banner ads are unintentional (Morrissey, 2013).

Due to the abundance of marketing communications, clients have "largely immunized" (Hilker, 2017, p. 30) themselves against traditional marketing - e.g. through "banner blindness": Eye-tracking research has revealed that consumers typically overlook advertising today (Quesenberry, 2016, p. 41).

In addition, the usage of ad blockers is on the rise, which poses a dilemma for advertisers, particularly on mobile devices (Tynan, 2016). If consumers believe advertising to be obnoxious, this can be harmful for advertising companies. In a 2009 questionnaire, nearly 80 percent of respondents indicated that pop-up and layer advertisements on the Internet irritate them very or excessively.

In light of this trend, traditional marketing, which relies on purchased reach and interruption, is not only becoming less effective but also more expensive. Keith

Quesenberry, for instance, states: "For advertisers, the cost of newspaper advertising per unit of circulation increased ten times from the 1960s to 2000s (...) Research (...) found that advertising had become significantly less efficient in the past three decades." (Quesenberry, 2016, p. 42). As early as 2001, Seth Godin pointed out that "interruption marketing fails because it cannot attract enough attention from consumers" (Godin and Gladwell, 2001, p. 49), while Judy Ungar Franks concludes: "(...) there is now excessive and perhaps unsustainable cost inflation in paid media. The costs to reach customers in and across most paid media sectors are skyrocketing." (Franks, 2016, p. 317).

Instead of distributing homogeneous marketing messages, Content Marketing focuses on exposure at the moment of need, thereby overcoming these shortcomings of conventional marketing. This marketing strategy also gives the consumer greater control over the flow of information, as the (possible) customer can cease communication at any time if he is no longer interested in the material. Content marketing is a paradigm change from push to pull marketing because it addresses the growing sensory overload with a generally more cautious type of communication that emphasises interaction, long-term relationship building, and the correct content at the right time (Hilker, 2017, p. 4-5, Borst, 2017, p. 394).

2.3.2.2 Technological developments

Recent technical advancements have contributed to the rise of content marketing. In recent years, technological barriers to content generation and delivery have been dramatically reduced (e.g. the production of videos). Global content distribution is easily implemented via the Internet, and the platforms for content distribution have "exploded" in recent years. (Solomon, 2013, p. 8). On top of this, several new solutions and tools (such as data analysis, content optimization, and inbound marketing software) and new online technologies now enable even smaller businesses to employ content marketing effectively and efficiently.

Mobile Internet usage is another trend that has profoundly influenced the evolution of content marketing. Stephan Heinrich emphasises that the "Always on" effect of smartphones has played a significant role in this development: "Uninterrupted access to the Internet, regardless of where you are, is a decisive factor for the boom in content marketing." (Heinrich, 2016, p. 49).

In addition, significant modifications to search engine algorithms have also facilitated the rise of content marketing. For some time, Google has ensured that only websites with high-quality, relevant information and a positive user experience rank well. In this context, "social signals" (i.e., user interactions such as comments, shares, and likes) are gaining importance for search engine results since they are used to infer content relevancy. The rise of content marketing is thus driven in no small part by Search Engine Optimization (SEO).

2.3.2.3 Loss of importance for traditional media

Traditional media houses (newspapers, magazines, radio and television stations) have lost their monopoly on opinion due to the democratisation of content production and delivery brought about by the elimination of technological obstacles. In recent years, the classical media have experienced a considerable reduction in their reach, in part because to the rising fragmentation of interests, which has made it more difficult for them to reach a bigger audience: "With an increase in options, audiences are now scattering across various destinations to suit their individual content tastes. The result is that fewer media vehicles can deliver an audience en masse. (...) more audiences shift into the long tail of the media." (Franks, 2016, p. 318)

Due to this, modern marketers can no longer rely only on traditional media to reach their target audiences, and are instead relying more and more on their own content (Owned Media) and mentions by third parties (Earned Media) (Franks, 2016, p. 317). Today, the communication channel "press work," whose primary objective is to raise brand and company awareness, competes with a variety of other approaches and channels used in content marketing, such as influencer marketing, blogs, and social media. In spite of the continued significance of traditional press work in extending the reach of a company's messages, there are now a range of different ways to reach target audiences. In contrast to traditional public relations, content marketing may also support the full customer journey, from problem awareness through sale closure, with relevant material.

This development exacerbates the crisis of many traditional media firms (often as a result of a lack of a digital strategy) and has repercussions for content: According to a Pew Research Center study, the available funds for journalism in the United States decreased by a third between 2006 and 2014 (Franks, 2016, p. 340). The consequent loss of research time and high-quality content is rapidly being compensated for by

other companies, which are progressively becoming media houses and filling information gaps with their own content offerings (Pulizzi and Barrett, 2009).

2.3.2.4 Changed consumer behaviour

Traditional marketing is likewise becoming less effective as consumers become more demanding, more informed, more critical, more independent, more confident in their ability to access information, and simultaneously less loyal. They have stronger market power than a few years ago since they are better able to evaluate the veracity of information (Borst, 2017, p. 393, Kee and Yazdanifard, 2015, p. 1056).

This enhances the quality criteria for a company's released content: "Customers will not be satisfied with exaggeration or marketing gimmicks. Appropriate, valuable and rich content is needed to trigger purchasing behaviour and influence buying habits." (Kee and Yazdanifard 2015, p. 1061)

The fact that consumers are increasingly demanding ethical action and social responsibility from businesses reflects a more critical and enlightened perspective (Hilker, 2017, p. 39). To avoid jeopardising a company's reputation, it must provide information that is legitimate and genuine.

Due to the proliferation of social networks, the opinions of other users are becoming increasingly significant for customers' purchasing decisions, as customer reviews and testimonials enjoy greater credibility in comparison to corporate communications (Quesenberry, 2016, p. 48). To contribute positively to customer conversations, businesses must provide useful content: "Brands must consistently produce content that is share worthy, creating value for their consumers and their online networks to build strong consumer-brand relationships. (...) In the social Web environment, the currency of exchange is content." (Hayes, 2016, p. 69)

2.3.2.5 Changed purchasing processes

Customers' altered purchase behaviour is another factor in the expansion of content marketing. As a result of digitalization, the purchasing process in both the B2B and B2C markets has fundamentally shifted. Since digital channels, particularly for information acquisition, have become exponentially more significant, it is becoming increasingly vital for businesses to be visible at the moment of need and, consequently, at an early stage of the purchasing decision process. Google refers to this as ZMoT, or the "Zero Moment of Truth," which occurs when a user looks for

answers to specific inquiries. "A brand that answers these questions at just the right time scores a double win: It helps improve a consumer's life and stands to gain a competitive advantage over brands that don't." (Lecinski, 2014) Therefore, ZMoT is concerned with providing consumers with content that is suited to their specific questions and present location in the purchasing decision process. On the other side, merely referencing one's own product information and pricing sheets on the Internet is proving increasingly unhelpful, particularly as the information phase on the Internet grows longer for more complex products. "In 2010 the average consumer engaged with about 5 pieces of content before making a buying decision. In 2011, that number doubled to more than 10" (Lecinski, 2014).

Even if the actual purchase is performed in the store or branch, this is frequently preceded by extensive online research ("ROPO effect" - Research Online, Purchase Offline) and the customer has frequently already made his purchase decision prior to speaking with the salesperson or consultant. For instance, Melanie Tamblé notes on the altered B2B purchase selection processes: "95 % of business customers research the Internet when they are looking for specialist information and potential business partners. 57% of the purchasing process in B2B business has already been completed by the time decision-makers contact a sales representative for the first time". (Tamblé, 2016). To be in the customer's "Relevant Set" prior to the purchase decision, it is becoming increasingly crucial for businesses to be present with relevant content offerings during the earliest stages of information search and decision-making. Tamblé (Tamblé, 2016) states: "65 % of B2B customers confirm that the content of companies has a significant influence on the purchase decision".

2.3.2.6 Growing importance of long-term relationship building

The ineffectiveness of monolithic marketing communication with its undifferentiated messaging has prompted marketing researchers to believe that the primary objective of modern marketing is to establish stable, long-term client connections: "A shift is now occurring from emphasizing product to emphasizing engagement and building relationships between brand and consumer." (Quesenberry, 2016, p. 52)

The prevalence of social media has increased the significance of establishing long-term connections with consumers and stakeholders, who may now influence public opinion about a company more effectively than ever before. Ungar Franks emphasises that businesses must customise their communications to the demands

of clients and the stage of the customer relationship: "It is essential to tailor messages to the specific wants and needs of customer segments at each stage of their relationship with the brand – from awareness, to consideration, to purchase, to use, and ultimately to postpurchase satisfaction and brand loyalty. Gone are the days when brands could push out monologues of product features and benefits and expect their customers' undivided attention to the message." (Franks, 2016, p. 326)

Relationship-focused marketing communication offers numerous benefits to businesses, including decreased long-term marketing expenses, faster acquisition of new customers, greater direct access to existing customers, and increased customer loyalty (Hayes, 2016, p. 68). Since content marketing is long-term, process-oriented, and attempts to deliver high-quality content that meets the demands of the target audience, it is ideally suited for establishing and sustaining customer connections.

2.3.3 YouTube Content Marketing

YouTube, as one of the most significant communication vehicles of video-sharing platforms, is a part of the social media communication tool. YouTube was launched in 2005 as a "content community" that allows users to publish, view, comment on, and share a variety of content (Dehghani et al., 2016).

After Google, YouTube is the second largest content search engine in the world. The video portal has 30 million daily visitors. Eighty percent of 18-to-49-year-olds include the site into their media consumption. There are explanations: YouTube has no broadcast deadlines or defined broadcast times, and it provides an infinite amount of content. YouTube, like other social networks, can be viewed as a small-world network, according to Bampo et al. (2008). These networks are characterised by strong ties that result in quick spread and hence enable viral marketing.

Figure 15 Ranking of the largest social networks and messengers by number of users in January 2021 (in millions) based on WeAreSocial et al. (2021)

YouTube covers around 50 percent of the world's Internet users, or roughly 2.3 billion people (see Figure 15). And this number continues to rise. There are already 2.6 billion people in 2021 on YouTube. This is a tremendous opportunity for all marketing professionals and managers. With a revolutionary concept, it is possible to find a buyer for virtually every good offered on the site. The problem is to package the content in a unique and "spectator-friendly" manner and to be familiar with a few key functionalities and rules of the platform in order to draw attention and get discovered in the platform's vast video pool. Figure 16 demonstrates clearly the growing importance of YouTube as an advertising platform. This exemplifies the huge development of advertising revenues on YouTube and, consequently, the increase in advertising expenditures by businesses on YouTube.

Figure 16 YouTube advertising revenue from 2017 to 2020 (in billions of US dollars) based on Alphabet (2021)

YouTube has additional benefits for marketers. Commercials on YouTube have tremendous potential for achieving high visibility through video sharing and maybe also strong virality (see chapter 2.4 on Viral Marketing). As the video reaches new audiences via social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, and LinkedIn, commercial sharing can garner greater attention than traditional advertisements. Moreover, YouTube advertisements are very cost-effective. Aside from the expense of generating and possibly promoting the video, YouTube advertising is free; money is only received after visitors watch the entire commercial. Furthermore, YouTube advertising is limitless. Advertisers can post as many videos as they'd like for a nominal fee. Additionally, there is virtually no length limit for YouTube advertisements. A lengthy advertisement can convey a tale or depict a drama that can evoke powerful emotions. Unlike other advertising strategies, viewers watch the advertisements voluntarily. The advertisement is only viewed if a viewer chooses to view it. Ultimately, YouTube adds a significant new dimension to television advertising. Marketers can put advertisements on YouTube as a pre-release test before placing them on paid television networks. Alternately, marketers can utilise sponsored television channels to influence the sharing of spots.

On YouTube, two categories of material are distinguished: content developed and released by companies and content created and published freely by companies. The first form enables corporations to make information about themselves, their brands, and their products available online, as well as to display television commercials online, so extending their advertising campaigns online. The second type of material is user-

generated content. This allows consumers to express their enthusiasm or disdain for the company's products or brands, which can have a favourable or bad effect on the company's or brand's image (Kreutzer, 2021, p. 410f). Only the first type of material is important for this study, i.e., content created by the companies themselves.

Brands also use the platform successfully

Additionally, brands access millions of people. Providing the content is accurate. Lego is an example of this. The Danish channel is flooded with video. Some of the clips are barely 11 seconds long, and they are uploaded daily. Occasionally, these short film sequences featuring Lego figures are uploaded multiple times in various languages. A successful strategy: 2,4 million subscribers and around 100 million views in January 2017.

YouTube distinguishes between two primary content categories. The content for "Lean-Back" and "Lean-Forward." The words are formed from the alleged attitude of the spectator during viewing. "Lean-Back" is about entertaining content in which the viewer leans back and is amused. On the other hand, "Lean-Forward" refers to content where information is consciously retrieved. Examples of such content are HowTo formats, Do-It-Yourself projects, and tutorials. Traditional problem-solving material (Modenbach and Neumüller, 2020).

What characteristics must the content and marketing of a YouTube channel possess to generate multiple clicks? In both circumstances, the content must provide the audience with something essential: added value.

Clearly, entertainment is an additional value. Pranks and comedy formats satisfy the customers' desire for amusement. Like similar formats do on television. However, the video of the beauty blogger allegedly advising the 14-year-old on how to invest her pocket money adds further value to this target audience. For the automotive enthusiast who utilises YouTube to get tuning recommendations and vehicle reviews and then invests several thousand euros, this test represents a significant added value. The video platform provides access to the largest variety of customer groups. If the target audience is familiar with their difficulties, the advertised product can be appropriately staged on YouTube.

YouTube should be viewed primarily as a communication tool for expanding reach, which is subsequently utilised to accomplish diverse objectives.

HYGIENE CONTENT

According to Google (2015), "hygiene content" consists of movies that fulfil a constant demand. They address themes that are relevant 365 days a year, have no seasonal relevance, and enhance the users' daily lives. These videos constitute the foundation of a channel and help to attract initial attention; they are the channel's fundamental noise. Typically, hygiene content is a video that provides answers to search questions. The format for hygiene materials is one that can be used daily. Here, the upload frequency, or the number of movies uploaded, takes precedence. The videos are quickly made both technically and in terms of content. Examples of viable formats include vlogs, tutorials, and product videos. The production can be conducted in-house with minimal effort. These videos are created with YouTube's algorithm, which promotes frequent uploads, in mind. Moreover, the greater the number of video units, the greater the number of possible interactions (comments, likes, and subscriptions). When there is more material on a site, more search results are generated for relevant searches.

HUB CONTENT

With the hygiene material, the channel's foundation was established. It provides visitors with many access points to your channel via YouTube search. Now, the user must be provided with a reason to subscribe to the channel and frequently visit it. The Hub content (Google, 2015) assists in this endeavour. These are periodic and episodic formats with a predetermined "send time." Weekly publications are the most effective. The content must be created in a distinct manner. In addition, the audience should be informed of the following episode's release date at the conclusion of each video, so that they know when to return to the channel.

HERO CONTENT

The Hero content should be the "highlight" of the content strategy (Google, 2015). This type of content should help to enhance subscriber numbers and brand recognition. As the name suggests, this is event-specific special material. Channel traffic can be increased through collaboration with YouTube personalities, a (viral) video, or an elaborate production. A bigger budget and external professional production are recommended for these videos. The greater the video's entertainment value, the greater the likelihood that it will be shared.

The Edeka food chain is an excellent illustration of hero content. The TV advertisements are also becoming a YouTube sensation in Germany.

Example Edeka:

With its effective television commercials, Edeka receives a great deal of attention on YouTube for its own channel. And turns the traffic they generate into new subscribers using intelligent hub content formats.

In February of 2014, the grocery store's "Super Geil" TV ad campaign was a true hero, and it also performed exceptionally well on YouTube. The success of the campaign is readily apparent in the rise in the number of subscribers. The number of members increased from 1,000 to approximately 15,000 by April 2014, and at the end of November, Edeka's first television Christmas advertisement went live on YouTube. The "Kassensymphonie" increased the number of subscribers by an additional 10,000 in a relatively short period of time. However, even in the instance of Edeka, not every ambitious advertising strategy is successful on YouTube. This is seen in the "Dorfdrift" advertisement from early November 2015, which had a little effect on increasing views and subscribers. Unquestionably a solid commercial, but lacking the "wow factor" and emotional power of the preceding actions. Consequently, YouTube's subscriber increase failed to materialise. The 2015 Christmas advertisement "#coming home" led to unprecedented growth for Edeka.

During the Christmas season, the number of subscribers increased from 38,000 to 68,000. The entire nation debated, "Is this permissible as Christmas advertising?" The cause: In the video, a grandfather fakes his own death during the holiday season in order to reunite his family. An emotionally engaging narrative. The title and description of the commercial are now available in other languages. Thus, even foreign search queries can be satisfied with a single movie. In 2016, the corporation was unable to replicate the popularity of their previous Christmas advertisement. With "#Zeitschenken," it was more on the emotional level of the Federal President's Christmas message. There are no friction points in the neighbourhood, and excellent entertainment is provided. This advertisement likewise failed to increase the channel's subscriber base.

Hero-Content is a fantastic method for increasing the channel's visibility. Only by adding and consistently utilising the channel with good hub and hygiene material is it feasible to develop a long-term relationship between "event attendees" and the

channel. At the same time, they generate these subscribers' dedication to the hub and cleanliness content. For visitors, comments and likes are a significant aspect of the content's quality. The Edeka example demonstrates how cleanliness, hub, and hero content may be strategically employed. Due to the high degree of attention, Hero-Content attracts new viewers to the channel and thus enhances the overall reach. The content of the hub then fulfils the users' interests on a regular basis. Hygiene content also generates a fundamental supply of content that directs viewers to the channel via search.

Especially for hero content, Edeka prioritises advertising that conveys a story. The success seems to validate Edeka's position. This type of advertisement appears to be extremely popular among viewers. This is why this study project is being conducted. The purpose of this research is to determine how this hero material may be produced effectively through storytelling.

2.3.4 Storytelling

As demonstrated in the previous chapter, Hero Content consists primarily of narrative elements. One reason to examine storytelling in greater depth in this chapter. Throughout human history, storytelling has been utilised as a potent form of communication (Ochs et al., 1992). The objective is to target consumers with narratives. Consumers should perceive items to be enticing and dynamic. An emotional connection to the brand strengthens the relationship. Thus, well-structured stories can circumvent the challenges of "regular" marketing and inspire customers on a personal level, resulting in the formation of a brand identity (Woodside, 2010). People recall stories more than conventional advertising (Kaare, 2012). Therefore, marketers utilise many forms of stories to connect with consumers. Ideally through digital means. It is essential to highlight that exponential development is particularly evident on digital platforms. Approximately 59% of the world's population has access to the Internet, and this proportion is rapidly increasing (Internet World Stats, 2020).

Storytelling Advertising aims to employ narrative components (Escalas, 2004, p. 171). Therefore, it is also called narrative advertising (more details in chapter 2.6 and following). The goal is for the reader to identify with the characters and feel the same things as they do. Consumer perception of the advertising personality should evolve (Boller and Olson, 1991). A brand can generate awareness, understanding, empathy and memory among consumers through storytelling (Singh and Sonnenburg, 2012p).

189). When the brand aids the protagonist in attaining his or her objective, the customer develops a positive association with the brand (Woodside et al., 2008). Inevitably, the issue arises as to why storytelling in general is a suitable marketing tactic since it has been shown to be beneficial with consumers. Studies have demonstrated that narrative marketing is preferable to traditional argumentative marketing because consumers tend to think in narratives rather than argumentative sequences (Woodside et al., 2008). This occurs primarily in the attribution of events (Escalas, 2004). People store all of their knowledge in historical settings. These stories are retrievable when it comes to interactions between individuals, as well as between individuals and brands. It is the same with experiences and assessments (Woodside, 2010). Thus, it can be stated: Storytelling taps into "a broad spectrum of consumers' unconscious brand knowledge from episodic and implicit/procedural memory" (Koll et al., 2010, p. 589).

Narrative advertising can direct the thoughts of customers (Escalas, 2004, p. 171). The reverse is also true of contentious advertising (e.g, factual advertisements). Here, a counterargumentative cognitive process is initiated (Wentzel et al., 2010). Through a story, the consumer is able to focus on story aspects and devote himself to the story without being distracted by marketing elements or considering them (Escalas, 2004, p. 171).

Audiences relate a narrative to their own experiences and recollections (Woodside, 2010). The greater the number of these recollections and points of contact with one's own life, the more memorable the narrative, in comparison to an argumentative marketing exercise. Thus, stories establish a strong bond between the listener and the narrative. This is also consistent with contemporary academic research (Woodside et al., 2008). The more effectively a commercial tells the story, the stronger the connection between brand and consumer. This process is described in the Self-Brand Connection narrative (Escalas, 2004). This refers to the activation of a so-called "matching process," or the comparison of own experiences to those of the advertisement (Escalas, 2004). This technique specifically strengthens the Self-Brand Connection, resulting in a favourable consumer response. Academic research has proven the validity of this idea, demonstrating that storyboard advertisements increase brand favorability and buy intent. (Escalas, 2004).

Marketing study investigates how stories captivate listeners and persuade them to alter their behaviour (Harmeling et al., 2017). Using the extended transport-imagery

model, it is shown that a story involves customers through narrative transport, defined as "the extent to which a consumer empathizes with the characters in the story and the story's plot activates his or her imagination, causing the consumer to experience the imagined reality while perceiving the story" (Van Laer et al., 2014, p. 799-800). Narrative persuasion is the change that achieves this type of customer connection. The persuasiveness of storytelling is substantially more than the more established and traditional attempts at customer interaction made by conventional advertising. The consequent entrainment of individuals through narratives has a mental effect on individuals and decreases the production of counterarguments (Green and Brock, 2002) by bringing them into the narrative and thereby causing emotional reactions. The narrative transport effect manifests in the emotive and cognitive responses, beliefs, attitudes, and aspirations of the tale's recipients when they are carried along by a narrative and transported into a narrative world that alters their sense of reality (Gerrig, 1993, Green and Brock, 2002). In addition, the narrative transport effect has the potential to endure for an extended period of time and possibly intensify (Appel and Richter, 2007), making the return on investment extremely efficient in terms of these advertising investments. This has ignited the marketing industry's interest in various sorts of narrative content and skyrocketed spending on it. But while billions of dollars are invested in digital stories, "few brands have generated significant consumer interest online" (Holt, 2016, p. 42). Insufficient understanding of how advertising campaigns function in the digital era (Lambert, 2013) and the enhanced creativity of consumers to produce their own stories (Arvidsson and Caliandro, 2016, Hughes et al., 2016, Luedicke et al., 2010) inhibit the persuasive power of brand advertising stories, which eventually results in decreased corporate revenue. Therefore, this thesis is considerably more persuasive and engaging for advertising firms.

More detailed elaborations on the topic of narrative persuasion can be found in the chapter 2.6.

Scientists have not yet offered definitive research for video content storytelling. In particular, YouTube material. In addition, there is no research on whether aspects of video storytelling content, as contrasted to standard video content, lead to a good attitude and, in the best case scenario, a positive attitude shift.

2.4 Viral Marketing and Word-of-Mouth

The consumer becomes an information selector who favours easily digestible visual information. The need for individualised communication and "non-advertising" is increasing as a result of the saturation of daily media (Kelly et al., 2010). Currently, it is tough to reach young customers via traditional media. They view advertising tactics as alluring tricks and attempt to decipher the programmes.

The term viral marketing was first referred to by Rayport (1996). A year later, Jurvetson and Draper defined the phrase "viral marketing" as "network-supported word of mouth." Hotmail is regarded as a pioneer of viral marketing due to its use of email as a mass distribution medium (Jurvetson, 2000).

In the internet version of word-of-mouth (online or electronic Word-of-Mouth, eWOM), users share their product or service experiences with other users. These guidelines have a substantial relevance and high credibility, as demonstrated by empirical investigations (see Senecal and Nantel, 2004). Their unique significance stems from the greater trustworthiness of interpersonal communication compared to mass media, and rises when the recommenders are subject-matter experts (influencer marketing). Unique to eWOM is the fact that it is nearly independent of advertising companies. Xia and Bechwati (2008) demonstrated that advertising impacts are produced when the products or services discussed are judged to be valuable and when users may make personal references ("cognitive personalisation"). Similarly, other research highlight user trust in such recommendations and the relationship with online opinion leaders as key factors.

2.4.1 Definition of Viral Marketing

The definitions and understanding of viral marketing have evolved over the past two centuries. The definitions and forms of the phrase viral marketing in the literature are notably influenced by a biological virus or epidemic comparison (Kiss and Bichler, 2008, Dobele et al., 2005). Helm (2000) defines viral marketing as a "communication and distribution concept" relying on the distribution of digital content between customers who transmit this content "in their social environment" via email. With regard to viral marketing, Wilson (2000) commented that it "describes any strategy that encourages users" to spread content in order to generate "the potential for exponential growth", such as a virus. Welker (2002) cites upsides like the incredibly

rapid and inexpensive dissemination of content. The cited disadvantage is the method's unpredictability, which is a significant danger when it comes to negative evaluation. A distinction is made by Dobele et al. (2005) regarding a functional perspective and a marketing viewpoint. In a functional view, Viral Marketing is a strategy "in which people forward the message to others on their email lists or include advertisements in or at the end of messages". From a marketing viewpoint, on the other hand, it is more of an "encouragement process" that aims to persuade people to "forward beneficial or persuasive marketing information they receive", either "intentionally or accidentally". Porter and Golan (2006) define "viral advertising" as "unpaid peer-to-peer communication of provocative content" because recipients should be motivated to share this advertising via the internet, e.g. via social media. Two relevant aspects play a decisive role in the spread of content. Kaplan and Haenlein (2011) state that the dissemination rate must be above one and that a social media application should be used for distribution. These two aspects can lead to exponential growth. The risk of losing control in viral marketing was mentioned by Cruz and Fill (2008), who mentioned the tight relationship with classic Word of Mouth (WoM). The relation of viral marketing to WoM is frequently mentioned in the literature (Berger and Milkman, 2012a, Kaplan and Haenlein, 2011, Dobele et al., 2005). For this reason, viral marketing it is also termed "electronic Word of Mouth" (eWOM) (Chu and Kim, 2011, Hennig-Thurau et al., 2004).

Reichstein and Bruschi (2019) have proposed a new and thus the most up-to-date definition of viral marketing, taking into consideration the most recent scientific advancements, as follows: "Viral marketing is defined as marketing strategies that permit exponential distribution of content in network-based channels in the shortest time with comparatively little effort and additionally generate measurable added value through the content, which leads to a high cost-benefit effect."

2.4.2 Difference between Viral Marketing and Word-of-Mouth

There is scientific evidence to imply that Word-of-Mouth (WoM) and viral marketing are distinct. Traditional WoM has a greater impact on actual buy intent than viral marketing (Baker et al., 2016). The primary advantage of viral marketing over traditional word-of-mouth is the ability for an advertisement to spread exponentially, resulting in rapid brand or product recognition (Baker et al., 2016). In addition, viral marketing metrics are more easily measurable than Word of Mouth metrics (Kaplan

and Haenlein, 2011). Some study indicates a chain reaction between viral marketing and Word of Mouth. For example, according to Ferguson (2008), WoM is said to be the consequence of viral marketing.

The decision over selecting content to share is heavily influenced by the audience being addressed. If the content is focused on one or a few individuals, it is typically useful. Once the content has been shared with multiple individuals, the one sharing it will typically wish to market himself. The study by Barasch and Berger (2014) points out these differences. Due to information asymmetries, engaging content is also mostly shared in writing (through viral marketing). In direct oral communication, there is typically limited time to consider the message. In written communication, however, there is considerable time for evaluation of the message (Berger and Iyengar, 2013). Essentially, the manner in which content is shared differs greatly between viral marketing and Word of Mouth. The content is directly tied to the profile in viral marketing. Self-promotion plays a crucial role here. WoM, on the other hand, predominantly occurs within the private sphere. For these reasons, the partial behaviour is essentially different.

2.4.3 Influencing Factors

2.4.3.1 *General conditions for viral marketing*

People utilise broad frameworks to filter and classify the massive quantities of information and content available on the internet. The response of other individuals to a certain piece of content also significantly influences the selection of content to be consumed beforehand.

High dependence exists between purchase intent and the credibility of the content source or presenter (Gunawan and Huarng, 2015). On the one hand, it increases the possibility of a purchase, but on the other, it increases the likelihood that the recipient would share the material. If the sender and recipient have a closer relationship, the likelihood that the content will be viewed significantly improves (Camarero and San José, 2011). The same holds true for the likelihood that the content will be shared (Ketelaar et al., 2016). The quality of the content is also important. If it is known that the sender consistently distributes subpar content, even a close relationship between sender and recipient is ineffective (Phelps et al., 2004). Even a high level of credibility is unable to alter the bad perception generated by a lack of quality (Hsieh et al., 2012). It is important to note that people are less critical of content they have sought for or

examined themselves than of content that has been pushed onto them (Chen and Berger, 2016). In turn, this impacts the willingness to share.

In terms of the diffusion of information, opinion leaders play a key role. They succeed in influencing the attitudes, motivations, or beliefs of others (Valente and Pumpuang, 2007). Influencers on Instagram might be regarded as thought leaders. Influencers are well-connected individuals or notable figures. Influencers can be crucial for businesses pursuing a viral marketing strategy, as they are more likely to disseminate promotional content than individuals with fewer connections (Smith et al., 2007). According to studies, the narrative presentation of content supplied by an influencer boosts its perceived informational value (Bobkowski, 2015).

The appropriate communication channel also plays a crucial impact. In this regard, it is essential that the target audience and the chosen communication channel correspond (Grifoni et al., 2013). Especially through social media, content may be swiftly and extensively shared. However, the appropriate social media channel must also be selected. LinkedIn, for instance, is an appropriate channel for B2B products and services. The focus of B2C and D2C products should be Instagram and TikTok.

2.4.3.2 Content

The level to which individuals interact with content, i.e., like, remark, or share, is highly dependent on the content itself. Therefore, the question arises as to how material must be created to achieve the largest level of virality feasible. Numerous studies have conclusively demonstrated the significance of engaging material (Berger and Milkman, 2012a, Miquel-Romero and Adame-Sánchez, 2013).

However, what makes content engaging? Multiple studies show to the emotional triggering of events (Berger and Milkman, 2012a, Berger, 2011). Emotions influence both partial intention and diffusion rate positively. Particularly emotional material appears to have a positive effect on behaviour (Heimbach and Hinz, 2016, Berger and Milkman, 2012a). Dafonte Gómez (2014), who analysed 25 viral video advertisements, and Hsieh et al. (2012) confirm the favourable influence of positive emotions in the content, particularly on the propensity to share. Humor is an example of a stimulus for positive feelings. According to Eckler and Bolls (2011), this also leads to positive emotions towards the brand. However, unpleasant emotions are more memorable than positive ones (Cohen, 2014). Emotions that result from a viewer's intense activation or enthusiasm considerably raise the intent to share (Guadagno et

al., 2013). If the source of activation or excitement is also triggered by pleasant emotions, the likelihood of sharing is much greater than if negative emotions are present (Nelson-Field et al., 2013).

According to the majority of studies, content should always evoke emotion (Dobele et al., 2007) to generate increased interest, which in turn translates into an increased likelihood to share. The emotions triggered should be as positive as possible for increased virality. to generate higher interest, which in turn increases the possibility of sharing. For greater virality, the elicited emotions should be as upbeat as feasible.

Social media consumption has a favourable effect on purchasing behaviour, hence viral marketing can have a positive effect on the purchase behaviour of recipients (Zhang et al., 2017). Viral marketing is characterised by rapid exponential growth in terms of views. Nevertheless, the dissemination rate also falls again just as quickly (Broxton et al., 2013). It is therefore crucial for businesses to incorporate recognition triggers so that viewers will remember the product or brand (Berger and Schwartz, 2011). According to Tucker (2015), there is a negative correlation between the number of views of a commercial and the purchase intention for the advertised product. This effect becomes apparent between three and four million views, because beyond a certain point, adverts are only shared due to their story. The product or brand becomes inconspicuous. To avoid this, the content must convey emotions while still incorporating the brand or product in a natural way. The brand or product shouldn't be advertised too aggressively or too subtly, as this would negatively impact the sharing probability (Hsieh et al., 2012).

Obviously, viral content carries hazards. When creating viral content from a commercial viewpoint, it is vital to carefully assess and analyse how the material will affect the audience, as negative consequences for the organisation are possible. The deployment of viral marketing with care and precision may have substantial financial benefits for businesses.

2.4.3.3 Interaction goals

What interaction objectives do individuals pursue? Most people wish to project a favourable image of themselves to others (Berger, 2014). According to one study, social media is primarily used for social connection, followed by exchanging opinions and general information (Whiting and Williams, 2013). Influencers share content to distinguish themselves from the crowd and emphasise their individuality, particularly

through their own content (Ho and Dempsey, 2010). People are more likely to share content that they feel important, amusing, or beneficial. When it is recognised that one's own image could be enhanced in the desired manner, the inclination to provide content increases (Huang et al., 2009). As a fundamental requirement for sharing, the content must adhere to social norms, as people will not tolerate harm to their reputation caused by the content they share (Palka et al., 2009).

Self-perceptions and social perceptions are the primary determinants of content sharing and, consequently, virality. This is the conclusion of Scholz et al. (2017). The primary objective of those who distribute content is to achieve favourable outcomes for themselves. Interestingly, practically all verbal expressions of opinion are favourable. However, unfavourable comments received from others are shared significantly more frequently than positive ones (De Angelis et al., 2012).

2.5 Attitude and attitude change

Since the beginning of the 20th century, attitudes and changes in attitudes have been one of the core research concerns of social psychology and communication studies, particularly in the context of persuasion research (Allport, 1935, Jonas, 2014, Pürer, 2003). A general definition of an attitude is the judgement of an attitude object (Bohner and Dickel, 2011). Positive, negative, or neutral attitudes can vary in intensity and ferocity. Objects of attitude can be either real objects, such as a particular cosmetic product, or abstract notions, such as democracy. Frequently, attitudes are decisive predictors of behaviour (e.g. Allport, 1935, Martin and Levey, 1978). To provide two examples: we seek the company of those we like and avoid that of those we dislike. Additionally, we purchase things we prefer more frequently than those we dislike.

The research done at Yale under the direction of Hovland systematically examined the impact of various content, recipient, sender, and situational circumstances on the effectiveness of rhetorical communications (Hovland et al., 1953).

2.5.1 Definition, structure and functions of attitudes

In theory, attitudes are the overall judgments of an attitude object, such as persons, behaviours, objects, or abstract concepts, in the form of an evaluative category such as positive or negative (Albarracín et al., 2005, Bohner and Dickel, 2011, Maio et al., 2009). The most prevalent definition comes from Eagly and Chaiken (1993) and is published as follows: "Attitude is a psychological tendency that is expressed by

evaluating a particular entity with some degree of favour or disfavor" (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993, p. 1). Whether a person evaluates something positively or negatively, likes it or dislikes it, supports it or rejects it, etc., these assessments are founded on his affective reactions to, his cognitions of, and his behaviour toward this object (Albarracín et al., 2005). All four phenomena are unique and distinct. In contrast to attitudes, affective reactions, i.e., emotions and feelings, need not be tied to a specific object or event (Berkowitz, 2000, Niedenthal et al., 2006). While both beliefs and attitudes are classifications, beliefs pertain to the likelihood that an object or event is connected with a characteristic. They are more easily verifiable than attitudes (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993, Fishbein and Ajzen, 1975, Wyer Jr and Albarracín, 2005). Behaviour comprises an individual's observable acts, which may not always correspond with his attitudes (Fishbein and Ajzen, 2010).

Influence of affect, beliefs, and behaviour on attitudes: While these three occurrences can provide the basis for attitudes independently or in combination, attitudes can exert a reciprocal influence on them (Albarracín et al., 2005, Olson and Zanna, 1993). Consequently, attitudes can be derived from affective reactions, beliefs, and behaviour (Albarracín et al., 2005). In conclusion, this exemplifies the definition of attitudes by Albarracín and colleagues (2005) as "(...) evaluative tendencies, which can both be inferred from and have an influence on beliefs, affect, and overt behaviour" (Albarracín et al., 2005, p. 5). Additionally, attitudes vary according to their mental representation. Thus, attitudes can be represented in the mind as stable dispositions, that is, as strong linkages between an item and its associated judgement. In addition, these are frequently situation-specific, short-term judgments (Bohner and Dickel, 2011, Fabrigar et al., 2005). In this instance, in addition to extrinsic elements like mood or social setting, the convictions and emotions that are currently available and deemed important have a significant effect (Ajzen, 2001, Schwarz and Clore, 1983). Affective aspects are more readily available than cognitive ones - also known as the affective primacy hypothesis (Zajonc, 1980, Verplanken et al., 1998). With consistency between affect and beliefs, it is easier to anticipate attitudes and behaviour than with inconsistency or ambivalence. Unlike consistency, where all qualities are nearly equally accurate predictors, ambivalence is mostly influenced by affect (Lavine et al., 1998). Individuals differ in whether they are more likely to form attitudes based on their thoughts and emotions (Haddock and Zanna, 1998). Similarly, attitudes toward some objects are founded on affective rather than cognitive factors (Kempf, 1999). It is also conceivable for individuals to base attitude

assessments on earlier behaviours linked with an object of attitude (Olson and Stone, 2005). According to the theory of self-perception (Bem, 1972) individuals often develop their attitudes through attribution processes based on their own behaviour. This is especially true of weak or unclear attitudes (Chaiken and Baldwin, 1981). In the context of Festinger (1957) theory of cognitive dissonance, it is assumed that in some settings, people adjust their attitudes so that they agree with their behaviour and thereby reduce dissonance (Kim et al., 2014). Depending on the situation, it is also conceivable for a person to hold multiple attitudes toward the same attitude object (Lieberman and Chaiken, 1996). In addition to stability, accessibility, and composition of affect, beliefs, and/or behaviour, the structure of attitudes is also characterised by active knowledge (eng. working knowledge), i.e. the number of accessible affective, cognitive, and conative attributes to an object of attitudes, and complexity, i.e. the diversity of this knowledge in terms of qualitative differences between attributes (Fabrigar et al., 2005). An additional differentiation is proposed based on the degree to which individuals are conscious of their attitudes (Bohner and Dickel, 2011, Nosek et al., 2007). In the context of methodological developments for the indirect measurement of attitudes based on response times, such as the Implicit Association Test (Greenwald et al., 1998b), it was discovered that these so-called implicit attitudes do not always coincide with the explicit attitudes expressed by individuals or have the same behavioural implications (Fazio and Olson, 2003, Goodall and Ewoldsen, 2011). Implicit attitudes, defined as spontaneously triggered object assessment associations, are extremely inaccessible to introspection, not purposeful or controlled, but efficient, in contrast to explicit attitudes (Bohner and Dickel, 2011, Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006). In accordance with these characteristics, implicitly measured attitudes tend to be more accurate predictors of information processing or behaviour than explicitly measured attitudes in contexts where resources or motivation for reflected and controlled, propositional processing-based attitudes are present or in sensitive contexts where social desirability or similar distortions are explicitly expressed (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006, Wittenbrink and Schwarz, 2007).

Theoretical approaches to the functional relevance of attitudes have highlighted a variety of attitudes' possible functions (Carpenter et al., 2013, Katz, 1960, Smith et al., 1956). Attitudes enable the organisation, structuring, and hence the comprehension of the external world (knowledge function), as well as the efficient discrimination of objects in terms of their valence, or perhaps their utility (utilitarian function). But they can also be firmly related to the individual and express personally

significant values (value expression function) or defend the individual's self-esteem against aggression (self-defense). In addition, attitudes facilitate and control social interactions and relationships (social adaptation) (Ajzen, 2001, Carpenter et al., 2013). Thus, it is possible for the attitudes of two individuals to be identical but each to have a distinct purpose (Carpenter et al., 2013). Relevance comes for persuasion research from the ability to adjust communications to the attitudes' underlying functions, hence potentially improving the persuasive effect (Carpenter et al., 2013). In general, it is important to highlight that attitude contents, attitude structures, and attitude functions are interconnected. For instance, attitudes that serve distinct purposes frequently differ in the nature of their underlying beliefs (Maio et al., 2009).

2.5.2 Types of attitudes

Attitudes can be categorised in various ways. There is currently a distinction between explicit and implicit attitudes. Explicit attitudes are accessible introspectively and can be articulated directly, although certain motivations may impede direct expression. In contrast, implicit attitudes are engaged naturally and frequently evade reflection and verbal reporting. Accordingly, direct and indirect approaches for measuring attitudes are distinguished. For measuring explicit attitudes, direct questions and various rating measures are usually employed (Bohner and Wänke, 2002). On the other hand, indirect measuring techniques reveal the implicit attitude through reaction times or behavioural patterns. The most popular indirect measurement methods include the Implicit Association Test (Greenwald et al., 1998a) and the Automatic Evaluation Task (Fazio et al., 1995). Direct and indirect measurement methods correlate positively (Bar-Anan and Nosek, 2014, Dovidio et al., 2002), but not perfectly, hence implicit and explicit attitudes towards the same object can differ (Petty et al., 2003).

2.5.3 Persuasion

2.5.3.1 *Theoretical explanations of persuasion processes*

Beginning with the cognitive-response approach (Greenwald, 1968, Cacioppo et al., 1981), the valence of cognitions in response to a persuasive message is viewed as the most important predictor of persuasive effects (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993). If a message generates mainly positive thoughts, it is most likely successful. If the recipients react predominantly negatively and generate counterarguments, a message is most likely to miss its target. The two dominant theories, the Elaboration-Likelihood-Model (ELM) (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986b, Petty and Cacioppo, 1986a,

Petty and Cacioppo, 2012, Petty and Wegener, 1999) and the Heuristic-Systematic-Model (HSM) (Chaiken, 1980, Chaiken et al., 1989, Chen et al., 1999), differentiate between processing routes requiring high cognitive effort and those requiring minimal cognitive effort, which can result in persuasive effects of variable quality. In contrast to the two two-process models conceptualize one-process models, such as the Unimodel of Persuasion (Kruglanski and Thompson, 1999, Kruglanski et al., 1999) or the cognition-in-persuasion model (Albarracín, 2002), conceptualise the persuasion process as a continuum of propositional - i. e. conceptual, logical - thinking from low to high processing effort, rather than as two qualitative In their Associative-Propositional-Evaluation-Model, Gawronski and Bodenhausen (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006, Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2011) propose an expansion of prior models (APEM). They combine propositional and association processing, as well as their persuasive impact on both conscious and implicit attitudes.

As stated at the commencement, the extent and especially the valence of topic-relevant elaboration are crucial determinants of a message's persuasive power (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993, Greenwald, 1968). Topic-relevant elaboration refers to the questioning, weighing, and checking of the contents or arguments of a message, the drawing of inferences, the generation of new arguments, and the determination of the final (new) position in relation to the attitude object, against the background of one's own relevant background knowledge (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986b). The extent to which the elaboration is positive or negative for the intended message depends primarily on the perceived strength or validity of the arguments in the message, the extent to which it elicits reactance, the recipient's mood as well as his or her prior knowledge and attitudes, and the degree to which it triggers reactance (Bodenhausen and Gawronski, 2013, Briñol and Petty, 2006). This processing of a message with a high cognitive effort - referred to as systematic processing in HSM (Chaiken, 1980), in the ELM central route (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986a) - leads to the integration of all important information into the underlying knowledge structures of the respective attitude in memory, resulting in a stable and consistent attitude. (Briñol and Petty, 2006). However, persuasive effects can be evident even if recipients do not engage with a message in depth. In this instance, they are impacted by rapid and efficient processing strategies requiring little cognitive effort, as modelled in the ELM in the peripheral route (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986b) and in the HSM in heuristic processing (Chaiken, 1980). Here, the content is decided by irrelevant cues, such as the attractiveness or favorability of the sender, the good or negative mood of the

recipients, and heuristics, which are simple, learnt schemes or decision rules that have a persuasive effect, such as the increased credibility of an expert (Chaiken, 1980, Chaiken and Trope, 1999, Petty and Cacioppo, 1986b). Two elements determine whether recipients process a message with high or low mental effort: their capacity and motivation for intensive processing (Brinol & Petty, 2006; Chaiken et al., 1989; Petty & Cacioppo, 1986b). The ability to work intensively is hindered, for instance, by a lack of understanding and the message's high complexity, a lack of cognitive resources owing to distraction or anxiety reactions, and can be improved by, among other things, repeating the message (Briñol and Petty, 2006, Chaiken et al., 1989, Petty and Cacioppo, 1986b). The most focus was paid to the influence of distraction on the persuasive process in terms of capability. According to research, distraction can both strengthen and reduce the persuasive power of a message (Baron et al., 1973, Festinger and Maccoby, 1964, McGuire, 1964, Petty et al., 1976, Tormala and Petty, 2004). Due to the fact that distraction demands cognitive resources and hence distracts the elaboration of the information, the effect depends on which cognitive responses to the message predominate. If distraction precludes the development of counter-arguments, the persuasive effect of a message improves; but, if distraction prevents the elaboration of agreement, it diminishes relative to instances of reception without distraction (Briñol and Petty, 2006, Petty et al., 1976). In addition to being able to comprehend it deeply, recipients must also be adequately motivated to devote themselves to the message in depth. In addition to surprising or unexpected aspects, multiple independent sources instead of a single source, and rhetorical questions, it is the perceived personal relevance of a message's topic or content, also known as involvement, that motivates the recipients to conduct a more intensive, critical examination of the message (Briñol and Petty, 2006, Chaiken, 1980, Petty and Cacioppo, 1986b). Like many other concepts, involvement (for more see chapter 2.1.5) has a very heterogeneous conceptual diversity (Slater and Rouner, 2002a). Sherif and colleagues have established the notion of ego-involvement, which explains the extent to which something influences an individual's commitment to a situation by affecting his or her self-image (Sherif and Sherif, 1967, Sherif and Sargent, 1947). In accordance with the problem participation utilised by Petty and colleagues (Cacioppo et al., 1979, Petty et al., 1992), it also includes any personal relevance of a communication theme for a recipient, even if it is simply situational. A distinction between possible types of involvement, as proposed by Johnson and Eagly (Johnson and Eagly, 1989), is not meaningful because their general influence on

processing and persuasion does not differ and possible differences have not been distinguished from confounding factors such as the disparity between message and recipient attitudes (Johnson and Eagly, 1989, Johnson and Eagly, 1990, Maio and Olson, 1995). A constraint on engagement as a motivating element that heightens the intensity of message processing is therefore logical. According to meta-analyses, involvement has a negative influence on persuasion, i.e., recipients with a high level of involvement are less likely to be persuaded by persuasive messages because they scrutinise the arguments more seriously (Groeben and Drinkmann, 1989, Johnson and Eagly, 1989). In addition to participation, a number of personality factors influence the incentive for extensive processing. The most important are the Need for Cognition requirements (Cacioppo and Petty, 1982) - i. e. the individual disposition to pursue strenuous cognitive activities and enjoy them, the need to evaluate (Jarvis and Petty, 1996) - this is the tendency to make judgments about attitude objects and the need for closure (Webster and Kruglanski, 1994) - the need for a definitive answer or final clarity. In conclusion, the greater an individual's motivation and ability to process persuasive messages, the more systematically they can process them. In this instance, the persuasiveness of a communication is mostly determined by its content, which consists of considerable evidence and solid arguments. If the recipient lacks the ability and/or willingness to pay close attention to the message, then peripheral cues or heuristics will be more influential in its persuasive effect. Relevant to persuasion are characteristics that influence motivation and cognitive processing abilities, as well as the direction or valence of cognitions, and/or serve as arguments, cues, or heuristics. Consequently, a variable might play various functions as an influential variable in the persuasion process, depending on the situation and the individual (Briñol and Petty, 2006, Petty and Wegener, 1998). In the ELM, the two processing paths reflect the respective ideal-typical poles of a continuum (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986a, Petty and Wegener, 1998), whereas in the HSM, they are expressly recognised as distinct modes that can occur or interact concurrently (Chaiken et al., 1989, Chen et al., 1999). Even while the substance and reasoning of a communication are more influential in intensive, critical processing, this does not mean that heuristics and other cues are not used and consequently have no effect. Rather, they can also augment or weaken the persuasive effect and, as relatively automatic and rapid processing processes, guide the slower, more cognitively complex processes. In the context of the development of one-process models, the degree to which these two processing processes genuinely represent distinct modes is a contentious issue (e.g.

Albarracín, 2002, Albarracin and Wyer Jr, 2001, Bodenhausen and Gawronski, 2013, Kruglanski et al., 1999, Kruglanski and Thompson, 1999). As was previously stated, persuasive effects can result from both systematic, intensive processing and heuristic, transitory processing of a message. However, attitudes that arise from deliberate thought are more robust than those that are created more instinctively and without cognitive effort. Therefore, attitudes based on the systematic or central route are more available, stable, resistant to other persuasion influences, and predictive of behaviour (Bodenhausen and Gawronski, 2013, Briñol and Petty, 2006, Chaiken and Trope, 1999, Chen et al., 1999, Petty and Wegener, 1999).

2.5.3.2 Integrative models of persuasion

The development of theories of attitude change has gone through different trends (McGuire, 1985). Since the 1980s, a theoretical style referred to as "integrative models" has dominated, as it views the change of attitude with low cognitive effort and high cognitive effort to be integrative. Initially, emphasis was placed on the two-process models of persuasion, which suggest that there are two methods of processing information that might lead to an attitude change. As with the Cognitive Response Approach, an intricate, content-related processing mode is anticipated. However, attitude changes can also be the outcome of a less time-intensive process.

The two most prevalent two-process models are the Elaboration Likelihood Model and the Heuristic Systematic Model. First, the fundamental assumptions of these two models are outlined, followed by a description of the uni-model of persuasion, which was designed as an alternative to the two-process models, but which may also be seen as an integrative model. Finally, the associative-propositional value model will be introduced, which attempts to explain the interaction between implicit and explicit changes in attitudes in an integrative manner.

2.5.3.2.1 Model of the Elaboration likelihood

The Elaboration likelihood model (ELM) (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986b, Petty and Briñol, 2012) posits that people have a basic interest in adopting appropriate attitudes. The processing intensity and manner of attitude-relevant information depend on the recipients' capacity and motivation.

The central processing path can only be taken if both the ability and motivation of the target individual are substantial. This entails analysing information and arguments in

depth, i.e., the individual engages in an in-depth and critical analysis of the message's subject matter and evaluates the quality of the arguments. In this instance, an attitude shift happens when the arguments and information are of high quality and convincing. Consequently, a person must have the opportunity and capacity to intensively digest the persuasive message, as well as an interest in and motivation to do so. This raises the possibility of intensive processing (likelihood of elaboration) of the provided information.

If a person is unmotivated or incapable of intensively processing a message, the peripheral path is adopted. In this instance, the quality of the arguments is not decisive, but the individual's attitude will alter if some peripheral cues have an effect that is independent of the quality of the arguments. Peripheral cues include the source's attractiveness, assumed knowledge or awareness, duration of communication, etc. For instance, individuals with low levels of motivation and ability are more likely to approve expert messages than those from non-experts, regardless of their substance (Bohner & Wanker, 2006). Peripheral processing is prevalent in daily life since it saves time and mental effort.

Motivation and the ability to work intensively are influenced by various individual and situational factors (Frey et al., 1993). Important are the characteristics of communication itself. If the topic is highly relevant to the individual, the motivation to analyse the information more thoroughly increases (Petty et al., 1981, Thomsen et al., 1995). In a study, Dijkstra and Ballast (Dijkstra and Ballast, 2012) showed that personalising a persuasive message in a smoking cessation program was only successful if the perceived personal relevance was high. In contrast, a message's great complexity can hinder its ability to undergo intensive processing. Moreover, the setting in which communication occurs plays an essential role. Under time constraint or distraction, for example, the ability to process information via the central pathway declines. Additionally, receiver characteristics influence the chance of elaboration. When individuals have past knowledge of a topic, it is easier for them to intensively assimilate new information. Similarly, there are people who enjoy thinking more than others (Bless et al., 1994, Cacioppo and Petty, 1982) and are therefore probably more motivated to process a message intensively (Cacioppo et al., 1983). The communicators' traits must also be evaluated. Thus, a clear self-interest on the part of the communicator could result in a more critical perspective of the presented information and a more comprehensive analysis of it (Bohner et al., 1995a). The

medium of communication also has an important influence. A complex message, for instance, can be processed more effectively and intensively if it is presented visually and not merely aurally, as this permits repeated and accurate reading (Frey et al., 1993).

Even though attitudes can be altered by both the central and peripheral routes, the stability of the new attitudes varies. As a result of rigorous processing, attitudes are more stable and change-resistant than attitudes that result from a focus on surface cues. Therefore, attitudes that are formed or altered centrally are more accurate predictors of behaviour and more resistant to efforts to change them (Petty and Cacioppo, 2012).

The ELM continues to presume a sort of "trade-off" between the two modes of processing information, which means that the importance of central processing on a judgement grows as the influence of peripheral processing reduces. This suggests that throughout the majority of the elaboration continuum, both types of processing occur concurrently and can influence judgement jointly. In addition, travel along this continuum implies that the relative effect of the two processes shifts in different ways.

After more than three decades, the ELM remains one of the most prominent models for altering attitudes and is utilised in a variety of communication study fields outside of advertising psychology.

2.5.3.2.2 Heuristic Systematic Model

The Heuristic systematic model (HSM) (Bohner et al., 1995b, Chaiken et al., 1989) has many similarities to the ELM. It also differentiates between a complex (systematic) kind of information processing and a less complex (heuristic) form. As in ELM, the systematic processing of persuasive messages is characterised by an emphasis on argument quality and is cognitively sophisticated, comprehensive, and controlled. Heuristic processing, in comparison, is simple, rapid, and takes few cognitive resources. People utilise heuristics when a communication is especially complex or of low significance. In persuasive messages, available cues (e.g., indicators of the communicator's expert knowledge) are processed using heuristics (i.e., decision rules such as "experts should be believed"), provided that these heuristics are cognitively available, conveniently accessible, and applicable. Differences between the peripheral route in the ELM and the HSM are primarily due to the HSM's more detailed assumptions regarding when and how heuristically processing occurs.

Although the fundamental assumptions of HSM and ELM are fairly similar, there are significant distinctions. HSM assumptions on the motivational fundamentals of processing are more differentiated than ELM assumptions (Bohner et al., 1995b). The HSM differentiates between accuracy motivation (i.e., the desire to hold accurate attitudes), defence motivation (i.e., the need to defend self-relevant attitudes), and impression motivation (i. e., the desire to possess attitudes that provide social recognition). The accuracy motive coincides with the expected motivation in the ELM. It can exist with the other two motifs and can be fulfilled with either more or less processing (Chen et al., 1999). In addition, the HSM postulates a “sufficiency threshold”. If heuristic processing methods are adequate to attain the appropriate level of judgmental confidence, then there is no systematic processing. People, according to the HSM, seek a balance between the principle of least effort and the drive to have accurate (or, in the sense of the prevalent motive, optimal) attitudes.

The relationship between the two processing types is a further distinction from ELM. In contrast to the ELM, the HSM does not presume antagonism between the two processes; instead, it suggests that heuristic and systematic processing can occur simultaneously and postulates particular theories regarding their interaction. The additivity theory states that heuristic and systematic processing can have independent outcomes. If evidence of content is systematically processed, the effect of a heuristic reference stimulus is concealed or lessened, according to the mitigation hypothesis. For instance, a reference to the communicator's high level of competence may not have any further impact if the persuasiveness of his or her arguments has already been considered. The distortion theory states that heuristics establish an expectation that can skew future systematic processing. Consequently, a reliable source led to a positively biased processing of the supplied arguments, which was especially pronounced when these arguments were confusing (Chaiken and Maheswaran, 1994). Lastly, the contrast hypothesis describes the case of the mirror image: If successful arguments defy a heuristic expectation, processing is warped in the other way (Bohner et al., 1995b). Therefore, students may be less persuaded by the same weak arguments if they are delivered by an expert instead of a layperson (Bohner et al., 2002, Bohner et al., 2008).

Alongside ELM, HSM is one of the most influential persuasion theories and is utilised in a variety of fields of study, including smoking cessation programmes. (Webb

Hooper et al., 2013), medical decision making for cancer patients (Steginga et al., 2004) and consumer behaviour (Dardis and Shen, 2008, Chang, 2004).

2.5.3.2.3 Unimodel of persuasion

Despite the fact that both ELM and HSM have been empirically validated and continue to influence research, there are a number of key considerations. Both two-process theories presuppose a continuum of processing depth but emphasise two qualitatively distinct poles (central/systematic and peripheral/heuristic) on this continuum. In their Unimodel, Kruglanski and colleagues (Erb et al., 2003, Kruglanski and Thompson, 1999) question the premise of two qualitatively distinct processing processes and instead assume a single process in which the distinctions in information processing are merely quantitative. The authors of the Unimodel are also critical of the fact that the processing modes proposed by the two-process models correspond to distinct information categories (peripheral cues vs. arguments). In contrast to the two-process theories, the Unimodel postulates that both types of information are functionally similar and therefore interchangeable in terms of their processing importance. For instance, a peripheral cue stimulus can influence high or low motivation, and a content argument can play a role at either low or high capacity. Therefore, there are no intrinsic properties of information that determine how it is processed. Instead, the Unimodel postulates numerous orthogonal characteristics, the combination of which determines the processing level. This includes the personal importance of the material, the subjective difficulty of processing, motivation, and cognitive ability. All parameters should be seen as continuums, not as dichotomies. In conclusion, the Unimodel emphasises the concept of continuity and postulates that the degree of processing depth ultimately depends on a set of continuous characteristics.

In the meantime, various investigations corroborate the Unimodel's fundamental assumptions (Kruglanski et al., 2007). For example, Erb et al. (Erb et al., 2003) could demonstrate that strong processing motivation can increase the influence of complex peripheral information. On the other hand, even with minimal motivation, a basic argument can be persuasive. In this instance, the intricacy of the information affects whether or not it influences attitudes, regardless of whether the stimulus is a substantial argument or a peripheral cue. This contradicts the assumptions of the two-process theories, which argue that increasing motivation typically results in more systematic and less heuristic information processing (Bohner and Siebler, 1999). The Unimodel also has potential implications for more practical fields, such as health-

related information transmission. In the realm of cancer prevention and early detection, Kruglanski and colleagues (Kruglanski et al., 2006) propose that effective communication techniques can be drawn from the Unimodel. Different measures can be created based on the motivational and cognitive resources of the recipients, but they can all produce the same degree of profound attitude change (Kruglanski et al., 2006).

Recently, the Unimodel has been utilised not just to explain changes in attitudes but also as a general model to explain the creation of opinions (Kruglanski et al., 2007). The assessment of available evidence leads to the creation of a judgement through a quasi-logical procedure. Overall, the Unimodel is an intriguing alternative to ELM and HSM because it not only makes more economical assumptions but can also be used in a variety of human decision-making domains (e. g. attribution, perception of people, social influence).

Even though the architects of the three persuasion models discussed thus far emphasise the contrasts between the theories, they can be categorised as "integrative models." Whether the distinctions between the processing methods are qualitative or quantitative may ultimately be a matter of perspective. Petty, Wheeler and Bizer (Petty et al., 1999) suggest that, depending on how the underlying continuum is defined, nearly every psychological process can be viewed as quantitative (rather than qualitative). Additionally, there are advantages to quality distinction (Bohner and Siebler, 1999, Petty et al., 1999).

[2.5.3.2.4 Associative-propositional model of evaluation](#)

In some ways, the associative-propositional model of evaluation (APE model) (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006, Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2011) is an integrative model, as it was originally intended to combine seemingly contradictory information into explicit and implicit attitude changes. According to the APE model, attitudes are built on two distinct mental processes: associative judgments are regarded as the basis for implicit attitudes, while propositional conclusions are regarded as the basis for explicit attitudes.

The APE model interprets associative evaluations as automatic emotive responses triggered by the perception of the relevant attitude object. This activation procedure involves little cognitive power and evaluates the attitude object without conscious purpose. Various association patterns are activated based on the circumstances and

the memory's existing associations. An essential feature of associative evaluations is their independence from truth attributions (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006). This indicates that an associative evaluation can be engaged regardless of whether the individual considers this evaluation to be accurate or inaccurate. Negative connections against Muslims, for instance, can be generated automatically, even if the individual deems these negative associations to be erroneous or inappropriate. There is no requirement for personal endorsement of associative judgments. These associative judgments are tested by indirect or implicit measures of attitude, such as the implicit association test (Greenwald et al., 1989), the AMP ("affective misattribution procedure") (Payne et al., 2005) and the automatic evaluation task (Fazio, 1995).

Propositional evaluations, on the other hand, are based on syllogistic deductions concerning propositional facts pertinent to the specific judgement. According to Strack and Deutsch (Strack and Deutsch, 2004), such conclusions are generated by a reflecting system that translates the associative network's input into a propositional structure. For instance, a negative affective reaction can be translated as "I cannot stand Person X." The validity of these propositions is then evaluated, and truth values are assigned to them. If a proposition is consistent with other relevant propositional views, it is regarded as legitimate and can be used as the basis for an evaluative judgement. In contrast, a proposition is regarded as invalid if it contradicts another proposition. For instance, the conversion of a negative affective reaction to a member of a minority into a proposition ("I don't like these Turks") could be contradictory with the statement "It is unacceptable to assess adversely members of a discriminated minority." This discrepancy could therefore lead to the rejection of the negative affective reaction as a valid basis for an evaluation (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006).

The transformation of associative valuations into propositions can explain how a change in an implicit attitude can result in an explicit attitude change. Inversely, propositions can also affect associative assessments since they enhance the activation level of a related association in the memory system (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006). Thus, it is also conceivable to explain how pure knowledge of a stereotype about a certain foreign group might lead to automatic negative evaluations of that foreign group, even if the stereotype is inaccurate (Bohner and Dickel, 2011, Devine, 1989). The APE model is distinguished by its explicit assumptions regarding the interaction between associative and propositional

processes. Gawronski and Bodenhausen (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006) describe eight instances in which associative and propositional processes should individually or jointly contribute to distinct patterns of implicit and explicit change in attitudes. Case 1 illustrates an indirect effect of associative valuations' direct effect on the propositional conclusion. In this instance, it would be able to witness a changed attitude both implicitly and overtly, with the explicit change being entirely mediated by the implicit change. According to Gawronski and Bodenhausen (Gawronski and Bodenhausen, 2006), it is also conceivable for the implicit attitude to alter while the explicit attitude remains unchanged. This is the situation if the associative structure changes but the associative valuations are inconsistent with activated, valid proposition values.

Theoretically, the APE model can incorporate multiple study findings on explicit and implicit attitude change and generate new predictions. Advocates of the single-process models (Albarracín et al., 2006, Kruglanski and Dechesne, 2006) criticised the APE model because they believe that the assumption of qualitatively distinct processes is unnecessary and that both explicit and implicit changes in attitudes can be explained by a single continuous process. Even though the APE model was initially developed to theoretically integrate findings on explicit and implicit changes in attitudes, the influence and reciprocal interaction of associative and propositional processes are now also used in other processes, particularly applied areas such as political decision-making (Galdi et al., 2008), consumer psychology (Gawronski, 2013) or affective disorders (Ouimet et al., 2009).

2.6 Narrative Persuasion

Every consumer has a fundamental comprehension of what a narrative entails (Polanyi, 1981, p. 315). Our culture is expressed through storytelling, and narratives dominate human communication (Barthes and Duisit, 1975, p. 237). Many experts assert that narratives are the predominant type of human thought (Adaval and Wyer Jr, 1998, Escalas, 2004). People impart knowledge and convey their experiences and emotions through the use of narratives. However, narratives do not merely function to convey information; they also enable the recipient to experience particular emotions in a specific manner. People succumb to the beauty of books, theatre plays and operas - or develop a spontaneous preference for romantic films because they are cold (Hong and Sun, 2012, p. 303). They immerse themselves in a universe and

experience the narratives as if they were part of their own world and life. It is considered that we only desire lovely, pleasant emotions in our life and, hence, only wish to hear such stories, e.g. in the shape of films (Kroeber-Riel and Gröppel-Klein, 2013, p. 179). It is surprising that consumers do not do this (De Wied et al., 1995, p. 92): When people watch horror films, they place themselves in a terrifying scenario (Brewer, 1996, p. 107). Perhaps they suffer when stories like "Romeo and Juliet" have a tragic conclusion (Schramm and Wirth, 2010, p. 320). The impact of narratives extends beyond reception alone. Rather, it resembles the effect of a narrative. This is how consumers desire to experience the emotional impact of narratives, such as via listening to film music, prolonging a narrative cinema experience (Batat and Wohlfeil, 2009, p. 375), or by discussing a film, book, etc. (Russell and Schau, 2014).

Additionally, narratives are utilised in advertising. For instance, advertising in the form of narratives can evoke the entire spectrum of good emotions but can also make customers unhappy or furious, thus diminishing the effectiveness of the advertisement (Batra and Ray, 1986). This demonstrates the intricacy of narratives and the variety of options available to storytellers. Using narrative persuasion, businesses can persuade prospective clients and overcome objections. For the advantage of the business, attitudes must be altered.

2.6.1 Narration

Booth distinguishes between two kinds of narrative in his essay *The Rhetoric of Narrative Art: narration and representation* (Booth, 1974). As this distinction is addressed in a considerable measure of literature, it will be explained here.

Narration

According to Booth, narrative styles vary with the period. In early narrative literature, the author communicated to the reader directly through the narrative. In "authoritative rhetoric," "the author or his trusted speaker appears directly" by commenting and judging from this vantage point (Booth, 1974, p. 14). The author writes that an action is either good or bad, and that a character is either beautiful and good or ugly and nasty. In modern narrative writing, indirect representation has supplanted this direct narration.

Representation

Instead of directly evaluating a character or action as good and right or evil and wrong, the author can explain what occurs. The reader forms his own impression based on the story's illustration. He reads about a who who gets up early, milks the cows, feeds the animals, prepares breakfast and wakes the children, works all day without complaining, and is the last one to go to bed; the author's judgmental premise about a hardworking man is dropped. The reader must independently determine the significance of the whole image. Booth asserts that proper presentation requires dramatic narration: The narrative must be more than a simple, insignificant fact. The story must speak for itself (Booth, 1974, p. 32).

This representation is not objective, despite the absence of judgmental predicates and commentary. Here, too, "the author's arranging hand becomes visible" (Booth, 1974, p. 27). Through indirect representation, the author merely transmits his thoughts more softly than he would through direct narrative, in which he evaluates explicitly: "The author's judgment is always present, always evident to anyone who knows how to search for it." (Booth, 1974, p. 29) Even if the author of a story refers to a pure transmission and does not incorporate morality and commentary, he betrayed himself to the reader simply by selecting what he is telling." (Booth, 1974, p. 29) This already demonstrates the narratives' ideal application to persuasion.

Narrative Persuasion

Narratives must contain "vivid drama," "sincerity," or a comparable element. (Booth, 1974, p. 45). Therefore, the art of narration should appear pure and genuine.

Not the aesthetic art character, but the reality character is vital for narrative persuasion: narratives that are intended to be more compelling must be realistic. They need not depict reality; they can be imaginary, but the reader must believe that this is a plausible scenario. The narrative must be convincing.

2.6.2 Definition of narratives

Various authors study narratives and stories in their articles. Green and Brock state that a narrative should include a plot that generates questions and resolves difficulties: "Narratives must have [...] a real story line: Questions are raised which are only answered in subsequent portions of the narrative" (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 319). Berman and Schank use the term "story" to denote "a structured, coherent retelling of

an experience or a fictitious account of an experience " (Schank and Berman, 2002, p. 288). They demonstrate that humans learn and think through storytelling. Slater examines narratives via the lens of narrative simulation. Narrative simulations are "short stories that illustrate possible negative consequences " (Slater, 2002b, p. 165).

First, the impacts of narratives are frequently included in the concept of narratives, which is problematic. Nevertheless, effects and definition must be separated. Narratives are not stories that give a framework, are simple to comprehend and memorise, discreetly illustrate, are believable, possess psychological resistance, and emotionally engage and transport the reader. These qualities are not attributes that these narratives must always possess; rather, they are partially qualities that only narratives receive, but which they are not required to receive, and partly qualities that narratives are not the only ones capable of receiving. These attributes are referred to as potentials since they can be added to narratives.

Second, narrative and story are not always distinguished from one another. In general, the examined literature makes no apparent distinctions. The concepts of narrative and story are not clearly distinguished. Hanyard and Kreuter criticise this as well. (Hinyard and Kreuter, 2007, p. 778).

A narration is rather a purposeful communicative action (Viehöver, 2012, p. 66), by means of which a narrative or a narrative text is written or communicated. A text understood as a "limited ordered sign complex with communicative intention, [...] where the sign systems or codes can change" (Knape, 2008, p. 896) - can be noted in any way: "vocal-acoustic, written-optical, written-haptic [...], signing-optic" (Knape, 2008, p.896-897) and signing-haptic. This results in many scenarios from which the narrator may choose. A narrative includes a storyline with a clear beginning, middle, and end, as well as characters (Hinyard and Kreuter, 2007, p. 778). This narrative communication is persuasive not by definition, but when it causes a change in attitude in the addressee; narrative communication is rhetorical when it is developed strategically with the purpose of generating an attitude change.

2.6.3 Classification of narrative persuasion in psychology

Within psychology, social psychology is concerned with study on attitudes. Among other things, this research investigates how persuasion or "attitude change as a result of information processing" (Bohner and Wänke, 2002, p. 276) takes place.

It is believed that attitudes are the result of cognitive, emotional, and behavioural processes. They influence the cognition, emotions, and behaviour of humans without the persons' awareness (Bohner and Wänke, 2002, p.268). It is unclear whether attitude change is largely driven by cognitive or affective elements, by facts and arguments, or by altering the emotional responses to an attitude object (Fuegen and Brehm, 2004, p. 41).

The ELM is a fundamental paradigm of persuasion. Depending on the level of elaboration, this model emphasises distinct stages and outcomes in the persuasion process: motivation and information processing ability are necessary for elaboration. The degree of interest and the topic's importance are decisive for motivation (for more 2.5.3.2.1).

What does this suggest about the persuasive power of narratives? It can be expected that narrative persuasion occurs with minimal elaboration because Gerrig has already demonstrated that narrative reception occurs with minimal elaboration: "A reader need only invest minimal attention to experience a narrative world" (Gerrig, 1993, p. 237-238). Therefore, narrative persuasion occurs on the peripheral route: typically, no one reads a novel in order to engage with the text's message; people read novels for enjoyment. One can also presume that television viewers, film and theatre audiences are seeking enjoyment. Critical thinking is improper for this type of entertainment; a critical attitude typical of complex works would impair the enjoyment of this work. The motivation and relevance of the topic, as well as the level of detail, are rather low. If the level of elaboration is low, the model predicts that persuasion should only occur in response to certain cues, such as identification. If it occurs, the event and its effects should be temporary.

Green and others have presented an opposing argument. According to them, narrative persuasion is more powerful and enduring than argumentation persuasion: "We claim that when pure tests are conducted, narrative persuasion, in comparison to rhetorical persuasion (i.e., argumentation), will lead to belief changes that resist counterinfluence and that persist longer over time." (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 336)

2.6.4 Theoretical Approaches for explaining Narrative Persuasion

Although there are other theoretical methods and models of narrative persuasion, narrative experience - or transport, absorption, or immersion - is viewed as the primary explanation for the influence of stories (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008, Gerrig, 1993,

Green and Brock, 2000, Moyer-Gusé, 2008, Slater and Rouner, 2002a). The four most relevant theoretical approaches, the Transportation Imagery Model, the Extended Laboration Likelihood Model, the Entertainment-Overcoming Resistance Model, and the Narrative Understanding and Experience Model, will now be used to present the different conceptualizations of this phenomenon and its detailed modelling in the process of narrative persuasion.

2.6.4.1 *Transportation*

Gerrig has previously employed the phrase “transportation” (Gerrig, 1993, p. 157-195). Transportation has been identified by Green and Brock as a major element of persuasive narratives (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 319). They define transportation as “a convergent process, where all of the person's mental systems and capacities become focused on the events occurring in the narrative.” (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 324) Recipients who are transported experience the story inside and respond emotionally to its events (Mazzocco et al., 2010, p. 365).

According to some academics, transportation also occurs during discussion (Dunlop et al., 2010, p. 154). Green's research consistently demonstrates the opposite: “The effects of transportation were unique to narratives and did not extend to rhetorical (i.e., argumentative) communications” (Mazzocco et al., 2010, p. 361) Regardless, transportation can be described in a broader sense without more explanation. Transportation is the process or state in which an individual forgets his or her surroundings and enters a cognitive world (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 316). Abstract speech is likewise intended to be covered by the phrase “cognitive world”.

Transportation impacts narrative in numerous ways:

- **Transportation enhances identification and persuasion.** In the outermost case, the recipient forgets himself and mentally assumes the identities of the narrative's characters (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 326). The stronger the transport, the more the recipient of a narrative is immersed in the narrative, and the more likely he is to identify with the narrative's characters and embrace its messages.
- **Transportation reduces mental resistance.** The narrative creates its own world. If the recipient loses contact with reality during elevated transportation (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 325), normal opinions and attitudes do not apply. He does not analyse the narrative text's statements and messages with his

everyday attitudes and he does not contradict the character with whom he identifies.

- **Transportation prevents critical thinking.** Furthermore, "imagery [...] acts as a cognitive 'load' that can interfere with cognate tasks" (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 336). The recipient cannot process messages at a high cognitive level.
- **Transportation reduces situational resistance.** If a recipient is engrossed in thoughts, if his thoughts revolve around concerns while reading, or if he is otherwise absent-minded, it is difficult for him to change his attitudes; he lacks the capacity to retain what he has learned. A recipient who is heavily transported, on the other hand, abandons everyday concerns and worries (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 325). Because of this, narratives serve as an escape from reality or a pleasurable activity for many individuals (Oatley, 2002, p. 43). Text content can be processed unencumbered, and persuasion can occur if the reader is so engrossed that he freely and deliberately loses himself in the world of the text.

Not every recipient is transported with equal force (Dal Cin et al., 2004, p. 186). According to Green and Brock, imagination, absorption, and emotion, coupled with historical knowledge, are the determining variables for transportation (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 326-327, Mazzocco et al., 2010, p. 361). According to their concept, persuasion is proportionate to transportation (Green and Brock, 2002, p. 316).

2.6.4.2 Extended-Elaboration-Likelihood-Model

The Extended-Elaboration-Likelihood-Model (E-ELM) was developed by Slater and Rouner (2002) to explain the processes and mechanisms of the intended persuasive influence of fictional narratives used in entertainment-education interventions. Entertainment-Education (EE) is described as the strategic inclusion of educational messages within media entertainment content "in order to increase audience members' knowledge about an educational issue, create favourable attitudes, shift social norms, and change over behaviour" (Singhal and Rogers, 2004, p. 5). Entertainment-Education, which was initially utilised primarily as a communication strategy in development aid, is now being implemented all over the world. Messages are frequently related to health or social issues, such as stigmatisation or intergroup disputes. Their incorporation occurs mostly in the plots of narrative media such as television programmes and radio plays (Singhal et al., 2013). Bandura's socio-

cognitive theory (Bandura, 1986, Bandura, 2009), whose primary concept is model-based learning, is the predominant theoretical underpinning for assumptions about the EE method. Bandura (Bandura, 2004) identified the following features of role models as influential elements in the success of observational learning:

1. their appeal or possibility for identification for receivers,
2. their status as an ideal role model, negative example, or transitional role model shifts from negative to positive during the action., and
3. their success or failure, in the form of direct consequences on behaviour and in relation to the subsequent course of action, as positive or negative amplifying factors of behaviour.

Despite the undeniable general success of EE interventions in influencing attitudes and behaviour (Singhal et al., 2013), there is more than enough need for investigation into the specific effects of specific content predicted by social cognitive theory, such as a transitional character or the positive or negative reinforcement of certain behaviours through action on behaviour or self-efficacy (Pajares et al., 2009). Slater and Rouner (Slater and Rouner, 2002a) further demonstrate that social cognitive theory is pertinent but insufficient for explaining the impacts of EE signals. Rather, it is required to go beyond the study of observational learning of behaviour and examine pre-existing influences on the beliefs and attitudes of the recipients, which can precede potential behaviour changes. Slater and Rouner (2002) place special emphasis on the examination and explanation of how the processing of persuasive content in narratives affects the effect. They adapt the Elaboration Likelihood Model (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986a, Petty and Wegener, 1999), which models these processing processes during the reception of non-narrative persuasive messages, to the setting of narrative persuasion and entertainment-education material (Slater and Rouner, 2002a).

The E-ELM created for this purpose by the two writers is based on the original ELM but differs greatly from it. While in ELM, a recipient's attention to a message and how he or she processes it depends on the respective topic involvement, narratives have a larger selection potential due to their inherent potential for enjoyment and their fairly undiluted persuasive goal. In addition, the amount of participation or drive to process for the recipient originates from the amount of his involvement with a narrative during the reception process. In E-ELM, exogenous factors, which also influence the attention and, most importantly, the depth of absorption, include the allure of the plot,

which may be, for instance, due to the genre, the quality of the narration, whether it be the performance of the actors or the writing style of the author, the subtlety of the persuasive content or intention, as well as the similarity of the recipients to the characters in this story or even homophilia. Consequently, theme involvement as a major variable loses its significance in the ELM in the context of narrative persuasion, but will be relevant in the E-ELM through absorption in the narrative and identification with the characters (Slater and Rouner, 2002a). Absorption is described as "the degree to which a message recipient is cognitively and affectively invested in a narrative" (Slater and Rouner, 2002a, p. 179) therefore, the extent of persuasion through a narrative depends on the extent of absorption. According to the authors, the phrases "absorption", "conveyance", and "commitment" all describe the same phenomena. In the E-ELM, Slater and Rouner (2002) disregard the distinction between central and peripheral processing because the strength of the persuasive effect depends entirely on the degree of absorption. Similar to Green and Brock (Green and Brock, 2000, Green and Brock, 2002), Slater and Rouner (2002) contend that intensive reception and processing of narratives prevents cognitive resistance to persuasive content or 'unbelief' (Gilbert, 1991) and that this mechanism is responsible for changes in attitudes. Fundamentally, absorption and counterargument are irreconcilable. Even if the compelling subtext of narration contradicts a recipient's notions, his transportation experience during reception will prohibit him from counterarguing (Slater and Rouner, 2002a). According to the authors, this is also the unique potential of narratives for entertainment-education interventions: They make resistant persons accessible and persuadable. In addition to absorption, the E-ELM's identification with a story's characters may play a role in the process of persuasion.

Changes in central route processing in ELM result in longer-lasting and more persistent attitude changes. This sustainability is subject to the persuasive effects of EE-messages, as they are frequently serialised and permit repeating or "rehearsal" of the messages. Discussions frequently follow the reception of EE content and allow for the repetition and social reinforcement of narrative ideas. These reinforcement opportunities play a crucial moderator role in the E-ELM, enhancing and stabilising attitude and behaviour modifications.

In their Extended-Elaboration-Likelihood-Model, Slater and Rouner (2002) systematically modify the correlations presented in the Elaboration-Likelihood-Model for persuasion by Entertainment-Education materials and integrate socio-cognitive

theory-based theoretical concerns on EE. In addition to the cause-and-effect relationships beyond transportation and reduced negative cognitions, the authors of the E-ELM also attribute impact-relevant influences to perception or relationship with characters and social reinforcement through discussions outside of reception.

2.6.4.3 Entertainment-Overcoming-Resistance-Model

In the entertainment overcoming resistance model, Moyer-Gusé (Moyer-Gusé, 2008) not only incorporates assumptions from social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1986, Bandura, 2009) and the extended laboratory likelihood model (Slater, 2002a), but also distinguishes between various related constructs of relationship with the characters of a story and their specific potentials for narrative persuasion. In addition to the lowering of counterargumentation, she models the elimination or avoidance of additional forms of cognitive resistance to persuasion influences. Her objective is also to understand the persuasive impact of Entertainment-Education-Narratives on the attitudes and actions of recipients.

Moyer-Gusé (Moyer-Gusé, 2008) likewise locates the core impact potential of prosocial stories in the immersive experience they offer their listeners, specifically in the different ways of experiencing a story and its characters. Regarding immersion in a story, i.e., the predominant to complete shifting of mental focus from the immediate environment or reality to the events in a story, the author acknowledges the existence of different terms for the same phenomenon, such as absorption, immersion, commitment, or submersion, but chooses the term transportation due to its widespread use - at least in the context of narrative persuasion (Green and Brock, 2000, Green and Brock, 2002). Moyer-Gusé (Moyer-Gusé, 2008) presents and contrasts five differing but related notions of viewer connection with the characters to find potential specific impacts in lowering cognitive resistance within the framework of the relationship with the characters. Identification, wishful Identification, perceived likeness, parasocial contact, and liking are only mentioned in this round.

In the Entertainment-Overcoming-Resistance-Model Moyer-Gusé (Moyer-Gusé, 2008) combines assumptions about the effects of social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1986, Bandura, 2009) and the Extended-Elaboration-Likelihood-Model (Slater, 2002a) and adds her own suggestions for the modelling of the decrease of various forms of resistance to changes in attitudes and behaviour through the distinctive influences of the many forms of experiencing narratives. She complements the

counterarguing already integrated in the Transportation Imagery Model (Green and Brock, 2002) and E-ELM (Slater, 2002a) with six further forms of resistance to persuasion attempts and psychological barriers to changes in attitudes and behaviour. Following Knowles and Linn (Knowles and Linn, 2004), she describes resistance as a perceived rejection of change in reaction to pressure to accept or implement that change. Reactance is one of the most famous manifestations of such resistance (Brehm, 1966, Brehm and Brehm, 2013). Psychological reactance is sometimes cited as a reason or explanation for why a specific persuasive message or campaign failed or even elicited undesirable, opposite effects, known as boomerang effects (Dillard and Shen, 2005, Quick et al., 2013). Perceived persuasive intent or manipulation is a catalyst for reactivity.(Quick et al., 2013). This perception of persuasive intent is typically absent in narrative persuasion.

However, prior to reception, viewers can protect themselves against persuasive messages by avoiding them in the first place. This phenomena of selective attention or avoidance ('selective exposure') is studied extensively in the framework of cognitive dissonance theory (Festinger, 1957). Festinger (1957) hypothesises that people attempt to avoid cognitive dissonance in the form of contradicting beliefs. Accordingly, one viable method is to focus on material that is congruent with their views and beliefs. and the avoidance of content that is inconsistent. According to Moyer-Gusé (2008), narratives have the ability to prevent the avoidance of nervous content because they place it in a framework that serves primarily as entertainment, thus rendering it less dangerous. The results of the research on enjoyment (Shafer and Raney, 2012, Bartsch et al., 2008) and appreciation (Wirth et al., 2012, Oliver and Bartsch, 2010) support this argument, as they demonstrate that recipients are willing to experience intense negative emotions in exchange for an overall positive reception experience. Thus, Moyer-Gusé (2008) hypothesises that the entertainment potential associated with narrative reception can outweigh the avoidance of anxiety-inducing content.

Moyer-Gusé (2008) extends the positive influences already postulated in the social cognitive theory (Bandura, 2009) of perceived similarity on self-efficacy, as well as perceived similarity and wish identification on the motivational effect of reinforcing and inhibiting consequences of behaviour, by adding assumptions on two additional frequent barriers, perceived invulnerability and perceived norms. People are vulnerable to a so-called optimistic bias with regard to their own perceived vulnerability or perceived susceptibility, i.e., they tend to underestimate the negative

repercussions that dangerous behaviour can have for themselves (Weinstein, 2003, Weinstein and Klein, 1996). Here, entertainment-education narratives can intervene, according to Moyer-Gusé (2008), since they can raise perceived vulnerability through perceived likeness to characters and identification with those portrayed as being at risk.

An additional barrier to changing attitudes and behaviours may be the perception of the accompanying social norms, specifically the legitimization of prejudices or risky behaviour through (false) assumptions about their prevalence and broad acceptance (Lapinski and Rimal, 2005, Rimal and Real, 2003). Again, a narrative's relationship to its characters has the capacity to remedy this misunderstanding, often known as the "false consensus effect" (Marks and Miller, 1987). Consequently, persons with whom recipients connect or maintain a parasocial relationship and whom they respect and trust may also serve as a reference for social standards (Moyer-Gusé, 2008). Furthermore, Moyer-Gusé (2008) notes that it is an important prerequisite for immersion in narratives that they are not perceived as persuasive. It is also possible that different types of resistance can impede other action mechanisms, i.e. they interact.

The merit of Moyer-Gusé's (2008) Entertainment-Overcoming-Resistance model resides in the systematisation of many sorts of experiencing narrations and the modelling of the lowering of various types of relevant resistance to narrative effects by these narrative forms.

Figure 17 Entertainment Overcoming Resistance Model based on Moyer-Gusé (2008), p. 415

2.6.4.4 Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement

The Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement is developed by Busselle and Bilandzic (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008) as a theoretical framework for connecting theoretical models of narrative processing with approaches to narrative persuasion research. Their objective is to explain the creation of immersive experiences during the reception of narratives, with a focus on the involvement of various forms of perceived realism.

Figure 18 Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement based on Busselle and Bilandzic (2008), p. 272

Busselle and Bilandzic (2008) distinguish between three mental models pertinent to the comprehension of narration: the situation model, the story world model, and the character model. This distinction is more analytical in nature, as the three models interact naturally during the narrative processing procedure. The situation model is the most significant of the three types (Van Dijk and Kintsch, 1983). It is continuously updated during reception by comparing and combining incoming information with the existing situation model (Zwaan et al., 1995). In doing so, the viewer accesses his or her own schemata (see chapter 2.1.3) and scripts, i.e., existing knowledge frameworks for both the real world and narrations or genre conventions, in order to interpret and classify developments in a narrative, as well as to generate expectations or predictions about their progression (Graesser et al., 2002).

In contrast, the model of the story world is a relatively static representation of a story's setting and logic (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008). The 'storyworld logic' (Segal, 1995) consists of the rules and limitations to which a story's characters and events are subjected. Standard procedure is to begin with the realities of the real world, unless its laws have already been suspended, as in genre conventions. Although the model of the story world is essential to the comprehension of a narrative, it frequently recedes into the background during processing and only resurfaces when one of the rules is broken (without explanation) (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008).

The concept of flow developed by Csikszentmihalyi (Csikszentmihalyi, 1990, Csikszentmihalyi, 2020) describes the pleasurable, optimal state of high concentration and complete merging into a seemingly effortless activity that neither under- nor overstrains the performer, but achieves the optimal balance between the demands and the performer's abilities. Green and Brock (2002) had previously identified parallels between the ideas of transportation and flow. Both are pleasurable sensations of total immersion, characterised by a loss of self-awareness and time perception. However, they did not follow the implications further, noting that it may be pertinent to examine the impact of a text's complexity or difficulty on transportation in the future. If the narrative is too branchy or if there are too many interruptions due to new characters that do not match the plot or if the activities take on unrealistic characteristics, the recipient cannot get into the flow of the narrative. But Busselle and Bilandzic (2008) also identified a distinctive characteristic of the flow experience with narrations that distinguishes it from other flow activities: the required psychological shift of one's own experience's frame of reference into the story world. The authors employ Deictic-Shift Theory to describe this transformation (Duchan et al., 1995). Through the psychological shift of perception into the narrative, the recipient's experience attains a closeness and immediacy that, the more it demands the cognitive resources of the recipient and causes it to abandon itself and its original reality, contributes to the intense experiential nature of the state of transportation. If this transition occurs from my perspective to the perspective of a character whose eyes I observe the events through, this is already the essential prerequisite for identification (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008). Thus, according to Busselle and Bilandzic (2008), the Deictic Shift Theory can also explain aspects of the phenomenology of transportation and identification. Busselle and Bilandzic (2008) identify a significant aspect in the establishment of perceived reality that disturbs or interrupts the immersive "Narrative

Engagement". They first distinguish between three distinct sorts of narrative proximity to reality that recipients can perceive:

- (1) Fictionality - as a work category of reality correspondence (Nickel-Bacon et al., 2000, Rothmund et al., 2001),
- (2) External realism - as closeness to reality considering genre standards, and
- (3) Narrative realism - as a story's internal consistency (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008).

The authors suggest that the fictionality of a narrative is in no way decisive for the reception experience and that viewers perceive figures and events in a narrative in the same way as they perceive people and events in their everyday lives.

Busselle and Bilandzic (2008) conceptualise fictionality similarly to Shapiro and Lang (1991) or Shrum (2009) as context information on narration and thus as part of the mental model of the story. It serves as an external indicator of a possible lack of correspondence to reality and, for instance, raises expectations for a genre-appropriate plot. The knowledge of a narration's fictionality is static and so does not need to be updated throughout reception (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008). Rather, it fades into the background, potentially to the point where it is forgotten and information from the narrative is mistakenly remembered as information about reality, i.e., the source is misattributed (Shrum, 2001, 2009). At the same time, though, knowledge of fictionality is available and can be triggered when necessary, for instance to comfort us that horror pictures are merely films (Kovakovich and Gendler, 2005). Fictionality as a work category of the correspondence to reality is therefore of little value to the reception experience, but functional, because it expands the boundaries of what is feasible for the story's world (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008).

In contrast to fictionality, the two authors view external and narrative realism as significant aspects affecting the reception experience. Even if the label of fictionality indicates the degree to which it matches reality, it is nevertheless conceivable for an audience to see a fictional narrative as "twice as true as fact" (Oatley, 1999, p. 103). Despite the lack of factuality, recipients can judge fictional stories, their events and characters as more or less real based on their similarity with external reality and their own experiences (Potter, 1988). It is generally assumed that the more convincing a media message is, the more real it is perceived to be (Busselle and Greenberg, 2000). In addition to exterior reality, storytelling itself can serve as a standard for assessing

realism. For narrative realism, it is significant and credible that the events, setting, or characters exist within the framework of the story's world and genre (see for relative realism Shapiro and Chock, 2003), coherence and consistency of the events and their clarity for the recipient (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008). Busselle and Bilandzic (2008) situate realism evaluations within the context of the development of mental models of a narrative. Only when contradictions are detected between the model of narration and the recipient's knowledge or experience (external realism) or between newly received information about the narrative and the already constructed mental model (narrative realism) is the smooth processing of the narrative disrupted and the (missing) realism made apparent. Whether these contradictions interrupt the reception process depends on how crucial they are to a story, how extensive they are, and, most importantly, whether they are explained within the narrative. Disturbing violations of both forms of perceived realism rip the reader from the story world, induce negative cognitions, which, according to the authors, are also a form of counter-argumentation, and ultimately, at least temporarily, diminish the reader's immersion in the narrative and their identification with the characters. (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008). In addition to these frequently particular judgments made during receipt, recipients can also construct a memory-based judgement about the realism of the entire narrative following reception, i.e., offline, into which the online judgments, of course, flow (Busselle and Greenberg, 2000). This in turn shows analogous connections with "Narrative Engagement" and identification (Bilandzic and Busselle, 2011).

Busselle and Bilandzic's (2008) "Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement" fills a critical theoretical void, which all previous models demonstrate. By defining transportation as a fluid experience that might emerge during the process of story comprehension elaboration, they provide the idea with a theoretical foundation that transcends its operationalized one. This permits a more systematic theoretical development and empirical validation of narrative persuasion mechanisms and the assumptions associated with intensive story experiences.

The factual equivalence of negative cognitions as counterargument and negative cognitions as a response to realism breaches is crucial. It is feasible, for instance, that realism breaches detract from the genuine counterargument against the persuasive substance of a narration, so enhancing its persuasive effects. Obviously, it is also feasible that reality violations are so pervasive that the negative reactions to them

prohibit any further confrontation with narration and, specifically, transportation. In this instance, the absence of narrative consequences would be the result of "realistic counterarguing." However, subsumption under classical counterargument appears premature. It would make more sense to employ a more differentiated conceptualization as opposed to several procedures, each of which can negate a persuasive effect.

Overall, the "Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement" is a strong example of theoretical development based on existing theoretical foundations, notwithstanding its flaws. It not only meaningfully complements the other models but also provides them with a more solid theoretical basis.

It should be emphasised that Busselle and Bilandzic have established their own scale to measure "Narrative Engagement," a critical component of their paradigm. The name of this verified and validated scale is the "Narrative Engageability Scale" (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2009). This scale is vital to this thesis since it serves as the foundation for the ensuing empirical research (chapter 3).

2.6.4.5 Schematic summary

The offered theoretical models complement one another rather well but share many commonalities. These commonalities will be examined and presented in accordance with their current research status.

2.6.4.5.1 The persuasive effect of narrations

In addition to studies that focus primarily on investigating the mechanisms of narrative persuasion (e.g. Cohen et al., 2015, Green and Donahue, 2011, Moyer-Gusé and Nabi, 2010), the effect of narratives has also been investigated in a wide variety of studies in different thematic research contexts such as health communication (e.g. Banerjee and Greene, 2012a, Dunlop et al., 2010, Kreuter et al., 2010), advertising communication (Zheng, 2014, Chang, 2013) or political communication (Shen et al., 2014, Landreville and LaMarre, 2011). Equally different are the types of impacts considered: therefore, the effects of narratives on recipients' attitudes (Johnson, 2013), behaviour (Strick et al., 2015), intentions (Barraza et al., 2015), beliefs (Niederdeppe et al., 2015) and knowledge (Fazio et al., 2015) were examined.

In the area of health communication, a meta-analysis of studies on the persuasive effect of entertainment-education material (Shen and Han, 2014) indicated a small

but significant persuasive effect of EE narratives on knowledge, attitudes, intentions, and actual behaviour. Four more meta-analyses (Allen and Preiss, 1997, Reinhart and Feeley, 2007, Shen et al., 2015, Zebregs et al., 2015) that examine the persuasive effect of narratives vs statistics messages offer a slightly conflicting picture. While Allen and Preiss (1997) reported a compelling advantage for statistical messaging, Reinhart and Feeley (2007) found no significant difference, Shen, Sheer and Lee (2015) found that narrative messages in the context of health communication were more persuasive than statistical messages. In the meta-analysis of Reinhart and Feeley (2007), the individual consideration of different dependent variables reveals a significantly stronger persuasive effect of narrations on attitudes, whereas the meta-analysis of Zebregs and others (2015) reveals a stronger effect of statistical messages on beliefs and attitudes and of narrations on intentions. In the context of health communication, Shen and colleagues (2015) discovered that story messages were more convincing than statistical ones in terms of attitudes, intentions, and behaviour. Despite the ambiguity of these meta-analyses, they indicate that narratives may have persuasive effects, sometimes stronger than statistical or non-narrative messages.

In general, the research findings (e.g. Frank et al., 2015, Kreuter et al., 2010, McQueen et al., 2011, Williams et al., 2011) suggest that narratives can also lead to long-term changes in knowledge, intentions, and behaviour beyond the immediate context of reception, even though only a one- to two-week period was examined here.

2.6.4.5.2 Mechanisms of effect

In their meta-analysis, Tukachinsky and Tokunaga (2013) examined the relationship between various constructs of experiencing narratives, such as perceived homophilia, parasocial interaction or relationships (PSI/PSR), identification, and transport, and various types of persuasive effects, such as knowledge, attitudes, and behaviour. There is a moderate association across all constructs; however, it is not uniform across all studied studies, exhibiting significant statistical variability and indicating the absence of moderating variables. In terms of output variables, the impacts of experience on behaviour are by far the most prominent, followed by similar effects on attitudes and knowledge. Among the many types of experience narrations, transportation and identification have the most persuasive effects, whereas perceived homophilia and PSI/PSR have the least persuasive effects.

Narrative Engagement and Transportation

In addition to the above-mentioned meta-analysis conducted by Tukachinsky and Tokunaga (2013), a meta-analysis carried out specifically for transportation (Van Laer et al., 2014) also revealed a medium persuasive effect of transportation on beliefs, attitudes and intentions as a whole, as well as individually for the various dependent variables. Despite this consistent association between “Narrative Engagement” and persuasive effects, which is visible in the vast majority of studies, there are a few instances where no correlation could be demonstrated. These include above all investigations on the effect of narrations on the recipients' knowledge, which was not affected by the distance travelled (e.g. Barriga et al., 2010, Dahlstrom, 2010, Dahlstrom, 2012, Jensen, 2011).

Overall, a moderately consistent relationship can be established between transportation, namely the dimensions of presence or absorption and emotional involvement in the story, and the effect variables. Moreover, the results indicate the existence of many moderator variables, such as default attitudes.

Identification

In addition to transportation as an intense immersion in the narrative, identification as the process of narrative persuasion is thought to be an intense empathy with the characters. The meta-analysis conducted by Tukachinsky and Tokunaga (2013) has already demonstrated that identification has a moderate effect on the recipients' knowledge, attitudes, and behaviour. Problematic in the context of identification studies are the different conceptualizations and operationalizations between the liking of the characters, the similarity with them or the desire to be so (Liking, Similarity, Wishful Identification) or even parasocial interaction on the one hand and, according to the definition of Cohen (2001), the immersive, cognitive and emotional adoption of a figure on the other hand (e.g. Cohen et al., 2015, Igartua and Barrios, 2012, Moyer-Gusé and Nabi, 2010).

Similar to transportation, only a few research cannot establish a correlation between identification and knowledge (e.g. Jensen et al., 2011) or a mediation connection between identification and attitudes (e.g. Hoeken and Sinkeldam, 2014). Various studies also indicate that the persuasive effect of identification or moderating variables may have limitations. In the study by Chung and Slater (2013), for instance, adopting the perspective of a more stigmatised figure (a drug addict) had a smaller

impact on the social acceptance of the corresponding group of people than adopting the perspective of a less stigmatised person (a single mother). Recipients connect with characters who share their perspective more strongly than those with opposing views, and identification with characters with discordant attitudes produces fewer impacts than identification with those with harmonious attitudes (e.g. Cohen et al., 2015, Hoeken and Fikkers, 2014).

Transportation versus Identification

The theoretical premise and empirical results of the two concepts, transportation and identification, share numerous similarities. Both are characterised by a loss of sense of reality outside the narrative and of one's own self due to complete immersion in the narrative (Cohen, 2001, Green and Brock, 2000). "Both involve a loss of awareness of the viewing situation and a shift in identity" (Tal-Or and Cohen, 2010, p. 404). Additionally, both emotions impact storytelling. In Transportation, however, the attention is on the full story, its characters, and events, and no specifics are provided. Identification, in contrast, focuses exclusively on a single individual. Both notions share a substantial amount of variance, which is reflected in their highly correlated empirical settings (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2009). This begs the question of whether they are in fact two independent notions, each having their own research value. Tal-Or and Cohen (2010) devoted themselves to solving this question, and their findings indicate that these are two separate conceptions. First, in a factor analysis, the items for measuring both constructs demonstrated a clear split based on whether they belonged to transportation or identification. Second, the authors were able to demonstrate that transportation and identification can be manipulated independently of one another: While the valence of an action of the protagonist of a story that a recipient receives before seeing affects identification with the protagonist but not transportation, the manipulation of the point in time of this action, i.e., whether it is already in the past or still in the future, has the exact opposite effect. The participants in the study were more immersed in the story when more information about a future action was provided than when more information was provided about a past activity. In contrast, their degree of identification with the protagonist was identical. This independent modification of transportation and identification could be reproduced in additional research. (e.g. Cohen et al., 2015). McKinley's (2013) study results give very compelling evidence for the distinction between the two "Narrative Engagement", as transportation and identification demonstrate opposite substantial cause-and-

effect relationships: Transportation increases perceived vulnerability to the negative effects of excessive alcohol use, as well as expectations of bad outcomes. In contrast, identifying with the protagonist has the unexpectedly negative effect of reducing susceptibility and lowering anticipation of unfavourable outcomes. These results, which contradict McKinley's (2013) original hypothesis, are most likely attributable to the protagonist. In contrast to the majority of research, this was a negative role model that did not undergo any character development, i.e., the protagonist suffers from the negative repercussions of excessive alcohol intake, but neither expresses sorrow for his behaviour nor plans to change it. Consequently, it is probable that a greater identification with this negative role model results in unfavourable outcomes.

In conclusion, the refereed studies support the conceptualization of transportation and identification as two distinct forms of immersive experience of narrations, which, while sharing common interfaces and common variance in many contexts, differ in their persuasive effects in specific contexts such as content, structural features (e.g., emphasis on plot versus characters), and contexts.

Critical cognitions: Counterarguing

The persuasive power of transportation and identification resides in the diverse theoretical approaches to narrative persuasion, particularly in the decrease of counterargument connected with these reception processes. In their meta-analysis, Van Laer and colleagues (2014) discovered a substantial negative correlation between critical cognitions and transportation and a significant positive correlation between narrative cognitions, defined as thoughts on narrative structure, and transportation. Even when specifically requested to do so, several studies indicate that transported readers are less likely to identify errors and factually contradicting information in a story (Green and Brock, 2000, Marsh and Fazio, 2006). Moyer-Gusé et al. (2011) discovered a negative correlation between identification and counterargumentation. The statistical evidence of (partial) mediation, i.e., that diminished counterargumentation transfers the persuasive effect of transportation or identification on attitudes and intentions, was also presented, albeit in a relatively small number of research (Banerjee and Greene, 2012b, Banerjee and Greene, 2013, Escalas, 2004, Moyer-Gusé et al., 2011).

Evidence supports the consensus prevailing in the research discourse (Green and Brock, 2000, Green and Brock, 2002, Slater and Rouner, 2002a) on missing or reduced counterarguing as a mediating mechanism between transport and effects.

Evidence supports the consensus prevailing in the research discourse (Green and Brock, 2000, Green and Brock, 2002, Slater and Rouner, 2002a) on missing or reduced counterarguing as a mediating mechanism between transport and effects. However, the research situation is far more complex. For instance, Dunlop and colleagues (2010) discovered a negative association between transportation and negative cognitions; yet, negative cognitions had no impact on attitudes and behavioural intentions; they did not mediate the persuasive effect of transportation. It was somewhat mediated by the extent of self-referencing (Dunlop et al., 2010). Igartua (2010) found that identification is associated with greater overall elaboration, regardless of the polarity of thoughts. In other research, transportation and counterargumentation also work separately. While in Mazzocco and colleagues (2010) transportation and valence of thoughts show no correlation, but both are parallel significant predictors of attitudes, in Shen and others (2014) only cognitive reactions and empathy, but not transportation, mediate the persuasive effect of a story.

Specifically, the results that demonstrate a favourable link between mobility and counterarguing raise questions (Moyer-Gusé and Nabi, 2010). Moyer-Gusé and Nabi (2010) consider both operationalization and theoretical modelling as potential causes for this conclusion. On the one hand, the inquiry with closed scale items is insufficiently particular to capture the relationship between the counterargument and the content, i.e., if persuasive material, realism, or character actions have been questioned. On the theory side, however, the question arises as to whether the suppression of critical cognitions is as important to the persuasive effect of transportation as other mechanisms, such as self-referencing.

Perceived Realism

Perceived realism is another characteristic claimed to explain the persuasive effect. It is commonly believed that greater realism supports the impact of storytelling (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008, Busselle and Greenberg, 2000, Cho et al., 2014). Consequently, numerous research have demonstrated a positive correlation between realism and transportation (e.g. Bilandzic and Busselle, 2011, Busselle et al., 2004, Caputo and Rouner, 2011). Unfavourable association was observed with negative thoughts (Busselle et al., 2004, Wilson and Busselle, 2004). However, it is not entirely obvious to what extent realism perceptions and the two forms of immersive experience are interdependent. While, for instance, McKinley (2013) identified

perceived realism as a mediator of the effects of transportation, Green's (2004) study did not confirm this, other studies demonstrated that higher realism is conducive to transportation and identification and indirectly influences the attitudes of the recipients through this (e.g. Bilandzic et al., 2012, Cho et al., 2014, Shapiro et al., 2010). Cho and others (2014) were able to distinguish between the distinct effects of various levels of realism. The perceived typicality of events and characters, i.e., the degree to which they may also exist in reality, is the strongest predictor of the realism aspects for identification but has no effect on emotional engagement with the story. On the other hand, the plausibility of a narrative, i.e., the extent to which the action is credible within the world of a story, and its perceptive quality have the greatest effect on emotional participation, whereby the two dimensions of plausibility and narrative consistency, i.e., the extent to which the events and actions of the characters are consistent, promote emotional participation exclusively. (Cho et al., 2014). In general, the given research results indicate that narrative realism has a larger association with transportation, whereas external realism has a stronger correlation with identification. It is probably safe to infer that perceptions of transportation or identification and realism can be mutually reliant during reception, so that high realism can both improve immersive experience and lead to a greater realism perception. The extent to which a certain causal direction predominates in a given situation and how this impacts the persuasive effects of narration depends on a number of narrative aspects, including the realism and experience involved, the recipients, and the effects under consideration.

Reactance

High identification and transport should, according to theoretical models, preclude or at least limit the formation of reactance (Moyer-Gusé, 2008). A number of research have confirmed the negative link between transportation costs and (Keer et al., 2013, Kim et al., 2011, Reinhart and Anker, 2012, Stitt and Nabi, 2005). Shen (2010) identified this as evidence. They have a favourable effect on attitudes, intentions, and message evaluations by lowering reactivity to transportation and identification (Reinhart and Anker, 2012, Shen, 2010). As expected, there is a positive correlation between reactance and counterarguing (Moyer-Gusé et al., 2012, Moyer-Gusé and Nabi, 2010). Particularly, an explicit persuasive goal of narrative might produce reactance and have a detrimental effect on the participants' intents (Moyer-Gusé and

Nabi, 2010). Regarding the lowering of reactance during transit and identification, a trend consistent with the theoretical assumptions can be observed.

2.7 Literature overview for success factors of Storytelling

In this part, it will be determined to what extent a research deficit on the topic of narrative persuasion (storytelling) in commercials (mini-films) and their design exists in the scientific community (success factors). Scopus, the largest scientific database including publications that have been peer-reviewed, was queried to find relevant scientific articles. These search terms were utilised for this analysis:

- “Viral Marketing” AND Storytelling
- “Success factors” AND Storytelling
- “Mini-films” AND Marketing
- “Narrative Persuaion” AND Marketing

The search results were then limited to the previous ten years. This yields a search period spanning 2010 to 2020. The result was then further filtered by journal articles. Finally, these results were individually analysed to determine whether the abstracts suggested that they addressed any of the themes pertinent to this study:

- Examining the **effect** of narrative persuasion in social media
- Research on relevant **components** (success factors) in the field of mini-films and videos under the aspect of Narrative Persuasion

Table 3 Breakdown literature overview selection process

Search String	“Viral Marketing” AND Storytelling	“Success factors” AND Storytelling	“Mini-films” AND Marketing	“Narrative Persuaion” AND Marketing
Overall results	130	539	36	558
Year 2010-2020 results	120	466	33	496
Journal results	76	307	28	426
Relevant results	5	2	7	36

Relevant results are assigned to the two categories "effect" and "components" as follows (due to search overlaps, the sum of the search does not equal the entire amount distributed):

Table 4 Relevant literature to be evaluated

	Effect	Components (success factors)
Relevant results	19	18

2.7.1 Literature overview Effect

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Tabassum et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Structured questionnaire • No statement regarding research design • 304 respondents • Age from under 18 to 23 	No model mentioned	Covariance-based SEM	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrative advertisement positively influences the purchase intention of Generation Z • Narrative advertisement positively influences the eWOM of Generation Z
Lee and Jahng (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pretest for stimulus material • 132 Participants • Mean age 21,35 and mainly female • 2 (Storytelling: Present Vs. Not-Present) x 2 (Locus of Control: Internal Vs. External) • Reading of CEO response letters to a crisis 	Narrative Engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008)	ANOVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Storytelling crisis response increased trust toward the organization and reduced the perception of crisis responsibility compared with a response without a storytelling
Ratcliff and Sun (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meta-Analytic Review 	-	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exposure to narrative messages, compared to nonnarrative messages, generated less resistance • Less resistance associated with greater narrative engagement

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Huang and Waddell (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 113 participants • Mainly female • Mean age 20,42 years • A 2 (high transportation vs. low transportation) x 2 (ad customization: choice vs. no choice) between-subjects experiment was conducted in a computer lab with created online video sites 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	MANCOVA and ANCOVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No main effects of ad customization and transportation on brand attitude
Kang et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 300 participants • Mean age 38,8 • Showing the participants three different own created commercials (2 Storytelling and 1 informative) • Subsequent questionnaire 	Emotion, Narrative Transportation, Narrative Preference, Identification	Hierarchical Regression Analysis, ANOVA and MANCOVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Verification of the key concepts in processing a narrative such as transportation and identification still determine the storytelling advertising effect in a commercial context just as they worked in a narrative-based public service announcement • The study adds empirical evidence to the claim that narrative in storytelling advertising improves branding and promotional efforts • The more participants imagined themselves in the scene of the story (transportation), the more likely they were to perceive the ad as creative, touching, and meaningful • The study found that emotion played a crucial role in motivating individuals to talk about the ads (WOM),

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Anaza et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 229 participants • 63% male • Mean age 43 • Decision makers and C-Level managers • Experiment with video watching and subsequent questionnaire • Second study with qualitative interview research 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	Covariance-based structural model	<p>which is consistent with previous research findings in narrative persuasion literature</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumers are more likely to be persuaded by affective outcomes rather than by strong arguments from the information provided in an ad • Additional statistical analysis indicated that women were more likely to have positive emotions toward a founder's story compared to a customer's story or the informational advertising <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results highlight that transportation into stories has the potential to result in positive attitudinal responses in the form of trust, personal connection and advocacy for the decision maker • Finding compelling evidence that C-level executives who are transported show greater relational tendencies than non-C-level executives • C-level executives experience higher tendencies to advocate for the supplier post narrative transportation • C-level executives do see value in story-based advertisements • C-level executives were open to being transported into stories

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
SULESTARINI et al. (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 100 respondents • 77% female • Experiment with mini-film advertising watching • Respondents have watched a entire series of nine videos from a brand who wants to sell a artificial sweetener 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	PLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrative transportation led to a favorable attitude toward the web series and the brand, which then led to purchase intention
Ha et al. (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 467 participants • Mean age 36,07 years • Mainly female • 2 (message type: narrative vs. nonnarrative) x 3 (social exclusion experience: socially rejected vs. socially ignored vs. control) • Text reading 	Narrative Engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008)	MANCOVA and ANCOVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No overall advantage of the narrative vs. nonnarrative message in generating communicative behaviours and civic behaviours • There were significant indirect effects through transportation and affective empathy on all outcome variables
Finkler and Leon (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1698 respondents • From all over the world • Mean age 29-55 years • Highly educated • Questionnaire after watching a storytelling commercial 	Berger and Milkman (2012b) SUCCESS formula	No statement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional storytelling video for a science topic, designed after the SUCCESS formula, effect a attitude change

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Huang et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 192 participants • Mean age 32 years • Exploring of Instagram accounts of two luxury brand hotel chains • Experiment with subsequent questioning 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	MANOVA and Structural equation modeling (SEM) with maximum likelihood estimation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrative stories on social media pages engage participants in imagery processing • Triggering of Narrative Transportation via: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ comprehension and imagery fluency, both of which are message giver factors ○ transportability, a message receiver factor
Dessart (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 127 participants • Ages from 17 to 26 • Video ads from YouTube • Subsequent questionnaire regarding the video and the brand • Two studies to confirm the findings of the first study • In the second study the stimulus material was exchanged • Third study to examine the role of the character in depth 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	Serial mediation analysis and two way ANOVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evidence that ads that tell a story exert a positive impact on narrative transportation compared to ads that do not tell a story • What the results also indicate is that when an ad tells a story, narrative transportation and identification serve as mechanisms that make a storytelling ad exert a less positive effect on brand attitude • The results show that when an ad is framed as telling a story, narrative transportation is increased and leads to lower identification with the character, ultimately having a less positive effect on brand attitude • No main effect of character type or any interaction between the conditions of ad framing (storytelling versus factual) and character type (human versus animal) on perception of the ad as a story

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Chen and Chang (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Study 1: • 347 participants • Mostly between 18 and 23 years old • Film watching with subsequent questionnaire regarding product involvement and attitude forward advertising • Study 2: • 123 participants • Mean age of 19,24 • 15 films watched (13 normal ads and 2 storytelling ads) with subsequent questionnaire regarding product involvement and attitude forward advertising 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	Multiple regression analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Both studies demonstrated that transportation is the best predictor of changes in the attitude and behaviour of narrative persuasion • Consumers may be more likely to be immersed or absorbed into the fictional worlds constructed by the mini-films and receive the brand messages conveyed • The results demonstrated that product involvement, pre-existing brand attitude, and attitude toward advertising in some cases influence brand attitudes or purchase intentions
Tseng and Huang (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 431 participants • 60% female and 40%male • Experiment with randomly assign participants to different narrative advertisings videos • Subsequent questionnaire 	The narrative theory (Polkinghorne, 1991) and high/low flow narrator advertising video (Hatfield et al., 1993)	Partial Least Square (PLS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In comparison to argument advertising, narrative advertising is more likely to trigger emotional response • Narrative advertising is more likely to enable the audience to share the same emotional state as the narrator • Compared with internet narrative advertising video, internet narrator advertising video with an emotionally invested high-flow narrator can strengthen online

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
				audience intention to adopt risk-reducing behaviours more directly and positively
Chen (2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 913 participants • 348 male and 565 female • Experiment with subsequent questioning • 10 Commercial mini films • Measuring the influence of transportation towards brand attitude and purchase intention 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	Structural equation modeling (SEM) LISREL and ANOVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Transportation shows a significant influence on the brand attitude and purchase intention • A SEM analysis of the study reveals that attitude toward the film played a full mediating role between transportation effect and brand attitude
Brechman and Purvis (2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 239 participants • Equal male to female • Mean age 45,25 • Questionnaire after the Super Bowl regarding transportation of the ads 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	Multilevel models	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Individuals with a disposition towards being transported demonstrate more positive attitudes towards advertising in general • Individuals with a higher dispositional likelihood of becoming transported show significantly higher levels of ad recall than individuals that are less likely to become transported • Narrativity did not negatively impact viewers' brand awareness
Shen et al. (2015)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meta Analytic Review 	-	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Across all studies, narratives exerted a small but significant effect on persuasion • When the persuasion items were examined separately, narratives had similarly small effects on attitudes, intentions and behaviours

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Van Laer et al. (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Meta Analytic Review 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	-	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The effect of narrative transportation on affective responses is especially large • Narrative transportation also leads to less critical thoughts
Chen and Lee (2014)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 913 participants • Mainly female • Watching one out of ten Mini-Film commercials • Subsequent questionnaire 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	LISREL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This study shows that the transportation effect is an important factor influencing Mini-Film Advertising (MFA) forwarding intention • Enjoyment is an indispensable mediating variable that is correlated highly with the transportation effect and has a strong effect on advertisement attitude and forwarding intention • It is assumed that consumers absorbed in the narrative world of MFA experience positive emotions and form positive attitudes toward both the advertisement and the brand

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Lundqvist et al. (2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative Research • 40 participants • Half of them got faced with reading a narrative story and seeing a narrative slidedeck of a cosmetic brand • The other half was not faced to any narrative stimulus material • Afterwards testing of the product with subsequent interview 	No information given	No information given	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study demonstrates that a well-crafted story may create positive associations with a brand and ultimately increase consumers' willingness to pay for it • The story did indeed create high quality expectations, based on genuine values, which, is one of the most important aspects of stories • The story had a filtering effect, changing the evaluation of the brand, raising its value

All research undertaken indicate that narratives have a favourable effect on the audience's attitude in the context of advertising: The research by Shen et al. (2015), Chen and Chang (2017), Finkler and Leon (2019), Tabassum et al. (2020) demonstrates a favourable impact on the influence itself. The studies of Chen and Lee (2014), Van Laer et al. (2014), Brechman and Purvis (2015), Chen (2015), Chen and Chang (2017), Dessart (2018), Huang et al. (2018), SULESTARINI et al. (2020), Anaza et al. (2020), Kang et al. (2020) show that a transportative effect is caused by narratives. Notable in this regard is the study Kang et al. (2020), which demonstrates that transportation and identification are measurable indicators for determining the effectiveness of an advertisement. Consequently, the concept of pure narrative storytelling can also be applied to the world of marketing. In addition, the more viewers' ability to become immersed in an advertisement, the more desirable they found it (transportation). In their study, Chen and Chang (2017) conclude that transportation is the best predictor of attitude change and future behaviour. This was the conclusion of two studies. They specifically contrasted storytelling advertisements with traditional advertisements. Only a small number of studies have measured little or almost no meaningful impacts. These studies were published by Ha et al. (2019) and Huang and Waddell (2020).

2.7.2 Literature overview Components (Success factors)

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Tiede and Appel (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two experiments with presenting reviews for films to participants and subsequent watching of the film Subsequent questionnaire First experiment 100 participants Second experiment 167 participants 	Narrative Engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008) and Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	ANOVA and PROCESS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The effect of reviews on transportation is mediated by recipients' expectations towards the movie This study did not support a hypothesis that reviews affect narrative presence and emotional engagement, rather than attentional focus and narrative understanding
Karpinska-Krakowiak and Eisend (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two experiments exposing mini-films to participants Mini-films had either lecture or drama content Experiment one all mini-films from car manufacturer Experiment one 441 participants Experiment two different brands and product categories and 2 (drama: high vs. low) x 2 (lecture: high vs. low) factorial design Experiment two 234 participants 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000) and Similarity–identification model (Slater and Rouner, 2002a)	ANOVA and PROCESS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mini-film advertising with both drama and lecture can be as effective as MA Mini-film advertising lecture These effects can be explained by the similarity–identification process, which serves as a viable alternative to the concept traditionally applied in research on narrative advertising, i.e. transportation The similarity–identification process explains the effects of drama combined with lecture on digital brand engagement better than the transportation model Drama components seem to be effective if no factual information is included The combination of drama and lecture, however, leads to effects similar to those for mere dramabased narratives

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Li and Liu (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 289 participants • Mainly female • Experiment with first watching a micro-movie and afterwards answering a questionnaire 	Empathy (Escalas, 2004)	PLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results showed that a tourism micro-movie's story content had a positive effect on empathy and persuasion • Empathy had a significant and positive effect on persuasion
Rodgers and Stemmler (2020)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Analysis of health videos and texts and their characteristics in terms of success through the metrics of number of views, number of likes and number of comments 	Framework from De Graaf et al. (2016)	Chi-squared tests	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • For story structures, high incidence was found of first-person stories told in chronological order as compared to nonchronological, third-person stories • Within dramatic features, higher presence of emotional appeals as compared to vivid examples was identified • Within behavioural mobilization, higher presence on calls to action and lesser reliance on referrals to resources and personal mobilization were also seen • Greater versatility was shown in text versus video modalities

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Dessart and Pitardi (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Qualitative research Four Dove Channels on YouTube in four different languages Analysis of the comments from mainly four different Storytelling videos 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000), Storyline (Escalas, 2004) and Customer Engagement (Hollebeek, 2011)	Netnography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The plot seems to prompt more cognition-based engagement, which was showed by viewers' level of concentration on and attention to the message conveyed by the branded story content and by the numerous comments bearing on the explanation of the ad message Characters were able to perform an emotional transfer from the story to the viewers, allowing them to feel sentiments and moods The degree of verisimilitude perceived by the viewers seems to result in more cognitive and behavioural reactions
Bartsch and Kloß (2019)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 150 participants Mainly female Experiment watching a personalized spot vs. non-personalized Subsequent questionnaire 	Involvement (Petty et al., 2002), Reactance (Dillard and Shen, 2005) and Empathy (Eisenberg et al., 1998)	Structure Equation model with AMOS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personalization showed no significant direct effect on prosocial outcomes The results supported the assumption that self-referencing and empathy are important mediating factors that contribute to positive effects of personalized charity advertisements on prosocial outcomes These positive effects were qualified by a direct effect of personalization on reactance

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Van Laer et al. (2019)	Investigation of moderating factors for Narrative Transportation	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000), Being Hooked (Escalas et al., 2004), Mysticism (Hood Jr, 1975) and Narrative Engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008)	Meta Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Narrative transportation effect is greater when <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ The story pertains to a commercial domain ○ amateur users are engaged in the story production, ○ the story-receiver interprets the story alone, which living in a digital world and one-to-one marketing tools foster
Van Laer et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documentary film regarding Narrative Transportation • Interview in the film with 55 participants 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	Interviews	<p>Relevant video characteristics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifiable characters • Imaginable plot • Climax • Key takeaway or moral
Yeo et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 347 participants • Mainly female • Experiment of watching a documentary • Subsequent questionnaire 	Theory of the immediately proximal causes of volitional behaviour (Eagly and Chaiken, 1993)	Correlation and PROCESS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results of the experiment suggest that some authoritative sources — compared to anonymous narrators — can have a significant impact on behavioural intentions • No significant difference between the scientist and politician narrator • The research implies that negative affect can encourage people to exchange information

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Su et al. (2018)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 316 participants • Mean age 30,12 years • Questionnaire to participants who have watched a series of advertising spots in TV 	ELM (Petty and Cacioppo, 1986b)	Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Argument quality primarily affected cognitive responses • Microfilm popularity has a positive effect on both cognitive and affective responses • Story plot had no significant effect on cognitive responses • Story plot had a positive effect on affective responses • Emotional components may override cognitive attitudes in persuading people • Celebrity effect positively affects both cognitive and affective responses • Cognitive and affective responses have positive effects on purchase intention, and, specifically, that changes in emotion states drive purchase intention
Kim et al. (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 530 participants • Close to equal female and male • Age from 18 to 64 equally distributed • Experiment with watching a narrative commercial or non-narrative • Subsequent questionnaire • Stimulus of 50 commercials (25 narrative and 25 non-narrative) 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000) and Identification (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008)	Confirmatory factor analyses, PROCESS, ANOVA and MANOVA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The study confirmed that narrative (versus non-narrative) commercials result in more emotive response, more ad hedonic value, more ad credibility, more perceived goal facilitation, more positive Ad attitude, and more positive brand attitudes • Further, the results supported the mediating role of ad hedonic value and ad credibility in terms of the effects of narrative (versus non-narrative) ads on ad attitude.

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Lee and Jeong (2017)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 314 participants Mainly female Questionnaire sent to person who had stayed in a hotel in the last 12 month and had seen a Social Network Site of the hotel 	Narrative Engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008)	Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation modeling (SEM) in LISREL	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The mediating role of emotive response in the effects of narrative (versus non-narrative) ads on Aad was not supported The effect of narrative (versus nonnarrative) ads on ad attitude was mediated by emotive response The effects of emotive response, ad hedonic value, and ad credibility on brand attitudes would be mediated by ad attitude The results further confirmed that the effects of narrative (versus non-narrative) ads on brand attitudes were additionally mediated by perceived goal facilitation Results identified both authenticity and humor as effective types of a hotel's brand story that induced customers' narrative engagement When the hotel's brand story was perceived real and interesting, customers tended to engage in the hotel's brand story on Social Network Sites (SNSs) This study identified narrative engagement had a positive influence on brand attitude and customers' behavioural intentions

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Jang et al. (2016)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pre-study with qualitative research • main study with experimental research • 10 participants in the main study • Experiment with viewing six different videos 	Narrative Engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008) and Interactivity (Bucy, 2004)	PLS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results indicate that the longer overall time of shared videos lead to a higher Narrative Engagement • A greater number of scenes leads to a more positive Narrative Engagement • Narrative Engagement was fully mediating between the temporal formats of a shared video and social interaction among users
Appel and Mara (2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 62 participants • Mean age 25,13 years • Experiment with reading a narrative story • Subsequent questionnaire 3 weeks later to find out if the behaviour has changed 	Narrative Presence (Narrative Engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008) and Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ANOVA and regression 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The trustworthiness of a fictional character matters with respect to persuasive outcomes • The disadvantage of a low-trustworthy character with respect to persuasive outcomes disappears among recipients with a strong experience to be part of the story world (high narrative engagement-presence) • Recipients who experience strong narrative presence are equally persuaded by both trustworthiness versions (low-trustworthiness and high-trustworthiness)

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Ching et al. (2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 816 participants • Questions prior and after watching a narrative advertising • Four different advertisements 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploratory factor analysis (EFA) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The findings suggest that a highly interactive, vivid, entertaining advertisement to which a consumer can relate facilitates the development of favorable product attitude, although these positive effects are contingent upon the degree to which a consumer is cognitively involved in the content of an advertisement • Greater self-referencing in the narrative advertisement induces transportation in the consumer and leads to favorable attitudes • Entertaining narrative advertising promotes consumer immersion by providing entertaining contextual details and elaboration that evoke emotional responses and facilitate mental simulation
Costabile and Terman (2013)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Two experiments • In Experiment 1, participants viewed a short film with its original musical soundtrack or with soundtrack muted • In Experiment 2, musical soundtrack was added to a film that was originally produced without music • Experiment 1: 61 participants • Experiments 2: 113 participants 	Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ANOVA and PROCESS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participants reported greater transportation into the film and greater agreement with film-relevant beliefs when musical soundtrack was presented, but only when music was congruent with the film's affective tone • The present experiments found similar effects of film music on both the cognitive and affective components of the psychological transportation scale

Literature	Method	Theory Model	Analysis method	Findings
Bhatnagar and Wan (2011)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Two experiments Experiment 1: 2 (narrative immersion: control, immersion) × 2 (self-character similarity: low, high); 88 participants; story reading; afterwards questionnaire answering Experiment 2: 2 (narrative immersion: control, immersion) × 2 (self-character similarity: low, high); 99 participants; story reading; afterwards brand naming 	<p>Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ANOVA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Narrative immersion moderates the impact of self-character similarity on brand and story evaluations Similarity to the character eases story-oriented immersion and frees up cognitive resources to proceed with brand-oriented elaboration Dissimilarity to the character makes story-oriented immersion challenging and leaves few resources for elaborating on brand information
Addis and Holbrook (2010)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Analysis of a database of high-quality cinema films 	<p>Narrative Transportation (Green and Brock, 2000); Identification (Green, 2007)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Weighted ordinary least squares (WOLS) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The anticipated role of a psychological match between the movie and the self, via an expansion of the possible drivers considered All drivers contribute significantly, with the sole exception of the driver most frequently studied in the past – gender and age

Several studies highlight the similarity between the audience and the story's characters as a determining factor in advertising design. This was emphasised by the research of Bhatnagar and Wan (2011), Karpinska-Krakowiak and Eisend (2020) and Van Laer et al. (2018). The study by Li and Liu (2020) demonstrates that empathy, which is typically accompanied by a likeness between narrative characters and viewers, has a good effect on attitude change. Several research (Kim et al., 2017, Su et al., 2018, Bartsch and Kloß, 2019) identify emotionality as a crucial determinant for the success of ads. None of the studies attempted to completely identify several elements in order to provide marketers with actionable advice. Before displaying ads or stories, only a small number of research attempt to ascertain attitudes toward the brand or the product. Consequently, the measurement of attitude change and persuasion is typically based on an assumption rather than a statistically meaningful result. Evaluation methods often consist of ANOVA, MANOVA, or confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). None of these methods of assessment permit the measurement of complex formative constructs that allow factors to be examined for their impact. The research by Li and Liu (2020), and Jang et al. (2016) use the Partial Least Square (PLS) assessment approach, which enables the evaluation of these complex formative constructs in particular. Jang et al. (2016) is the only study to apply the Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008) as a theoretical foundation. However, there are only 10 participants in this study, and the objective is not to explore the individual factors of "Narrative Engagement", but rather the occurrence of the construct as a whole. In addition, this study did not evaluate the attitude towards a brand or product before to viewing a commercial because it was not designed to analyse commercials, but rather to determine what causes a higher rate of social media sharing of personal videos. "Overall Time" (OT) and the "Number of Scenes" (NS) were examined for their influence on "Narrative Engagement" (NE). This study's objective was thus distinct from that of this thesis research. Therefore, the research of this thesis fills an obvious gap in the scientific literature by defining the important variables for a commercial that effects the brand or product attitude of viewers in a measurable way. Using "Narrative Engagement" as a theoretical foundation, potential variables (success factors) are identified and evaluated using the PLS approach.

3 Empirical study

3.1 Deriving from theory to research

The general assumption of many narrative persuasion models is that deeper immersion in the narrative story world, i.e., “Transportation” or “Narrative Engagement”, results in more consistent narrative attitudes following reception (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008, Green and Brock, 2000, Moyer-Gusé, 2008, Slater and Rouner, 2002b). Accordingly, the theory predicts that an attitude change will occur. This correlation has been demonstrated numerous times and validated by meta-analyses (Tukachinsky and Tokunaga, 2013, Van Laer et al., 2014). Thus, narratives present a tremendous opportunity for companies to serve as hero content and positively influence consumers' perceptions of a brand. It is yet unknown how the individual model factors will be formed. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to demonstrate to marketers which aspects must be considered to produce a good storytelling commercial. The underlying paradigm used is the “Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement” and the “Narrative Engageability” scale developed on this basis from Busselle and Bilandzic (2009). The advantage of the scale of “Narrative Engageability” compared to the “Transportation scale” of Green and Brock (2000) consists in the fact that it depicts the aspects of the reception process relevant for the state of transportation in unambiguous subdimensions. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to discover the elements that produce each factor on the scale of “Narrative Engageability”. The variables must be able to exert a substantial formative influence on the respective components. The corresponding variables were defined in Chapter 3.1.1.

It is important to alter the perception of a brand. The primary purpose of the brand is to foster a positive attitude. Consequently, brand perception is another essential element in the whole model. A negative perception of a brand infers a negative attitude toward the brand. Specifically, the negative image or attitude must be modified. Conversely, if a good opinion towards a brand already exists, it is expected that it cannot or should not be altered. This is because a change in attitude should always be beneficial.

A combination of attitudes and dissonant stimulus material is suitable for the study to measure the variables.

3.1.1 Indicator Variables

In the following, the indicator variables are explained in more detail, which serve as the basis for the questionnaire conducted. In addition, the indicator variables form the foundation for the following Partial-Least-Squares (PLS) structural model (more details in chapter 3.8.2), on the basis of which the subsequent evaluation will take place.

3.1.1.1 *Narrative Understanding*

Busselle and Bilandzic (2008) distinguish between three mental models pertinent to the comprehension of narration: the situation model, the story world model, and the character model. Situation model is the most significant of the three types (Van Dijk and Kintsch, 1983). It includes chronology and causation and is continuously updated during reception by comparing and integrating incoming data with the existing situation model (Zwaan et al., 1995). The viewer draws on his own schemata and scripts, i.e., existing knowledge structures of the real world and of narratives or genre standards, in order to comprehend and classify events in a narrative, as well as to make expectations or hypotheses about its progression (Graesser et al., 2002). In contrast, the model of the narrative world is a relatively static representation of a story's setting and logic (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008). The 'storyworld logic' (Segal, 1995) contains the rules and restrictions to which the figures and events of a story are subjected. Thus, we begin with the conditions of the real world, unless their laws have been suspended, as in genre conventions. Although the model of the narrative world is essential to the comprehension of a narrative, it frequently fades into the background during processing and only reemerges when one of the rules is violated (without explanation) (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008).

To accomplish these traits, the delivered narrative should ideally possess the following characteristics: The narrative has a clear structure for the listener's comprehension, and the characters are presented in an understandable manner, possibly with a brief introduction. The commercial should be presented in an understanding way overall.

3.1.1.2 *Attentional focus*

To explain the concept of attentional focus, the psychological measurement of activation is decoded. Activation is a crucial psychological variable when studying human behaviour, particularly consumer behaviour (Berlyne, 1960, Kroeber-Riel, 1979). Activation is a prerequisite for perception and information processing as it is the foundation of motivational processes (Kroeber-Riel and Gröppel-Klein, 2013). Activation is therefore described as a state of inner excitement that coincides with the human organism's willingness and capacity to perform as well as its attention (Kroeber-Riel, 1979, p. 241, Kroeber-Riel and Gröppel-Klein, 2013). Tonic, or long-term activation (e.g., attentiveness), is distinguished from phasic, or short-term activation, which is initiated by a stimulus (e.g., communication) and leads to a commensurate reaction. External or internal stimuli can initiate an activation state. A feeling of hunger is an example of an inner stimulus, while a trial stand in a pedestrian zone is an example of an outside stimulus. In communication, only the use of external stimuli plays a role.

The activation seeks to attract a potential consumer's attention to the message (contact impact) and then to employ it more intensively (amplification effect). Activating stimuli cause an orientation reaction, which is a neural system response that may be directly accompanied by a motor response or a change in a sense organ (Legewie, 1969, p. 168, Kroeber-Riel and Gröppel-Klein, 2013, p. 63 f.). "The strength of activation is a measure of how awake, reactive and efficient the organism is" (Kroeber-Riel and Gröppel-Klein, 2013, p. 61).

Upon successful customer contact establishment, the activation facilitates subsequent information processing (amplifying effect). Novak, Hoffman and Yung (2000) were able to demonstrate a positive effect of activation on concentration performance. Consequently, it should be highlighted that stimuli with a high activation level are better recognised and recalled (Berlyne, 1978, p. 98).

Power is proportional to activation in an inverted U-shaped relationship. According to the lambda hypothesis, power initially reaches an optimal level as activation increases. If this threshold is exceeded, stronger activation has a negative impact on an individual's performance (Yerkes and Dodson, 1908, Steenkamp and Baumgartner, 1992, Kroeber-Riel and Gröppel-Klein, 2013, p. 86 f.). A comparable study conducted by Gröppel-Klein (2013) at the Point of Sale indicates that the

alternating of strongly and mildly stimulating stimuli is evaluated as pleasant. If, however, all of the stimuli were highly stimulating, the retail environment would be perceived as unpleasant. This study varied the following stimuli: music, aroma, and customer rush.

However, the perception of "too little," "too much," or "ideal" activation is highly subjective. It depends on individual dispositions, habits, and anticipations (Berlyne, 1960, p. 211).

Research on the effects of advertising is one of the primary applications of activation techniques (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011, p. 41). For many years, it has been debated what features advertising must include in order to produce a specific activation in the customer and what results this has. In advertising, activating stimuli are widely employed to produce increased information absorption, faster information processing, and longer information storage by customers (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011, p. 41). Due to the plethora of products and brands that differ in quality just somewhat nowadays, distinguishing out in order to attract consumers' attention and pique their interest is becoming increasingly important (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011p. 43). In order to gain more customer activation and, eventually, to influence consumer behaviour, it is becoming increasingly essential to develop advertising that is distinguishable or unique (e.g., the renewed viewing or forwarding of an advertisement spot) (Foscht and Swoboda, 2011, p. 43, Duffy, 1962, p. 1 ff.). In addition, a number of research have demonstrated that customer activation has a favourable effect on his perception, attitude, and behaviour (e.g. Berger and Milkman, 2012b, Yang and Smith, 2009, MacInnis et al., 2002). Ultimately, various emotions might result in higher behavioural intentions on the part of individuals, such as the intention to pass on an advertisement to the desire to purchase (Berger and Milkman, 2012b, Yang and Smith, 2009). For more see chapter 2.1.2.

3.1.1.3 Narrative Presence

Narrative Presence describes the recipient's sense of immersion in the story's environment. In other words, the sensation of becoming engrossed in a narrative. Multiple things bolster this sentiment. Schubert and colleagues (1999) distinguish eight different factors: spatial presence, involvement, realness, immersion quality, drama, interface awareness, exploration and predictability. Rowe et al. (2007) Rowe et al. (2007) have taken up these factors and developed them further. They distinguish

between narrative-centric factors, user-centric factors and interpersonal factors. Since this distinction creates a large overlap with the other variables developed in this research, the following variables were analyzed as relevant and unique for the influence on narrative presence: Credibility, consistency of the story, enjoyment of watching, and immersion into the main character. As a clear negative factor, the perception of an attempted influence by the story was analyzed.

A major component of Narrative Presence is the recipient's "flow" sensation. Flow is defined as total attention on a task followed by a lack of awareness of oneself and the surrounding environment. Green and Brock argue that the transition into a narrative resembles a flow (Green, 2004, Green and Brock, 2000) in the recognition that the readers "lose track of time, fail to observe events going on around them, and feel they are completely immersed in the world of the narrative" (Green, 2004, p. 247).

In order to produce this flow, the following commercial features may be relevant and are therefore investigated in this study: Credibility of the story corresponding to the brand or product, consistency of the story, enjoyment of watching the commercial, empathy with the main character and the recognition of attempted influence by the viewer is considered counterproductive to flow, since it can induce reactance.

3.1.1.4 Emotional Engagement

Attentional Focus and Narrative Understanding are upstream processes that are required for Emotional Engagement and Narrative Presence. Emotional engagement is the process of developing an emotional connection with characters. This relationship entails experiencing emotions for characters (sympathy), exchanging emotions with characters (empathy), and experiencing arousal. Consequently, identification with characters is intimately tied to emotional engagement (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2009, Cohen, 2001).

Several things can impair emotional engagement at the same time. This is because, in a method based on mental models, "Narrative Engagement" competes for cognitive and emotional resources with other mental processes (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008). If resources are diverted away from comprehension, mental modelling and thus engagement should suffer. This effect can be caused by any procedure that has nothing to do with the narration (e.g., noise, hunger, work stress). Distraction, or the existence of thoughts that are unrelated to the narrative, is consequently a negative aspect of "Narrative Engagement".

Because the questionnaire was conducted online and the participants had trouble determining whether they are or were exposed to these obstacles during their involvement in the study, these obstacles were expressly excluded from the research. The primary objective of the study was to determine how empathy for the main character can be developed in the realm of emotional engagement. Consequently, all indicator variables in this field pertain to the examination of the elicitation of sympathy.

These include whether the listener identifies with the main character, finds him sympathetic, or empathises with him, and whether the story's perspectives encourage these emotions.

3.1.1.5 Overview of all indicator variables

On the basis of the Narrative Engageability Scale, the following indicator variables (attributes) were determined for each scale factor:

Table 5 Characteristics per Factor of the Narrative Engageability Scale

Factor	Characteristics
Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Clear structure• Characters presented in an understandable way• Commercial understandable overall
Attentional Focus	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Thrilling• Visual appealing• Personally relevant• Pleasant length• Background music entices attention
Narrative Presence	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Credability• Story consistent• Enjoyment• Immersion into the main character• Sense of influence (negative) - Reactance
Emotional Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Identification with the main character• Sympathy of the main character• Empathy with the main character• Perspectives support the empathy

3.2 Deduction of research questions and hypotheses

Prior to developing the hypotheses that will drive the research, it is necessary to identify the research questions. As proven in prior chapters, social media is a crucial communication medium for marketers today. YouTube stands out due to its diverse content options (see chapter 2.3.3). Therefore, the goal should be to construct YouTube content as effectively as feasible. Chapters 2.3.4 and especially 2.5 clearly indicate that storytelling or narrative persuasion is a suitable tool to positively influence people's attitudes. This begs the question of how exactly YouTube narrative commercials should be crafted to produce a favourable attitude shift among viewers:

RQ_1 = How should a storytelling commercial on YouTube be designed to successfully and positively influence the viewers' attitude towards the brand or the product?

Additionally, the question arises as to whether other factors greatly influence the impact of a commercial's design elements.

RQ_2 = Do other factors or design features have a significant moderating influence on the impact of the success factors?

Having established the theoretical foundations for the narrative persuasion resulting from storytelling commercials based on the "Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement", the purpose of this section is to develop hypotheses regarding the causal relationships between the indicators (success variables) and the constructs. The self-derived success factors for storytelling commercials are used for this purpose. These were conceptualised beforehand on a theoretical foundation. Figure 19 provides an overview of the complete impact model and identifies the hypotheses derived from it, which are detailed below.

Figure 19 Model with hypotheses

Understanding the narrative is crucial for the overall construct of “Narrative Engagement”. Narrative Understanding involves making sure that the viewer understands the story of the storytelling commercial so that he can then immerse himself in it. If the viewer does not understand the story of the commercial, it is unlikely that he or she will be transported into the world of the story. On the basis of the indicative variables, the following hypotheses about the development of Narrative Understanding can be formulated:

H_1 : A clear structure of the commercial has a significant impact on the construct of creating understanding.

H_2 : The comprehensible presentation of the commercial's characters has a significant influence on the construct of creating understanding.

H_3 : The comprehensibility of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating understanding.

For the establishment of Attentional Focus, a number of design elements have been established. See chapter 3.1.1. Attentional Focus indicates that the viewer gives the advertisement his undivided attention. The objective of the commercial producer should be to do this in order to attract the viewer's attention. Therefore, the following hypotheses are established:

H₄: Commercial tension has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.

H₅: The visually appealing design of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.

H₆: The personal relevance of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.

H₇: A pleasant length of commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.

H₈: Background music that increases attention to the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.

The narrative is made apparent to the viewer through Narrative Presence. He becomes convinced that the story is accurate and becomes immersed in it. Narrative Presence assesses how authentic and approachable the story was reported to the audience. The greater the viewer's Narrative Presence, the greater the likelihood that they will be transported. It is hypothesised that the following qualities of the commercial are responsible for this condition:

H₉: The credibility of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.

H₁₀: The consistency of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.

H₁₁: The perceived enjoyment of watching the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.

H₁₂: Immersion in the main character of the commercial has a significant impact on the construct of generating creating Presence.

*H*₁₃: Perceiving the attempted influence of the commercial has a significant negative impact on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.

Emotional engagement is the final element of "Narrative Engagement". The purpose of this composition is to evoke emotion in the observer. By evoking emotions, greater transportability into the commercial is produced. This can then result in a change in attitude. According to theory, when viewers sympathise with a major character, they are more likely to be transported and, as a result, more likely to have their perspectives altered. It is considered that the following variables contribute to emotional engagement:

*H*₁₄: Identification with the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.

*H*₁₅: The perceived sympathy for the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.

*H*₁₆: Perceived empathy with the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.

*H*₁₇: The perspectives of the commercial that support the perceived empathy with the main character have a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.

The corresponding hypothetically hypothesised "creation" constructs should have a substantial impact on their confirmed origin constructs. Thus, it is possible to confirm that the derivations of indicators from the literature and one's own thoughts were accurate and to continue the research.

*H*₁₈: The conceptual construct of creating Understanding has a significant influence on the construct of Understanding.

*H*₁₉: The conceptual construct of creating Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of Attentional Focus.

*H*₂₀: The conceptual construct of creating Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of Narrative Presence.

*H*₂₁: The conceptual construct of generating Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct Emotional Engagement.

Each of the established theoretical constructs should have an effect on attitude change. Furthermore, the brand impression should influence attitude change, as it should be difficult to accomplish an improvement if the brand impression is already positive. The commercials should not detract from the brand's reputation. Brands with a poorer brand impression should have easier access to influencing consumer attitudes.

H₂₂: Brand impression has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

H₂₃: The construct of Understanding has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

H₂₄: The construct of Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

H₂₅: The construct of Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

H₂₆: The construct of Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

In order to evaluate whether indicators have a genuine effect on attitude change, it is necessary to study each of the "creation" constructs to discover which indirectly affect attitude change. On the basis of this information, it is possible to conclude which of the detected indicators impact attitude change.

H₂₇: The construct of creating Understanding has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

H₂₈: The construct of creating Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

H₂₉: The construct of creating Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

H₃₀: The construct of creating Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

In conclusion, the hypotheses are detailed once more.

Table 6 Hypotheses for the design of storytelling commercials

Hypothesis	
<i>H₁</i>	A clear structure of the commercial has a significant impact on the construct of creating understanding.
<i>H₂</i>	The comprehensible presentation of the commercial's characters has a significant influence on the construct of creating understanding.
<i>H₃</i>	The comprehensibility of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating understanding.
<i>H₄</i>	Commercial tension has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.
<i>H₅</i>	The visually appealing design of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.
<i>H₆</i>	The personal relevance of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.
<i>H₇</i>	A pleasant length of commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.
<i>H₈</i>	Background music that increases attention to the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.
<i>H₉</i>	The credibility of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.
<i>H₁₀</i>	The consistency of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.
<i>H₁₁</i>	The perceived enjoyment of watching the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.
<i>H₁₂</i>	Immersion in the main character of the commercial has a significant impact on the construct of generating creating Presence.
<i>H₁₃</i>	Perceiving the attempted influence of the commercial has a significant negative impact on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.
<i>H₁₄</i>	Identification with the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.
<i>H₁₅</i>	The perceived sympathy for the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.
<i>H₁₆</i>	Perceived empathy with the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.

<i>H₁₇</i>	The perspectives of the commercial that support the perceived empathy with the main character have a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.
<i>H₁₈</i>	The conceptual construct of creating Understanding has a significant influence on the construct of Understanding.
<i>H₁₉</i>	The conceptual construct of creating Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of Attentional Focus.
<i>H₂₀</i>	The conceptual construct of creating Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of Narrative Presence.
<i>H₂₁</i>	The conceptual construct of generating Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct Emotional Engagement.
<i>H₂₂</i>	Brand impression has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.
<i>H₂₃</i>	The construct of Understanding has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.
<i>H₂₄</i>	The construct of Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.
<i>H₂₅</i>	The construct of Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.
<i>H₂₆</i>	The construct of Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.
<i>H₂₇</i>	The construct of creating Understanding has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.
<i>H₂₈</i>	The construct of creating Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.
<i>H₂₉</i>	The construct of creating Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.
<i>H₃₀</i>	The construct of creating Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.

3.3 Stimulus material

Based on the indicator variables (characteristics) defined in section 3.1.1.4, acceptable commercials for storytelling were selected. The indicator variables were associated with the commercials. This yields the following summary of properties per commercial:

Table 7 Stimulus material mapped with indicator variables (characteristics)

Video	Characteristics
Mercedes – The Journey Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Immersion into the main character can be hard (child) • Good understandable • Sympathic main character
Edeka - Villagedrift - Spectacularly short delivery routes Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • No real story • No connection to the character • Fast cuts • Sense of influence
Audi – An Avant Story Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual appealing • Long commercial (no pleasant length) • Good explanation of the character • Clear structure
Lacoste – Timeless Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual appealing • Background music entices attention • Fast Cuts
Penny - Christmas does not need much Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional • Visual appealing (animation) • Can be personal relevant • Credability
Volvo XC 60 – Moments Link	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thrilling • Emotional • Can be personal relevant • Background music entices attention • Good explanation of the character • Credability

Video				Characteristics	
Adidas Link	–	Break	Free	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thrilling • Emotional • Can be personal relevant 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Good explanation of the character • Clear structure
Cartier Link	–	L'Odyssée		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visual appealing (animation) • Very long commercial (no pleasant length) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Main character is an animal • Overall not really understandable and consistent

As stimulation material, eight distinct commercials with narratives were chosen. Each commercial has unique qualities. Efforts have been made to ensure that as many indicator variables as possible are covered by the various commercial features. Examples of primary characters include adults, children, animated people, and animals.

3.4 Data collection and sampling method

For the statistical assessment of the explanatory models, it is necessary to collect empirical data on storytelling commercials. The following section contains the definition of the sample, the format of the questionnaire, the selection of the research method, and the questionnaire procedure.

Prior to data collection, it was required to select the sample. All internet-accessible individuals were surveyed. Given that this is the ideal demographic for the selected brands, preference was given to younger, academic-degreed adults up to roughly 40 years of age. In addition, it is usually preferable to achieve a change in attitude at a young age; nonetheless, those with an academic degree have a greater average net household income.

The choice of questionnaire approach was motivated by the need to collect as many complete and comparable responses as feasible. To attain this purpose, the following questionnaire method was utilised:

Web-based questionnaire: A web-based questionnaire of individuals was conducted. The complete questionnaire was transformed into a web-based questionnaire. This strategy had the advantage of producing a large number of examples in a short amount of time. Another advantage was that the data could be transmitted directly into a database, hence increasing the likelihood of improved data quality. In addition, the commercial videos could be immediately included into the questionnaire. Additionally, the duration of the questionnaire was optimal for a web-based inquiry, and no personal explanations were required.

The design of the multipart questionnaire was tailored to the explanatory model and reflects the concept of "Narrative Engagement" of the "Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement". Respondents were initially questioned about their opinion of a specific brand. On a bipolar scale, they were required to rank related brands, indicate whether the brand was perceived positively or negatively, and assign certain characteristics to the brand. The responders were then shown the corresponding story-based advertisement. Subsequently, the "Narrative Engageability Scale" by Busselle and Bilandzic (2009) was questioned for each construct (Narrative Understanding, Attentional Focus, Narrative Presence and Emotional Engagement). After each construct, the derived "success factors" (see Table 5) were asked immediately. This was followed by a set of socio-demographic questions, and finally the respondents were asked to rate the brands again with the same questions as before the commercial. This made it possible to identify possible changes in attitudes later on using a simple difference calculation. Please see the full questionnaire in the Appendix.

When conducting the web-based questionnaire, respondents were provided with an identical cover letter on the Internet.

The questionnaire was conducted from April 2020 to September 2020.

Since this study was based on a quantitative research design, it would have been ideal to employ a probability sampling approach, which permits statistical inferences (i.e., generalisations) to be drawn from the sample of participants to the entire target population of potential consumers. This kind of probability sampling would increase the external validity of the findings. In principle it is not feasible to establish a clear, general population for this study due to the fact that the target group of consumers is determined by each organisation individually, and often varies throughout sectors. In the case that a population was clearly identified for this study, a stratified random

sample would have been the optimal choice of probability sampling method to ensure an equal ratio of women to males and, for instance, income levels.

Because the population for this study cannot be precisely defined due to the fact that it is not limited to companies in a particular industry, the target group cannot be precisely defined, and neither can the population. Consequently, stratified random sampling was not employed. As the objective was to obtain as many replies as possible, convenience sampling was selected as the non-probability sampling technique. Participants were recruited using personal social media accounts, HAW Hamburg mailing lists, and my employer's email. This has the drawback that the outcomes of the study may be less able to generalise due to the possibility of sample bias.

3.5 Description of the sample

Even though the PLS approach, as a distribution-free analysis method, does not require a normally distributed database and therefore provides highly robust results with non-normally distributed data, Kolmogorov-Smirnov tests (KS test) and Shapiro-Wilk tests (SW test) were conducted on all construct indicators to test for a normal distribution of the questionnaire data. It should be noted that an extreme deviation from the normal distribution in the given case would be unfavourable in that the evaluation of significance tests would be accompanied by more stringent conditions, which in turn would result in a decrease in the statistical predictive power within the bootstrapping procedure. The data set exhibited significant ($p < 0.05$) departures from the Gaussian normal distribution, as determined by both test methodologies. Table 8 displays the results of the testing for each indicator.

Table 8 Test for normal distribution of the measured indicators

Item	Skew	Kurtosis	KS Test	SW Test	Item	Skew	Kurtosis	KS Test	SW Test
Rating_Difference	-0.345	3.075	0.279*	0.856*	Attentional_Focus_2	-0.727	-0.688	0.268*	0.828*
Impression_Difference	0.235	0.825	0.341*	0.797*	Attentional_Focus_3	-0.781	-0.669	0.266*	0.816*
Difference_Difference	0.110	1.953	0.323*	0.810*	Attentional_Focus_Creation_1	0.755	-0.160	0.282*	0.854*
Attribute_1_Difference	-0.134	2.668	0.265*	0.868*	Attentional_Focus_Creation_2	1.366	2.214	0.270*	0.773*
Attribute_2_Difference	0.631	2.742	0.361*	0.764*	Attentional_Focus_Creation_3	-0.283	-0.986	0.217*	0.898*
Attribute_3_Difference	1.406	6.100	0.422*	0.627*	Attentional_Focus_Creation_4	-0.189	-1.256	0.237*	0.881*
Attribute_4_Difference	0.175	3.723	0.341*	0.781*	Attentional_Focus_Creation_5	0.751	-0.161	0.271*	0.868*
Attribute_5_Difference	0.769	1.188	0.272*	0.869*	NarrativePresence_1	0.171	-1.139	0.229*	0.891*
Attribute_6_Difference	0.843	2.302	0.288*	0.850*	NarrativePresence_2	-0.142	-1.172	0.239*	0.881*
Attribute_7_Difference	0.563	1.389	0.323*	0.832*	NarrativePresence_3	0.036	-1.160	0.197*	0.896*
Attribute_8_Difference	0.581	1.022	0.254*	0.883*	NarrativePresence_Creation_1	0.445	-0.827	0.257*	0.884*
Attribute_9_Difference	-0.157	1.651	0.274*	0.864*	NarrativePresence_Creation_2	1.281	1.921	0.336*	0.776*
Attribute_10_Difference	0.753	1.581	0.276*	0.864*	NarrativePresence_Creation_3	0.946	0.445	0.271*	0.843*
Attribute_11_Difference	0.384	0.511	0.197*	0.917*	NarrativePresence_Creation_4	0.502	-0.712	0.255*	0.883*
Attribute_12_Difference	0.285	1.008	0.272*	0.888*	NarrativePresence_Creation_5	0.360	-0.902	0.251*	0.882*
Understanding_1	-1.074	0.138	0.242*	0.786*	EmotionalEngagement_1	0.813	-0.140	0.278*	0.850*
Understanding_2	-0.867	-0.545	0.256*	0.794*	EmotionalEngagement_2	0.700	-0.431	0.266*	0.864*
Understanding_3	-1.180	0.435	0.262*	0.767*	EmotionalEngagement_3	0.676	-0.550	0.276*	0.860*

Item	Skew	Kurtosis	KS Test	SW Test	Item	Skew	Kurtosis	KS Test	SW Test
Understanding_Creation_1	1.080	0.467	0.294*	0.805*	EmotionalEngagement_Creation_1	0.020	-1.204	0.205*	0.896*
Understanding_Creation_2	1.357	1.444	0.288*	0.750*	EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2	0.964	0.573	0.250*	0.825*
Understanding_Creation_3	1.555	2.116	0.295*	0.725*	EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3	0.528	-0.558	0.275*	0.877*
Attentional_Focus_1	-0.662	-0.758	0.266*	0.843*	EmotionalEngagement_Creation_4	0.610	-0.300	0.257*	0.882*

KS test (asymptotic; test-wise case exclusion; significance correction according to Lilliefors)

SW test (listwise case exclusion; mean confidence interval: 0, 95)

Sample size: $n = 191$

Significance level: $*p < 0.001$

Maximum skewness and kurtosis are determined by the indicator Attribute_3_Difference (1.406 and 6.100). This indicates that the bias against the Gaussian normal distribution for all construct indicators is below a threshold of 2 for skewness and 7 for kurtosis, hence excluding the possibility of excessive bias. (Curran et al., 1996). Hence, a robust parameter estimation with respect to the data characteristics is assumed.

Harman's one-factor test was conducted to rule out the idea that a single source of variation determines all model constructs in accordance with the common-method bias. The 10 exploratory factors identified from the factor analysis explain a maximum of 29.46% of the overall variance.

Due to the fact that the normal threshold of 50% was not significantly surpassed, it may be considered that there is no common technique bias. Table 9 contains the test findings for the unrotated principal component analysis.

Table 9 Harman's one-factor test for common-method bias

Eigenvalue	Explained variance (%)	Cumulated variance (%)
12.962	29.459	29.459
4.049	9.203	38.662
2.445	5.557	44.219
2.388	5.428	49.647
1.693	3.847	53.494
1.491	3.389	56.883
1.253	2.848	59.731
1.241	2.821	62.552
1.129	2.566	65.118
1.038	2.359	67.477

Explorative factor analysis (unrotated; Kaiser-Guttman criterion: eigenvalue > 1)
Sample size: $n = 191$

Table 10 Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample

	Frequency	%		Frequency	%
Gender			Employment		
Female	122	63.9	Employee	86	45.0
Male	69	36.1	Self-employed	3	1.6
			Civil servant	4	2.1
			Pensioner	1	0.5
Age			Jobseeker	1	0.5
17 or younger	1	0.5	Student	94	49.2
18 – 20	3	1.6	Pupil	1	0.5
21 – 29	135	70.7	Housewife/husband	1	0.5
30 – 39	34	17.8			
40 – 49	6	3.1			
50 – 59	9	4.7	Net household income		
60 or older	3	1.6	under 500 EUR	16	8.4
			501 – 1,000 EUR	36	18.8
			1,001 – 2,000 EUR	38	19.9
Highest level of education			2,001 – 3,000 EUR	38	19.9
Secondary school	10	5.2	3,001 – 4,000 EUR	20	10.5
Grammar school	43	22.5	4,001 – 5,000 EUR	17	8.9
Bachelor	89	46.6	over 5,000 EUR	12	6.3
Master	45	23.6	no indication	14	7.3
PhD	4	2.1			

A little less than two-thirds (63.9 %) of the sample is female, indicating a preponderance of women relative to men (36.1 %). In terms of age distribution, it is notable that a very tiny percentage of respondents are twenty or younger (2.1 %), while only three are over sixty (1.6 %). Seventy percent of the responders are between the ages of twenty-five and thirty-nine.

Regarding the education level of the sample, it is obvious that nearly three-quarters (72.3 %) of the respondents hold a degree. This also explains why there are so few participants under the age of twenty. The sample can be roughly divided between employees (45.0 %) and students (49.2 %). 5.7 % of the sample are neither employed nor enrolled in school.

The distribution of household income is generally even. This is due to the proportionately high number of students and employees. Thus, within the sample,

nearly the same proportion of incomes are found in the lower to middle (up to 2,000 EUR) range (47.1 %) as in the middle (2,001 to 3,000 EUR) to exceptionally high (over 5,000 EUR) range (2,001 to 3,000 EUR to over 5,000 EUR) (45.6 %).

In conclusion, the descriptive findings presented here support the conclusion, both from a socio-demographic and a general data characterisation standpoint, that the empirical-quantitative analysis based on these primary data is not subject to any egregious distortions and fully satisfies the requirements of PLS structural equation modelling.

3.6 Ethical concerns

Throughout the research, it was verified that ethics were the primary concern. Adherence to the techniques outlined in this chapter was crucial for assuring the study's validity and reliability. Each participant received an electronic permission form prior to the study, which they were required to sign in order to participate. On the permission form, it was specified what will be studied and that participants might withdraw at any moment. Additionally, they were guaranteed and ensured that no personal information was maintained. All participants were over 18 years of age and stated that they do not demonstrate any impaired mental capacity. Meeting these criteria qualified them as participants in this study.

In addition, an ethics application was submitted to the UWS Ethics Committee because this study investigated psychological processes and drew conclusions about how people can be influenced by commercials. The Ethics Committee approved the application (see Appendix 6.2).

3.7 Operationalisation and measurement of variables

This chapter details the operationalization of the success elements and narratives derived in chapter 3.1.1. As these are complex theoretical constructs (latent variables), they are not directly observable and must be made quantifiable through the use of proper indicators (manifest variables). Edwards and Bagozzi (2000) define "a conceptual term used to describe a phenomenon of theoretical interest" as a theoretical construct or latent variable.

For the research area of narrative persuasion, the proven scale of Busselle and Bilandzic of Narrative Engageability is used. It is expanded to incorporate the

indicators from chapter 3.1.1 so that possible inferences can be drawn concerning the formation of Busselle and Bilandzic's variables. Thus, design ideas for commercials that tell stories can be provided.

Hypothetical constructs can basically have a reflective or formative character:

- Indicators are formed as a result of reflecting constructs; reflective constructs are therefore a variable underlying the indicators.
- Formative constructs are brought about by their indicators; they are a linear combination of their indicators.

Formative constructs are frequently used to evaluate the impact of company policies and environmental conditions, whereas reflective constructs are frequently employed to test theoretical relationships.

To analyse the nature of a construct, it must first be determined whether the construct's expressions are measured; if the construct has a reflective nature or if different aspects of the construct play a role, then the indicators constitute the construct. The decision to model a reflective or formative construct is supported by logical reasons based on facts. Due to the fact that improper specification of a construct might result in severe distortions of the results, it is crucial that a precise description of the corresponding construct is established at the outset of the research process.

In the next chapters, the operationalization of the constructs for the explanatory model of "Narrative Engagement" is described. In addition to describing the operationalization of the variables, the descriptive presentation of the results includes information about the indicators' features. Since operationalization of the conceptions can result in methodological distortions, steps to avoid so-called "common method bias" are offered for the subsequent research.

3.7.1 Measures to avoid a Common Method Bias

A potential issue with the operationalization of the variables is the distortion of the results by a common method bias, which consists of variation that is not explained by the model's variables but by the measurement method. Common method bias is one of the most significant sources of measurement errors that threaten the validity of empirical research's conclusions. On the basis of theoretical considerations, for instance, if an influence of construct A on construct B is established, a correlation

between the measures is anticipated. Nonetheless, if constructs A and B share the same measurement procedures, there is a chance that the methods will impact the correlation between the constructs. In a study of 70 empirical studies, Cote and Buckley (1987) found that on average 26.3% of the variance is due to a common method bias, compared to 15.8% in marketing studies.

The collection of dependent and independent variables by the same individual produces common source effects, which, for a variety of reasons, may result in correlations that do not exist in reality. Reasons for these absent correlations include the following:

- the respondents' need to be rational and consistent in their response behaviour,
- the desire of the respondents to be seen in a positive light, regardless of their actual opinion (social desirability),
- the answers to the questions regardless of the question posed,
- the respondents' perception of relationships between variables,
- the positive or negative basic attitude of the respondents.

Several factors may contribute to questionnaire design-induced distortions. They may result from the manner and context in which respondents are presented with the items. Causes of bias include, for instance:

- the unclear and ambiguous formulation of questions, which force the respondent to interpret the question himself. This encourages random answers or systematic misinterpretations,
- the use of the same scale format for dependent and independent variables. This can lead to distortions, since answering the questions requires less cognitive effort than with different scales and, by answering on the same scale ratios, can create a coherence between these variables that does not exist in reality,
- the context in which the questions are asked. Respondents can cause delays if they assume that variables have an influence due to the context. This can be triggered by the order of the items in the questionnaire or by emotions that are provoked by particular questions,
- the scale length. A bias can be a result of short scales being more memorable and more accessible when answering different questions,

- the time of the measurement. Measuring dependent and independent variables at the same time can also lead to distortions, as evaluations can be retrieved from the short-term memory.
- the elevation method. Computer-assisted and written questionnaires have a lower bias because personal interviews are often distorted by the influence of the interviewer.

The influence of the research design has demonstrated the significance of carefully evaluating the conditions under which data are obtained and avoiding bias.

By temporally, psychologically, or methodologically separating the collection of dependent and independent variables, source bias can be minimised. Due to the impracticality of temporal and psychological separation in the present study, an attempt was made to eliminate the common method bias by methodological separation. Using distinct types of scales or collecting methods for dependent and independent variables helps accomplish methodological separation.

In this questionnaire, an attempt was made to create methodological separation by employing various scale types. The usage of multiple scale types is counterbalanced by the simplification of question response when utilising the same scale types, which require a lesser cognitive performance from respondents. After assessing the pros and cons of using the same scales for the collection of dependent and independent variables, there was no total separation. The research success criteria were collected using seven-level Lickert scales.

Various countermeasures were developed to counteract the questionnaire's effect on the results. The respondents' anonymity was ensured to exclude the influence of social desirability.

3.8 Evaluation method

This section describes the approach for estimating the established explanation models. We begin by discussing multi-equation structure models and their estimation methods. The Partial Least Squares Approach (PLS) and the estimation quality criteria are then offered as the evaluation approach.

As can be seen in Figure 20, the process of selecting an appropriate analysis methodology at Hair (2009) begins with the question of what type of relationship between the variables to be analysed should be investigated.

Figure 20 Classification of multivariate analysis methods

First, a difference must be established between statistical methods of analysis that evaluate the relationship between dependent and independent variables and methods where the dependence and independence of variables are irrelevant and just the relationship's structures are examined. The determinants of "creation constructs" are the independent variables whose influence on the corresponding dependent variable is to be investigated. In addition, the influence of the associated dependent variable (such as Understanding) on the dependent variable Attitude Change is investigated, resulting in multi-level linkages between the variables in the theoretical model. Since the relationships between several dependent and independent variables are simultaneously analysed, only dependency methods (e.g., factor analysis or cluster analysis) can be used to test the hypotheses; interdependency methods (e.g., factor analysis or cluster analysis) cannot be employed.

Since the model under investigation comprises multiple complex interactions between independent and dependent variables, structural equation modelling is the only viable evaluation technique.

3.8.1 Multi-equation structure models

Given that the explanatory models contain many multi-level interactions between various hypothetical constructs that are monitored by indicators, it is reasonable to present and validate the explanatory models using multi-equation structural models. The components of a multi-equation structure model are non-measurable hypothetical constructions (latent variables) and measurable indicators (manifest variables). Two systems of equations are used to form a multi-equation structural model: the so-called

structural model or inner model and the so-called measurement model or outer model (Cool et al., 1989). The structural model describes the relationships between hypothetical constructs, while the measurement model illustrates the relationships between quantifiable indicators and hypothetical constructions (Betzin and Henseler, 2005, p. 50 f.).

Figure 21 Structural model with formative and reflective measurement models

Multi-equation structural models integrate the modelling of latent variables utilising observable manifest variables with econometric forecasting techniques, thereby allowing simultaneous estimate of the measurement and structural model (Fornell and Cha, 1994). Moreover, multi-equation structure models account for measurement mistakes in the model and permit different indicator weights or charges (Chin, 1998b).

Multi-equation structure models can be estimated using two divergent methods:

- Covariance-based approach: Originating from the study of Jöreskog (Jöreskog, 1967, 1970, 1979, Jöreskog and Sörbom, 1982), the covariance-based technique reduces the distance between the empirical and theoretical covariance matrices and employs maximum likelihood estimation. However, the covariance-based approach is frequently unsuitable for marketing problems because it places stringent requirements on the data, such as a large number of cases due to the simultaneous estimation of parameters, the normal distribution of data, and the exclusive use of reflective indicators.

- Partial Least Squares Approach: The Partial Least Squares Approach (PLS) developed by Wold (Wold, 1980, 1982a, 1982b, 1985) is based on least squares estimates.

Since the prerequisites of the Linear Structural Relationships (LISREL) as a covariance-based approach cannot be met for the current research issue, the rarely used PLS method is employed. Due to the estimate of least squares, the approach does not require distribution hypotheses. Due to the fact that PLS employs an iterative technique in which only one equation is estimated at a time under the assumption that all other variables are fixed, the method is suited to small samples with few degrees of freedom (Barclay et al., 1995, p. 292). While a minimum sample of 200 cases applies to LISREL (Hair et al., 2006, p. 605), for PLS Chin mentions either the largest number of constructs that explain an endogenous construct or the largest number of formative indicators that explain a construct multiplied by ten (Chin, 1998b).

Existing models' formative constructs can be estimated, which is another advantage of the PLS model over the LISREL technique. Since the path coefficients of the indicators are estimated simultaneously with the structural model, both formative and reflective constructs can be estimated, whereas with the LISREL approach only reflective constructs can be considered because the objective is to explain the covariance of all items (Barclay et al., 1995, p. 301).

In addition to the aforementioned benefits, the PLS method is superior at explaining complex relationships (Fornell et al., 1990, p. 1250). The LISREL method has a more confirmatory nature, whereas the PLS method is frequently employed in exploratory investigations to explain complex correlations.

Table 11 Comparison between LISREL and PLS

Criterion	LISREL	PLS
Model	Covariance structure model	Data structure model
Estimation model	Estimation of the parameters by approximating the model-theoretical correlation matrix to the empirical correlation matrix.	Estimation of the parameters by minimising the residual variance in the linear model
Estimation method	Maximum-Likelihood	Smallest squares
Data requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exclusively reflective constructs • multivariate distributional assumptions • Large samples (>200) • Interval scale level 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formative and reflective constructs • No distribution assumptions • Small samples • Nominal, ordinal and interval scale level

Source: Own Illustration based on Fornell and Bookstein (1982)

The low preconditions under which the PLS method functions are a source of criticism for this method. Due to the lack of distribution assumptions, the model's measurement errors cannot be defined, and only heuristic methods can be used to evaluate the model's quality (Chin, 1998b). Another issue with the PLS procedure is the consistency of the estimators, which, in contrast to LISREL, are not consistent but can be described as "consistent at large"; that is, as the sample size and number of indicators per construct increase, the estimated parameter values tend to approach the true parameter values.

Figure 22 Covariance-based Structure Equation Model (CBSEM) and PLS comparison

Comparing the methodologies revealed that the explanatory models developed for narrative success elements can only be estimated with the partial least squares method and the available data. This strategy is consequently elaborated upon in the subsequent section.

3.8.2 The Partial Least Square (PLS) Approach

The structural model describes the labels of hypothetical constructs and their impact relationships, whereas the measurement model describes the labels between latent variables and their indicators. In the PLS method, the relationships are considered to be linear. Figure 23 gives an overview of the basic PLS model.

Figure 23 Basic PLS model

In the model, η_i represents the exogenous constructs of the model. Y_{ki} and Y_{kj} represent the indicators of the model, β_{ji} represents the path coefficients of the

structural model and π_{ki} and π_{kj} represent the regression coefficients of the measurement model.

In a set of regression equations, the relationships between the latent variables in the structural model are understood as causal dependencies:

$$\eta_j = \sum_i \beta_{ji} \eta_i + v_j$$

Here, η_j refers to an endogenous hypothetical construct determined by the constructs η_i , β_{ji} refers to the regression coefficients and v_j refers to the inner residual variable. The error terms v_j are assumed to be independent of the predictor variables η_i :

$$cov(\eta_i; v_j) = 0$$

so that

$$E(v_j) = 0$$

The latent variable η_j appears as a regress of its exogenous latent variable η_i occurring in the path model. All constructs that appear in the structural model before a latent variable η_j arrow notation are considered to be exogenous latent variables. The structural model must also be recursive, meaning that none of the latent variables may influence themselves.

The measurement model describes the relationships between the latent and indicator variables. There are essentially two ways in which the latent variables and indicator variables might be related: Indirectly measuring reflective constructions with a set of indicator variables that explain the construct. Each variable reflective indicator can be characterised by a straightforward relationship to its construct (Mode A):

$$Y_{kj} = \pi_{kj} + \varepsilon_{kj}$$

On the other hand, formative constructs are explained by their indicators and are linear combinations of their indicator variables (Mode B):

$$\eta_j = \sum_{k_j} \pi_{k_j} Y_{k_j} + \varepsilon_{k_j} \text{ for } k=1, \dots, K$$

While Mode A is estimated using a series of simple regressions with the indicators as dependent variables, Mode B is estimated through multiple regressions with the indicators of a construct as independent variables (Seltin and Keeves, 1994, p. 4355).

The path coefficients are to be interpreted as loading coefficients for reflective constructs, while they represent weights for formative constructs (Fornell and Bookstein, 1982).

The model parameters are calculated using a two-step algorithm:

- In the first stage, the constructs are estimated via an iteration algorithm
- In the second step, the model parameters are calculated with least squares estimates. The process of the iteration algorithm is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24 Procedure of the estimation algorithm

The estimate of the parameters assumes that the constructs are linear combinations of the corresponding indicator variables.

$$\eta_j = \sum_{k_j} \omega_{k_j} Y_{k_j}$$

Here ω_{k_j} indicate estimates of the path coefficients π_{k_j} , which are initially unknown and are estimated in the iteration cycle. Y_{k_j} are the observations of the k-th indicator of construct j.

For the estimation, any starting weights ω_{k_j} are given first, from which the constructs are calculated. In the first step of the iteration algorithm, a coefficient v_{j_i} is determined for the correlation between the constructs. There are three procedures for determining

the correlation. Centroid weighting only includes the sign direction of the latent variable to be calculated and the neighbouring latent variables. The strength and direction of the correlation is not taken into account. Centroid weighting is hardly ever used because of the high loss of information.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{signCOV}(\hat{\eta}_j; \hat{\eta}_i) && \text{if } \eta_j \text{ and } \eta_i \text{ are connected} \\ & v_{ji} = 0 && \text{otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

Factor weighting additionally incorporates the strength of the association into the relationship variable by using the correlation coefficient between the linked constructs.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{CORR}(\hat{\eta}_j; \hat{\eta}_i) && \text{if } \eta_j \text{ and } \eta_i \text{ are connected} \\ & v_{ji} = 0 && \text{otherwise} \end{aligned}$$

Path weighting also takes into account the relationship between the constructs. Therefore, the independent variables are weighted according to their regression coefficients, whereas the dependent variables are weighted according to their correlation coefficients. When there are hypotheses concerning the direction of the association between two constructs, path weighting is frequently employed. If there are no hypotheses on the relationships between the constructs, factor weighting is the suitable technique. Due to the presumptions on the directionality of the relationships, the path weighting approach is applied in this context.

In the second step of the iteration algorithm (S2), a so-called "environment variable" is calculated, which is an approximation of the construct η_j from the connected constructs weighted with the coefficient v_{ji} .

$$\tilde{\eta}_j = \sum_i v_{ji} \hat{\eta}_i$$

The environment variable is designated with $\hat{\eta}$.

The weights ω are calculated from the environment variable in the third step of the iteration algorithm (S3). Both estimation modes A and B are applied here.

After calculating these weights for a new evaluation of the constructs (S4), the process for iteration is restarted from the beginning. The iteration concludes when no further improvements are possible.

In the second stage of the estimation algorithm, the model parameters are calculated from the constructs assessed in the first stage. All calculations are based on least squares estimates.

3.8.3 Validity criteria for the assessment of the PLS model

Due to the fact that the PLS approach does not require a distribution algorithm, no parametric significance tests can be employed to evaluate its validity. Therefore, heuristic approaches are employed.

The assessment of the validity of the explanatory model is done in two steps:

1. In the first phase, the validity of the measurement model or outer model is determined, as the structural model's validity can only be determined if the indicators adequately explain the hypothetical constructs.
2. Once the measurement model's validity has been established, the structural model's validity can be assessed. This is the only way to guarantee that the interpretation of the results is based on valid and reliable results.

Figure 25 Systematic evaluation of the PLS results

Methods are utilised to evaluate the multi-equation structural model by determining, on the one hand, the explanatory content of the structural and measurement models and, on the other, the stability of the estimators. The evaluation of the measuring model's quality must differentiate between reflective and formative indicators.

The indicator loadings on the respective construct can be used to evaluate the validity of the **reflective measurement model**. It is anticipated that the indicators would adequately explain the variation of the constructs. Observing the factor loadings, which indicate the strength of the relationship between a factor and its outcome variable, enables this. The recommendation is to include in the research only variables having a factor loading greater than 0.707. In addition, a principal component analysis is conducted, which provides values for indicator and construct loadings.

Two further assessment measures of reflective measurement models are the IC value and the AVE value. The IC value developed by Werts, Linn and Jöreskog is, similar

to Cronbach's alpha, a measure of the internal consistency of the estimators. The IC value is calculated with the following formula:

$$IC = \frac{(\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i)^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i)^2 + k - \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i^2}$$

With λ_i for the factor loading of indicator i and k for the number of indicators measuring the construct.

The IC value differs from Cronbach's alpha in that it takes into account the specific charges of each indicator, whereas Cronbach's alpha assumes that all indicators have equal charges. Under the condition that the estimated parameter values are valid, the IC value can be regarded as a more precise measurement.

Fornell and Larcker presented the determination of the average recorded variance (AVE) as a tool for evaluating reflective measurement models. The AVE measurement can be derived from the predicted charges using PLS:

$$AVE = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i^2 + k - \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda_i^2}$$

with λ_i for the factor loadings of indicator i and k for the number of indicators measuring the construct. It can thus be verified how high the variance share of revealed variables explained by a factor is.

The values of the quality measures range from zero to one, with higher values indicating higher measurement quality. For the IC value, values greater than 0.70 are acceptable, while for the AVE measure, values greater than 0.50 are acceptable.

Due to the fact that formative constructs reverse the causal direction of indicators, the validity metrics for reflective measurement models cannot be applied to **formative measurement models**. As the indicators are not connected, additional criteria must be utilised to evaluate the validity of the formative measurement approach. By their very nature, formative indicators may not necessarily indicate a strong association with the associated construct.

The validity and relevance of the indicators to the evaluation must first be determined. Prior to this, the signs and quantities of the path coefficients must be evaluated. The indicators should indicate the desired direction and be of sufficient quantity. Lower weights of formative indicators should not be construed prematurely as a sign of a

flawed measuring approach. Since the PLS method maximises the amount of explained variance in the dependent variable and hence suggests the deletion of indicators with low loadings in non-reflective measurement models, this rule must not be blindly applied to formative measurement models. The elimination of formative items necessitates both statistical and content-related considerations. These factors are based on two considerations: First, the construct has been assigned formative indications based on theoretical-conceptual concerns. Due to the fact that the indicators are not necessarily connected with one another, formative constructs typically have lower weights and, as a result, carry little weight within the measurement model. However, their deletion may result in a misrepresentation of the measurement model's precision.

Since a significant correlation between formative indicators can result in biased conclusions, multicollinearity must be examined for formative indicators. If multicollinearity is present, it is impossible to identify the solitary influence of an estimator, hence it is highly likely to contain redundant data. In this context, collinearity refers to the degree of linear dependence between the indicators. To identify linear connections among the formative indicators, the estimators' tolerance and variance inflation values, as well as the condition index, are examined.

Variance inflation denotes the factor by which multicollinearity increases the variance of a parameter estimator. Minimum variance inflation value and maximum tolerance value are 1 if the indicators are totally independent of one another. A high variance inflation value or a low tolerance value suggest the existence of multicollinearity. There is no precise threshold value indicating multicollinearity. The frequently applied rule that multicollinearity must be assumed for variance inflation values greater than 10 and tolerance values less than 0.1 must be viewed with scepticism, as a variance inflation value of 10 corresponds to a multiple correlation coefficient of 0.9, indicating that 90 percent of the variance is explained by the other independent variables. Since variance inflation levels greater than 2 can already result in multicollinearity issues, this is the highest limit for multicollinearity diagnosis. Consequently, a value of 0.5 is regarded as the lowest limit for tolerance values, given that multicollinearity issues can emerge with smaller values.

The condition index is a measure of the sensitivity of the solution of linear equations to changes in individual elements. The condition index CI_i is calculated as follows:

$$CI_i = \sqrt{\frac{\lambda_{max}}{\lambda_i}}$$

Where λ_{max} is the largest eigenvalue of an estimator and λ_i is the eigenvalue of the individual estimators. A high condition index indicates the presence of multicollinearity. As a reference value for the condition index, values greater than 30 indicate multicollinearity.

Using t-values and significances, the formative and reflective measurement models are evaluated lastly. Since there are no distribution measures, so-called resampling procedures are utilised to calculate the t-values and significances, which yield approximation t-statistics. The most prevalent resampling techniques are the jackknife and bootstrap procedures. For quality evaluation, the bootstrap approach is preferred to the jackknife method due to its smaller standard error. This work uses the bootstrap approach for this purpose. Using bootstrapping, portions of the data matrix are omitted from the estimating process and then recreated using the estimated parameters. This is performed iteratively for each matrix data point in order to determine the standard errors and t-values of the parameters based on the results. Assuming a direction of impact for the effects of the indicators on the constructs, a one-sided t-test is conducted to establish significance.

Table 12 Measures of validity and criteria of the measurement model

Validity measures and criteria	Aspiration level
Indicator reliability for each item of the measurement model: (1) loading and (2) significance.	(a) loading ≥ 0.7 , possibly ≥ 0.6 (b) t-value > 2.58 (two-sided) at 1% level; > 1.96 (two-sided) at 5% level; > 1.65 (two-sided) at 10% level
Convergence criteria for the measurement model: (1) AVE and (2) composite reliability (construct reliability, internal consistency) and (3) Cronbach's alpha.	(a) AVE > 0.5 (b) Composite reliability > 0.7 (c) CI = Cronbach's $\alpha > 0.7$
Discriminant validity: (1) Fornell-Larcker criterion (for the measurement model) and (2) unidimensionality (for each item of the measurement model).	(1) AVE $>$ highest magnitude of squared correlations of the latent construct with other latent constructs, and (2) higher correlation of the of the indicator index with the defined latent construct than with other latent constructs.

If the measurement model shows adequate for explaining the constructs, the next stage is to evaluate the quality of **the structural model** and, consequently, the **validity** of the proposed hypotheses. Here, too, the model's parameters must be verified. In a subsequent phase, the stability and prediction capacity of the corresponding explanatory model will be evaluated.

In the first step, the coefficient of determination R^2 of the latent variables is examined. The R^2 indicates which part of the variance is explained by the exogenous variables. The higher the value of the R^2 , the more variance is explained by the model. Since the number of independent variables influences the value of the R^2 , the R^2_{corr} corrected for the number of variables is also used to assess the model. The corrected R^2 is calculated as follows:

$$R^2_{corr} = \frac{1 * (1 - R^2)}{N - 1 - 1}$$

where N is the number of observed values and 1 is the number of directly preceding exogenous variables (Backhaus et al., 2006, p. 24).

Furthermore, the estimated parameters are also assessed in the structural model on the basis of their t-values and significance, which were generated using the bootstrap procedure (Venaik et al., 2004). Additionally, the strength of influence of each independent variable should be evaluated. Sellin and Keeves (1994) state that all path coefficients with a value greater than 0.1 have a non-negligible influence in the model (Sellin and Keeves, 1994, p. 4356). To be able to assess the influence of the individual latent variables on the dependent variables, the effect strength f^2 is also used. The effect size indicates the changes in R^2 when variables are eliminated or added (Cohen, 1988):

$$f^2 = \frac{R_{incl}^2 - R_{excl}^2}{1 - R_{incl}^2}$$

The effect size is calculated by calculating the structural model once including (R_{incl}^2) and once excluding (R_{excl}^2) the independent variables under consideration. Values for f^2 of 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35 indicate whether an independent latent variable exerts a weak, moderate or substantial influence on the endogenous variable related to it (Chin, 1998a).

In order to capture the whole relationship structure of the model, the total effects of the independent variables are evaluated, which take into account both the direct and indirect links between the variables. The so-called total effects are computed by summing the direct and indirect impacts, with indirect effects resulting from the multiplication of successive direct effects (Birkinshaw et al., 1995).

Using cross-validation, the predictive validity of the models is then evaluated. Either two independent samples or the existing sample can be divided for cross-validation (Cooil et al., 1987). Due to the limited amount of data accessible for this study topic, the existing sample has been divided. The cases are typically distributed at random to an estimation sample and a holdout sample, with the suggestion for the allocation being to assign 75% of the cases to the estimation sample and 25% to the holdout sample. The estimation sample is used to estimate the model (Hansen, 1987), while the values of the latent variables are calculated from the data of the holdout sample and the parameters estimated with the estimation sample. The correlation coefficient r between the calculated values from the holdout sample and the actual observed values is then calculated. A high value for the correlation r means a high part of

explained variance r^2 by the model. The smaller the difference between the R^2 and the r^2 , the higher the predictive strength of the model (Chin and Todd, 1995).

Next, the inner structural model's forecast or estimation relevance is evaluated for quality. The predictive relevance describes how effectively the model and parameter estimates can reconstruct the empirical data (Chin, 1998b, p. 317). For the reuse of data, the quality criterion relies on the cross-validation and Stone-Geisser tests (Stone, 1974, Geisser, 1974). Formally, forecast relevance can be represented as follows:

$$Q^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_D E_D}{\sum_D O_D}$$

The forecast relevance is calculated via the blind folding procedure, in which the sum of the squared errors is determined for both the estimated values (E) and the original values (O) (Tenenhaus et al., 2005). In the presented formula, the index (D) in turn describes the distance between the cases to be omitted and the cases to be estimated (Schloderer et al., 2009, p.586).

If the Q^2 values are in the positive range ($Q^2 > 0$), it can be assumed that the study model is relevant for forecasting. If the values are less than zero ($Q^2 < 0$) it cannot be assumed that the indicators are relevant for estimation (Ringle et al., 2005).

As before for the f^2 value, changes in the results for Q^2 can be used to determine the relative influence of the relationships in the structural model on the observed values of latent endogenous variables:

$$q^2 = \frac{Q_{included}^2 - Q_{excluded}^2}{1 - Q_{included}^2}$$

This allows to determine whether, for a given endogenous latent variable to be analysed, other latent variables in the inner path model have a small (q^2 by 0.02), medium (q^2 by 0.15) or large (q^2 by 0.35) influence on the forecast relevance (Schloderer et al., 2009, p.586).

Table 13 Measures of validity and criteria of the structural model

Validity measures and criteria	Aspiration level
Multicollinearity via the VIF	For each endogenous construct, which is determined by two or more latent variables applies: VIF \leq 5
Relevance of the model relationships: (1) path coefficients β and (2) their significance	(1) $\beta > 0.1$ (2) t-value > 2.58 (two-sided) at 1% level; > 1.96 (two-sided) at 5% level; > 1.65 (two-sided) at 10% level
Prediction precision: (1) coefficient of determination R^2 and (2) effect size f^2 .	(1) $R^2 \geq 0.1$ (depending on the field of research) (2) $f^2 = 0.02$ (low); 0.15 (medium); 0.35 (high)
Predictive relevance: (1) Stone-Geisser's Q^2 and (2) its effect size q^2	(1) $Q^2 > 0$ (2) $q^2 = 0.02$ (low); 0.15 (medium); 0.35 (high)

3.9 Specification of the PLS path model

3.9.1 Specification of the structural model

The Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement from Busselle and Bilandzic (2008) forms the basis of the theory presented. The model will be used to describe the influence of the individual design characteristics (success factors) on attitude change. This concept represents the model's reliant dependent target variable. The measurement scale developed by Busselle and Bilandzic (2009) is used for this purpose. This section is subdivided into Understanding, Attentional Focus, Narrative Presence, and Emotional Engagement. Each of them is examined for the presence of relevant questions from the existing, already-verified scale. Notably, both the Understanding and Attentional Focus constructs are asked negatively. Creation Understanding, Creation Attentional Focus, Creation Narrative Presence, and Creation Emotional Engagement each influence the dependent variables Understanding, Attentional Focus, Narrative Presence, and Emotional Engagement (independent variables). In addition, it is assumed that the brand impression has a decisive impact on attitudes. Because if a brand impression is already positive, it is difficult for a commercial to induce a large positive attitude shift toward this brand.

Consequently, brand impression is an independent variable that has a direct influence on the dependent goal variable of attitude change. Figure 26 illustrates the constructs and their relationships, thus providing the structural model for the PLS research.

Figure 26 Specified Structural Model

3.9.2 Specification of the measurement models

Because constructs cannot be directly observed, a measurement model is defined for every construct. The specification of the measurement models (i.e., multi-item vs. single-item measures and reflecting vs. formative measurements) is taken in part from the scale of Busselle and Bilandzic (2009) and partly derived as design elements in chapter 3.1.1. The construct of attitude change is derived from the difference between pre- and post-commercial attitude measurements.

The present model contains ten constructs. One of them (Brand Impression) is measured with a single item. All other constructs (Creation Understanding, Creation Attentional Focus, Creation Narrative Presence, Creation Emotional Engagement,

Understanding, Attentional Focus, Narrative Presence, Emotional Engagement and Attitude Change) are measured with multiple items. Understanding, Attentional Focus, Narrative Presence, Emotional Engagement and Attitude Change have reflectively specified measurement models, as indicated by the arrows pointing from the construct to the indicators. For example, the construct Understanding is measured using the three reflective indicators Understanding_1, Understanding_2 and Understanding_3, which relate to the following questions: “I have an unclear picture of the people and events in the commercial.”, “At some points I found it difficult to understand what is happening.” and “I found it difficult to find the red thread in the commercial.”.

Respondents should indicate the extent of their agreement or disagreement with these statements on a 5-point scale from 1 = strongly agree to 5 = strongly disagree.

In contrast to Creation Understanding, Creation Attentional Focus, Creation Narrative Presence, Creation Emotional Engagement, Understanding, Attentional Focus, Narrative Presence, Emotional Engagement and Attitude Change, the construct for Brand Impression is operationalised via a single item (Impression), which refers to the following question in the questionnaire: “How would you describe your impression of the brand?” The answers were given on a 5-point scale measuring the degree of positivity or negativity from 1 = negative, 2 = rather negative, 3 = neutral, 4 = rather positive to 5 = positive. Since Impression is the only item measuring brand impression, the construct and item are identical (this is evident from the fact that the relationship between the construct and the single-item measurement is always equal to one in the PLS-SEM). The choice of measurement perspective (i.e., reflective vs. formative) thus does not matter and the relationship between construct and indicator is undirected.

Table 14 Indicators of the reflective measurement model for Creation constructs

Creation Understanding	
Understanding_Creation_1	The commercial was clearly structured.
Understanding_Creation_2	The characters were clearly presented.
Understanding_Creation_3	The commercial was understandable overall.
Creation Attentional Focus	
AttentionalFocus_Creation_1	I found the commercial exciting.
AttentionalFocus_Creation_2	The commercial was visually appealing for me.
AttentionalFocus_Creation_3	For me the commercial was personally relevant.
AttentionalFocus_Creation_4	I liked the length of the commercial.
AttentionalFocus_Creation_5	The background music of the commercial tempted me to follow the commercial.
Creation Narrative Presence	
NarrativePresence_Creation_1	For me, the commercial was credibly presented.
NarrativePresence_Creation_2	I found the story of the commercial to be consistent.
NarrativePresence_Creation_3	I enjoyed watching the commercial.
NarrativePresence_Creation_4	I could put myself in the main character's place.
NarrativePresence_Creation_5	I had the feeling the commercial wanted to influence me.
Creation Emotional Engagement	
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_1	I could identify myself with the main character.
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2	I found the main character to be sympathetic.
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3	I could put myself in the main character's place during the commercial.
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_4	The perspectives of the commercial made it easy for me to put myself in the main character's place.

3.10 Results of the empirical analysis

Following the description of the evaluation approach, the results of the PLS analysis estimation of the explanatory model derived in chapter 3.9 for the influencing and success aspects of storytelling commercials are presented. Since the impact relationship of the hypothetical constructs can only be effectively tested for validity if the measurement model is suitable for measuring the latent variables, the quality of the measurement model is first evaluated so that the structural model's results then be discussed. All analyses were conducted using version 3.3.2 of Smart PLS. For a better comprehension of the results, it is suggested to examine Table 14 concurrently.

3.10.1 Validity of the measurement model for the influencing and success factors of storytelling commercials

In order to assess the measurement model, Table 15 first shows the weights or loadings of the indicators, the t-values determined with the help of the bootstrap procedure and the corresponding significances.

Table 15 Loading overview for the Measurement Model

Construct Indicator	Loading/Weight	Observed t-value	Significance
Attitude Change (reflective)			
Brand_Impression_Difference	0,789	23,799	0,000*
Attribute_6_Difference	0,701	11,598	0,000*
Attribute_7_Difference	0,699	10,006	0,000*
Attribute_8_Difference	0,789	14,435	0,000*
Brand Impression (single item)			
Brand_Impression	1		
Understanding (reflective)			
Understanding_1	0,846	25,543	0,000*
Understanding_2	0,874	41,502	0,000*
Understanding_3	0,881	35,527	0,000*
Attentional Focus (reflective)			
Attentional Focus_1	0,952	94,027	0,000*
Attentional Focus_2	0,946	64,145	0,000*
Attentional Focus_3	0,951	110,854	0,000*
Narrative Presence (reflective)			
Narrative Presence_1	0,877	26,277	0,000*
Narrative Presence_2	0,916	71,613	0,000*
Narrative Presence_3	0,909	58,531	0,000*
Emotional Engagement (reflective)			
Emotional_Engagement_1	0,929	59,292	0,000*
Emotional_Engagement_2	0,951	97,157	0,000*
Emotional_Engagement_3	0,917	62,052	0,000*
Creation Understanding (formative)			
Creation_Understanding_1	0,258	2,610	0,009*

Construct Indicator	Loading/Weight	Observed t-value	Significance
Creation_Understanding_2	0,296	2,523	0,012*
Creation_Understanding_3	0,554	4,999	0,000*
Creation_AttentionalFocus (formative)			
Creation_Attentional_Focus_1	0,445	3,157	0,002*
Creation_Attentional_Focus_2	-0,019	0,130	0,897
Creation_Attentional_Focus_3	-0,105	0,777	0,437
Creation_Attentional_Focus_4	0,674	6,535	0,000*
Creation_Attentional_Focus_5	0,168	1,208	0,227
Creation_NarrativePresence (formative)			
Creation_Narrative_Presence_1	0,246	1,758	0,079
Creation_Narrative_Presence_2	0,051	0,333	0,739
Creation_Narrative_Presence_3	0,540	4,482	0,000*
Creation_Narrative_Presence_4	0,430	3,560	0,000*
Creation_Narrative_Presence_5	-0,091	0,751	0,453
Creation_EmotionalEngagement (formative)			
Creation_Emotional_Engagement_1	0,342	2,467	0,014*
Creation_Emotional_Engagement_2	0,198	2,308	0,021*
Creation_Emotional_Engagement_3	0,501	3,287	0,001*
Creation_Emotional_Engagement_4	0,126	0,820	0,412

Due to their distinct effectiveness features, reflective and formative constructs require separate evaluations of the measurement model.

3.10.1.1 Reflective Measurement Model Evaluation

In the first stage, the **reflective measurement model's** quality is evaluated. The “Attitude Change” construct and its accompanying indicators must be investigated in greater depth for this aim. As can be noted in Table 16, numerous indicators fall below the ~0.7 criterion.

Table 16 Loadings of the construct Attitude Change

Indicator	Loading PLS	Indicator	Loading PLS
Rating_Difference	-0.654	Attribute_6_Difference	0.678
Impression_Difference	0.687	Attribute_7_Difference	0.645
Difference_Difference	0.196	Attribute_8_Difference	0.718
Attribute_1_Difference	0.514	Attribute_9_Difference	0.247
Attribute_2_Difference	0.593	Attribute_10_Difference	0.518
Attribute_3_Difference	0.296	Attribute_11_Difference	0.458
Attribute_4_Difference	0.503	Attribute_12_Difference	0.229
Attribute_5_Difference	0.336		

Consequently, the indicators with the lowest loadings are eliminated progressively, and the model is recalculated after each elimination. Finally, the indicators in Table 17 considerably clarify the concept of attitude change. The model is then calculated further with these indicators.

Table 17 Loadings of the Attitude Change construct after indicator exclusion

Indicator	Loading PLS
Brand Impression Difference	0.789
Attribute 6 Difference	0.701
Attribute 7 Difference	0.699
Attribute 8 Difference	0.789

When analysing the results in Table 15, it is noticeable that the reflective constructs "Attitude Change", "Understanding", "Attentional Focus", "Narrative Presence" and "Narrative Engagement" are highly significantly explained by their indicators.

For further investigation of the reflecting indicators' potential to explain the constructs, their loadings on the respective construct are evaluated. Table 18 examines the loadings of the PLS analysis and a separately performed principal component analysis (PCA) for this purpose. The indicators are deemed adequate for explaining the construct if their loadings surpass 0.707, as more than fifty percent of an indicator's variance is then explained by the construct. Since the loadings of all reflective indicators exceed this amount, they can be measured.

Table 18 Comparison PLS and PCA Loading for the reflective Measurement Model

Construct	Indicator	Loading PLS	Loading PCA
Attitude Change	Brand Impression Difference	0,789	0,708
	Attribute 6 Difference	0,701	0,761
	Attribute 7 Difference	0,699	0,737
	Attribute 8 Difference	0,789	0,722
Understanding	Understanding 1	0,846	0,847
	Understanding 2	0,874	0,882
	Understanding 3	0,881	0,872
Attentional Focus	Attentional Focus 1	0,952	0,952
	Attentional Focus 2	0,946	0,948
	Attentional Focus 3	0,951	0,949
Narrative Presence	Narrative Presence 1	0,877	0,887
	Narrative Presence 2	0,916	0,908
	Narrative Presence 3	0,909	0,908
Emotional Engagement	Emotional Engagement 1	0,929	0,938
	Emotional Engagement 2	0,951	0,957
	Emotional Engagement 3	0,917	0,903

Additional indicators of the reflecting measurement model's quality include Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Both Cronbach's alpha and the Composite Reliability value are more than 0.7 for all reflective constructions, as shown in Table 19. The AVE value exceeds the minimum value of 0.5 for all reflecting structures.

Table 19 Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability and AVE-Value for the Reflective Measurement Model

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE-Value
Attitude Change	0.711	0.818	0.529
Understanding	0.835	0.901	0.752
Attentional Focus	0.946	0.965	0.902
Narrative Presence	0.884	0.928	0.811
Emotional Engagement	0.925	0.952	0.869

The reflected indicators can thus be deemed suitable for measuring the constructs as a whole.

3.10.1.2 Formative Measurement Model Evaluation

For the **formative measurement model**, it is essential to first determine whether convergent validity exists for the formatively stated constructs. For this aim, a redundancy analysis is conducted separately for each important construct. The questionnaire contains the queries of the constructs to be created (“Creation Understanding”, “Creation Attentional Focus”, “Creation Narrative Presence”, and “Creation Emotional Engagement”) by reflectively measured constructs (“Understanding”, “Attentional Focus”, “Narrative Presence” and “Emotional Engagement”), which are based on the “Narrative Engageability Scale” of Busselle and Bilandzic (2009). Now, the association between the relevant formative and reflective constructs is being investigated.

Figure 27 depicts the measuring model developed for formative construct redundancy analysis. In each instance, the "Creation Construct" refers to the formative construct. The Busselle and Bilandzic (2009) scale is the equivalent reflective construct for gauging convergence validity. As can be observed, the path coefficients of all constructs are more than the 0.7 threshold value (for the “Understanding” and “Attentional Focus” constructs, the values are negative because the reflective construct is questioned negatively) and so demonstrate the needed convergence validity.

Figure 27 Redundancy analysis for the formatively specified constructs

The VIF values of the formative indicators are then used to evaluate the collinearity of the indicators of the formative constructs. Only the VIF values of the formative indicators are analysed, as it is expected that the reflective indicators have a strong

correlation amongst themselves. According to Table 20, “Understanding_Creation_2” has the greatest VIF value among formative indicators (3.243). This indicates that all VIF values are less than the threshold value of 5. Thus, it can be inferred that there is no collinearity problem in the estimate of the PLS path model and no critical threshold of collinearity for the formative indicators.

Table 20 VIF-Values of the formative indicators

Formative Indicator	VIF-Value
Understanding_Creation_1	1.987
Understanding_Creation_2	3.243
Understanding_Creation_3	2.620
AttentionalFocus_Creation_1	2.277
AttentionalFocus_Creation_2	2.038
AttentionalFocus_Creation_3	1.657
AttentionalFocus_Creation_4	1.788
AttentionalFocus_Creation_5	1.974
NarrativePresence_Creation_1	1.912
NarrativePresence_Creation_2	2.177
NarrativePresence_Creation_3	1.770
NarrativePresence_Creation_4	1.939
NarrativePresence_Creation_5	1.041
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_1	2.141
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2	1.469
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3	2.810
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_4	2.820

In the final phase of evaluating the formative measurement model, the weights of the formative indicators are analysed in terms of their significance and relevance. For this, the bootstrapping method is employed. Bootstrapping was conducted with 5,000 bootstrap subsamples, without sign modification, and bias-corrected and accelerated (BCa) bootstrapping was used as the confidence interval method at a significance level of 0.05. Since the importance of the weights is the primary focus of the analysis, only the measurement model is discussed below. As a general observation, it should be noted that when the bootstrapping technique is repeated, the results may alter. This is due to the fact that bootstrapping relies on randomly generated samples or

subsamples that vary each time the technique is executed. The discrepancies that occur in the bootstrapping results are minimal for the subsample of 5,000 that was chosen for this study. The t-values for the formative measurement models are analogous to the critical values of the conventional normal distribution for determining whether the coefficients differ significantly from 0. The p-values for formative measurement models must be less than 0.05 to demonstrate significance with a 5 percent error probability (i.e., $\alpha=0.05$).

Table 21 summarises the results for the formatively measured constructs "Creation_Understanding", "Creation_AttentionalFocus", "Creation_NarrativePresence" and "Creation_EmotionalEngagement" and provides the weights estimated using the original sample, the t-values, the p-values and the confidence intervals determined using the BCa approach.

Table 21 Results of the significance test for the weights in formative specified constructs

Construct	Formative indicators	Weights (loading)	t-value	p-value	95% BCa confidence intervals	Significance (p<0.05)?
Creation_Understanding	Understanding_Creation_1	0.227 (0.785)	2.537	0.011	[0.054; 0.408]	Yes
	Understanding_Creation_2	0.289 (0.907)	2.378	0.017	[0.056; 0.540]	Yes
	Understanding_Creation_3	0.588 (0.952)	5.001	0.000	[0.330; 0.801]	Yes
Creation_AttentionalFocus	AttentionalFocus_Creation_1	0.343 (0.856)	3.278	0.001	[0.139; 0.546]	Yes
	AttentionalFocus_Creation_2	0.351 (0.801)	3.586	0.000	[0.161; 0.548]	Yes
	AttentionalFocus_Creation_3	0.103 (0.673)	1.059	0.290	[-0.084; 0.299]	No
	AttentionalFocus_Creation_4	0.457 (0.859)	5.101	0.000	[0.279; 0.632]	Yes
	AttentionalFocus_Creation_5	-0.057 (0.646)	0.587	0.557	[-0.257; 0.120]	No

Construct	Formative indicators	Weights (loading)	t-value	p-value	95% BCa confidence intervals	Significance (p<0.05)?
Creation_NarrativePresence	NarrativePresence_Creation_1	0.181 (0.736)	1.699	0.089	[-0.034; 0.380]	No
	NarrativePresence_Creation_2	0.254 (0.813)	1.843	0.065	[0.008; 0.543]	No
	NarrativePresence_Creation_3	0.488 (0.885)	5.428	0.000	[0.298; 0.654]	Yes
	NarrativePresence_Creation_4	0.280 (0.813)	2.887	0.004	[0.079; 0.460]	Yes
	NarrativePresence_Creation_5	-0.063 (-0.007)	0.807	0.419	[-0.217; 0.086]	No
Creation_EmotionalEngagement	EmotionalEngagement_Creation_1	0.342 (0.867)	2.530	0.011	[0.060; 0.596]	Yes
	EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2	0.198 (0.667)	2.338	0.019	[0.034; 0.363]	Yes
	EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3	0.501 (0.928)	3.248	0.001	[0.193; 0.778]	Yes
	EmotionalEngagement_Creation_4	0.126 (0.843)	0.804	0.422	[-0.162; 0.461]	No

All formative indicators are significant at a 5 percent level, with the exception of “AttentionalFocus_Creation_3”, “AttentionalFocus_Creation_5”, “NarrativePresence_Creation_1”, “NarrativePresence_Creation_2”, “NarrativePresence_Creation_5”, and “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_4”. The loadings for these non-significant indicators are now assessed alongside their t and p values. The loading of the indicator “NarrativePresence_Creation_5” reveals a negative value, which seems reasonable as this indicator inquired whether participants felt persuaded by the commercial. Thus, this indicator works as a control variable, and the measurement

model confirms the hypothesis that the perception of a desired influence interferes with the formation of narrative presence. “AttentionalFocus_Creation_5” has the lowest charge among the non-significant indicators, with a charge of 0.646%. In addition, the p-values for the loadings of these five indicators (“AttentionalFocus_Creation_3”, “AttentionalFocus_Creation_5”, “NarrativePresence_Creation_1”, “NarrativePresence_Creation_2”, and “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_4”) are well below 0.01, indicating that all loadings are statistically significant at the 1% level. Consequently, the indicators remain in the measurement model.

3.10.2 Validity of the structural model for the influencing and success factors of storytelling commercials

Initially, the VIF values of all driving constructs in the structural model are examined for collinearity. As seen in Table 22, VIF values are manifestly below the criterion of 5. Therefore, it can be argued that the structural model does not contain a critical level of collinearity between the driver constructs.

Table 22 VIF values for the structural model

	Attitude Change	Understanding	Attentional Focus	Narrative Presence	Emotional Engagement
Brand Impression	1.051				
Understanding	1.379				
Attentional Focus	1.400				
Narrative Presence	1.735				
Emotional Engagement	1.776				
Creation_Understanding		1.000			
Creation_AttentionalFocus			1.000		
Creation_NarrativePresence				1.000	
Creation_EmotionalEngagement					1.000

After the investigation of collinearity, the path coefficients of the structural model are validated. Considering the relative importance of the external driver categories (Table 23), “Brand Impression”, “Narrative Presence”, and “Emotional Engagement” are the most influential on “Attitude Change”. Understanding and “Attentional Focus” are virtually irrelevant to the concept of attitude change. It should be noted that even

negative path coefficients only indicate an influence on the construct “Attitude Change” and do not permit statements about positive and negative influence, as the indicators “Attribute_6_Difference”, “Attribute_7_Difference”, “Attribute_8_Difference”, and “Impression_Difference” can also have negative values, which only provides a statement about a change. Negative, and therefore deteriorating, values do not exist in this construct, as a negative value implies simply a change on the bipolar scale for the attributes.

Table 23 Path coefficients of the measurement model

	Attitude Change
Brand Impression	0.514
Understanding	-0.012
Attentional Focus	0.036
Narrative Presence	-0.285
Emotional Engagement	-0.110

Because they are comparable to the redundancy analysis for formative constructs, the path coefficients for "creation" constructs are disregarded (please see 3.10.1.2).

The total effects can be used to determine the extent to which the formative constructs (“Creation_Understanding”, “Creation_Attentional_Focus”, “Creation_Narrative_Presence”, and “Creation_Emotional_Engagement”) impact the primary objective variable “Attitude Change” through the mediating constructs (“Understanding”, “Attentional Focus”, “Narrative Presence” and “Emotional Engagement”). “Creation_NarrativePresence” has the greatest effect on “Attitude Change”, as observed (-0.205). The other formative constructs had little (-0.079 and -0.027) or almost no (0.009) impact on attitude change (see Table 24).

Table 24 Total effects of the formative constructs in the measurement model

	Attitude Change
Creation_Understanding	0.009
Creation_Attentional Focus	-0.027
Creation_Narrative Presence	-0.205
Creation_Emotional Engagement	-0.079

By examining the external weights (Table 25), one can determine which variables "drive" the respective formative constructs in particular. It is apparent that especially "Understanding_Creation_3" (0.588; commercial understandable overall) drives the construct "Creation_Understanding". For the construct "Creation_Attentional Focus", "Attentional Focus_Creation_4" (0.457; Pleasant length), "Attentional Focus_Creation_2" (0.351; Visually appealing) and "Attentional Focus_Creation_1" (0.343; Thrilling) are particularly relevant. To elicit "Creation_Narrative Presence", "Narrative Presence_Creation_3" (0.488; Enjoyment), "Narrative Presence_Creation_4" (0.280; Immersion in the main character) and "Narrative Presence_Creation_2" (0.254; Story consistent) seem to have a high relevance.

Table 25 Outer weights of the formative constructs in the measurement model

	Creation_Understanding	Creation_Attentional Focus	Creation_Narrative Presence	Creation_Emotional Engagement
Understanding_Creation_1	0.227			
Understanding_Creation_2	0.289			
Understanding_Creation_3	0.588			
Attentional Focus_Creation_1		0.343		
Attentional Focus_Creation_2		0.351		
Attentional Focus_Creation_3		0.103		
Attentional Focus_Creation_4		0.457		
Attentional Focus_Creation_5		-0.057		
Narrative Presence_Creation_1			0.181	
Narrative Presence_Creation_2			0.254	
Narrative Presence_Creation_3			0.488	

	Creation_ Understanding	Creation_Attentional Focus	Creation_Narrative Presence	Creation_Emotional Engagement
Narrative Presence_ Creation_4			0.280	
Narrative Presence_ Creation_5			-0.063	
Emotional Engagement_ Creation_1				0.342
Emotional Engagement_ Creation_2				0.198
Emotional Engagement_ Creation_3				0.501
Emotional Engagement_ Creation_4				0.126

And for the purpose of establishing the “Creation_EmotionalEngagement” construct, “Emotional_Engagement_Creation_3” (0.501; Empathy with the main character) and “Emotional_Engagement_Creation_1” (0.342; Identification with the main character) are of particular importance.

The variables that have a significant influence at an error probability of 5% on the formative constructs are shown in 3.10.1.2.

Upon analysing the structural model's relationships, a number of path coefficients were found to have much reduced values. To test significance, a bootstrapping approach is employed. Bootstrapping is conducted with no sign modification, 5,000 subsamples, and as a full procedure. In addition, settings for bias-corrected and accelerated (BCa) bootstrap, a two-sided test, and a significance threshold of 0.05 are chosen.

In the results (Table 26), it can be seen that all formative constructs (“Creation Constructs”) have a substantial relationship with their respective reflective constructs, however these reflective constructs do not typically have a significant association with the "Attitude Change" construct. Only the construct “Narrative Presence” is significantly associated with "Attitude Change."

Table 26 Examination of the significance of the path coefficients in the structural model

	Path	t-value	p-value	95% confidence intervals	BCa Significance (p<0.05)?
	coefficient				
Creation_Understanding Understanding	→ -0.781	23.317	0.000	[-0.834; -0.694]	Yes
Creation_Attentional Focus Attentional Focus	→ -0.735	15.420	0.000	[-0.810; -0.612]	Yes
Creation_Narrative Presence Narrative Presence	→ 0.781	19.662	0.000	[0.624; 0.777]	Yes
Creation_Emotional Engagement → Emotional Engagement	0.713	17.788	0.000	[0.619; 0.778]	Yes
Brand Impression Change → Attitude Change	0.514	10.578	0.000	[0.401; 0.592]	Yes
Understanding Change → Attitude Change	-0.012	0.187	0.852	[-0.141; 0.107]	No
Attentional Focus Change → Attitude Change	0.036	0.557	0.578	[-0.091; 0.165]	No
Narrative Presence Change → Attitude Change	-0.285	3.502	0.000	[-0.435; -0.113]	Yes
Emotional Engagement → Attitude Change	-0.110	1.382	0.167	[-0.271; 0.042]	No

The total effects can be observed in Table 27. It reveals that only “Creation_NarrativePresence” influences the construct “Attitude Change” significantly.

Table 27 Examination of the significance of the total effects

	Total effect	t-value	p-value	95% confidence intervals	BCa Significance (p<0.05)?
Creation_Understanding → Attitude Change	0.009	0.185	0.853	[-0.085; 0.110]	No
Creation_Attentional Focus → Attitude Change	-0.027	0.544	0.587	[-0.126; 0.066]	No
Creation_Narrative Presence → Attitude Change	-0.205	3.319	0.001	[-0.321; -0.077]	Yes
Creation_Emotional Engagement → Attitude Change	-0.079	1.340	0.180	[-0.198; 0.031]	No

The next step is to check the R^2 -values of the endogenous latent variables. Since this research is about the study of consumer behaviour, all R^2 -values values above 0.2 are to be considered relevant (Hair et al., 2006). “Attitude Change” has a R^2 -value of **0.343** and thus the measurement model can be considered relevant.

As a further indicator of the validity of the measurement model, the f^2 -value for the effect sizes should be considered. For the assessment of the f^2 -values, the following guideline may be applied: 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35 represent modest, moderate and significant effects of the exogenous latent variables (Cohen, 1988). The following f^2 -values result for the measurement model can be noted:

Table 28 f^2 effect strengths

	f^2 -value
Impression → Attitude Change	0.383
Understanding → Attitude Change	0.000
Attentional Focus → Attitude Change	0.001
Narrative Presence → Attitude Change	0.071
Emotional Engagement → Attitude Change	0.010

Thus, it can be inferred that “Brand Impression” has a significant effect on the endogenous latent variable “Attitude Change”, whereas “Narrative Presence” has a negligible effect. Other concepts appear to have little effect on “Attitude Change”.

Finally, a blind folding is carried out to calculate the Q^2 -values and from these the q^2 effect strengths can be calculated. As can be seen in Table 29, the Q^2 -values for all endogenous constructs are well above 0. This demonstrates the model's predictive validity for endogenous variables.

Table 29 Q^2 effect strengths

	Q^2 -values
Attitude Change	0.158
Understanding	0.462
Attentional Focus	0.486
Narrative Presence	0.412
Emotional Engagement	0.425

The q^2 effect strengths are calculated using the following formula (example for the effect strength of endogenous construct Y_1 on the latent variable Y_3):

$$q^2_{Y_1 \rightarrow Y_3} = \frac{Q^2_{included} - Q^2_{excluded}}{1 - Q^2_{included}}$$

Calculating the excluded Q^2 -values requires repeating the blind folding procedure without the endogenous construct whose q^2 effect strengths are to be determined. This results in the following q^2 effect strengths:

Table 30 q^2 effect strengths of the measurement model

	Attitude Change
Understanding	-0.002
Attentional Focus	-0.002
Narrative Presence	0.026
Emotional Engagement	0.001

Consequently, only “Narrative Presence” shows a modest predictive relationship with the endogenous variable “Attitude Change”.

Figure 28 gives an overview of the explanatory model with the coefficients of determination and path coefficients, whereby relationships with a significant p-value are marked in bold italics.

Figure 28 Results of the structural model

3.10.3 Implication of the results on the established hypotheses

Based on prior findings, the hypotheses can now be evaluated. Table 31 provides a summary of the hypotheses and their validation or rejection based on the analysis results:

Table 31 Hypothesis results

Hypothesis		Analysis result
H₁	A clear structure of the commercial has a significant impact on the construct of creating understanding.	confirmed
H₂	The comprehensible presentation of the commercial's characters has a significant influence on the construct of creating understanding.	confirmed
H₃	The comprehensibility of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating understanding.	confirmed
H₄	Commercial tension has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.	confirmed
H₅	The visually appealing design of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.	confirmed
H₆	The personal relevance of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.	Not confirmed
H₇	A pleasant length of commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.	confirmed
H₈	Background music that increases attention to the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating attentional focus.	Not confirmed
H₉	The credibility of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.	Not confirmed
H₁₀	The consistency of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.	Not confirmed
H₁₁	The perceived enjoyment of watching the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.	confirmed
H₁₂	Immersion in the main character of the commercial has a significant impact on the construct of generating creating Presence.	confirmed
H₁₃	Perceiving the attempted influence of the commercial has a significant negative impact on the construct of creating Narrative Presence.	Not confirmed
H₁₄	Identification with the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.	confirmed
H₁₅	The perceived sympathy for the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.	confirmed

Hypothesis		Analysis result
<i>H₁₆</i>	Perceived empathy with the main character of the commercial has a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.	confirmed
<i>H₁₇</i>	The perspectives of the commercial that support the perceived empathy with the main character have a significant influence on the construct of creating Emotional Engagement.	Not confirmed
<i>H₁₈</i>	The conceptual construct of creating Understanding has a significant influence on the construct of Understanding.	confirmed
<i>H₁₉</i>	The conceptual construct of creating Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of Attentional Focus.	confirmed
<i>H₂₀</i>	The conceptual construct of creating Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of Narrative Presence.	confirmed
<i>H₂₁</i>	The conceptual construct of generating Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct Emotional Engagement.	confirmed
<i>H₂₂</i>	Brand impression has a significant impact on the construct of Attitude Change.	confirmed
<i>H₂₃</i>	The construct of Understanding has a significant impact on the construct of Attitude Change.	Not confirmed
<i>H₂₄</i>	The construct of Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of Attitude Change.	Not confirmed
<i>H₂₅</i>	The construct of Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of Attitude Change.	confirmed
<i>H₂₆</i>	The construct of Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct of Attitude Change.	Not confirmed
<i>H₂₇</i>	The construct of Creation Understanding has a significant impact on the construct of Attitude Change.	Not confirmed
<i>H₂₈</i>	The construct of Creation Attentional Focus has a significant impact on the construct of Attitude Change.	Not confirmed
<i>H₂₉</i>	The construct of Creation Narrative Presence has a significant impact on the construct of Attitude Change.	confirmed
<i>H₃₀</i>	The construct of Creation Emotional Engagement has a significant impact on the construct of attitude change.	Not confirmed

3.10.4 Moderator effect analysis

Theoretically, it is conceivable for the brand impression to have an effect on the individual exogenous constructs, as the brand impression substantially distracts from specific commercial characteristics. For this reason, a moderator analysis is conducted for the “Brand Impression” construct on all exogenous constructs. The two-step approach is adopted for the calculation of the moderation effect, despite the fact that the exogenous constructs are reflectively assessed constructs. This is because the relevance of the moderation effect must be demonstrated in theory, and the common recommendation is to choose this variant (Hair et al., 2006).

Consequently, the model emerges as follows:

Figure 29 Moderator analysis measurement model

In Figure 29, Moderation Effect 1 represents the moderation effect on the "Understanding" construct, Moderation Effect 2 represents the moderation effect on the "Attentional Focus" construct, Moderation Effect 3 represents the moderation effect on the "Narrative Presence" construct, and Moderation Effect 4 represents the moderation effect on the "Emotional Engagement" construct. As a single-item construct, the convergence validity of the construct "Brand Impression" does not need to be validated. By incorporating additional constructs into the path model, the measurement properties of the other path model constructs are altered. The reliability and validity of the measurements are supported by the reevaluation of all measurement models.

Analyses of the magnitudes of the moderator effects follow. It can be anticipated that a negative perception of the brand has an even more detrimental effect on the exogenous construct "Attitude Change" than a poor opinion of the brand itself. A stronger influence of the exogenous construct on the endogenous construct "Attitude Change" corresponds to higher ratings of the brand's impression. This theoretical perspective is reinforced by the fact that the majority of moderation effects have negative loadings, as seen in Table 32.

Table 32 Moderator analysis loadings

	Attitude Change
Moderation Effect 1 (Brand Impression → Understanding)	-0.042
Moderation Effect 2 (Brand Impression → Attentional Focus)	0.045
Moderation Effect 3 (Brand Impression → Narrative Presence)	-0.167
Moderation Effect 4 (Brand Impression → Emotional Engagement)	-0.054

By conducting a slope analysis, the correlations can be shown graphically. Figure 30 shows an example of the correlation for the moderator effect on the construct "Narrative Presence".

Figure 30 Slope analysis Moderator Effect 3

The relationship for the average value of the moderator construct "Brand Impression" is represented by the middle line. The other two lines depict the association between "Narrative Presence" and "Attitude Change" for greater (i.e., mean of "Brand Impression" plus one standard deviation) and lower (i.e., mean of "Brand Impression" minus one standard deviation) "Brand Impression" values. The negative slope of the three lines indicates that "Narrative Presence" and "Attitude Change" have a negative relationship. Higher levels of "Narrative Presence" (which, due to the scaling, corresponds to a lower rating of "Narrative Presence") are therefore accompanied by lower levels of "Attitude Change".

A closer look at the slope reveals the following: The top line has a steeper slope, representing a high level of the moderator construct "Brand Impression" (which, due to the scaling, results in a lower "Brand Impression" rating). In contrast, the slope of the lower line, which denotes a lower level of the moderator construct "Brand Impression" (and therefore, according to the scaling, a higher "Brand Impression" rating), is flatter. The straightforward line graph therefore validates the prior description of the negative interaction term. Higher values (and thus a lower rating) of the "Brand Impression" construct result in a stronger negative association between "Narrative Presence" and "Attitude Change", while lower values (and thus a higher rating) of the "Brand Impression" construct result in a weaker negative relationship.

Finally, significance of the interaction term is evaluated. For this aim, 5,000 bootstrap subsamples are generated with the properties no sign change, full bootstrapping, BCa

bootstrapping, and two-sided test selected. These are the p-values for interaction terms:

Table 33 p-values for the Moderation Effects

	p-value
Moderation Effect 1 (Brand Impression → Understanding)	0.536
Moderation Effect 2 (Brand Impression → Attentional Focus)	0.492
Moderation Effect 3 (Brand Impression → Narrative Presence)	0.035
Moderation Effect 4 (Brand Impression → Emotional Engagement)	0.506

In the Table 33 it can be observed that the negative effect of “Brand Impression” on the relationship between “Narrative Presence” and “Attitude Change” is significant. Consequently, a poor brand impression leads to an even weaker “Narrative Presence” and thereby to a lower attitude change. Finally, we consider the f^2 effect strength for Moderation Effect 3. According to Kenny (2018), this corresponds to a large effect size.

3.10.5 Analysis of Enjoyment

As chapters 3.10.1.2 and 3.10.2 have shown, enjoyment has a significant role in the measurement model. However, it is difficult to make a general recommendation that a commercial should generate enjoyment, so enjoyment will be analysed in more detail subsequently.

First, a multiple regression is conducted to determine whether of the factors considered in this measurement model have a substantial impact on enjoyment as a concept. Selecting “NarrativePresence_Creation_3” (Enjoyment) as the dependent variable. All additional formative variables that are accessible serve as independent variables. A stepwise method is chosen as the strategy for putting up the model since there are several independent variables that might be examined and the restriction to the significant variables is neither possible owing to the research question nor past research (previous research, published studies). In particular, the backward stepwise

technique is selected because it has the lowest probability of omitting influential factors (suppressor effects) (Field, 2013, p. 323).

Table 34 Multiple Regression backward stepwise for the Enjoyment construct – eleventh model

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig.	95% confidence intervals	Significance (p<0.05)?
(Constant)	0.059	0.316	0.752	[-0.309; 0.426]	Not relevant
AttentionalFocus_Creation_1	0.219	2.843	0.005	[0.067; 0.371]	Yes
AttentionalFocus_Creation_5	0.169	2.369	0.019	[0.028; 0.309]	Yes
NarrativePresence_Creation_2	0.354	4.785	0.000	[0.208; 0.499]	Yes
NarrativePresence_Creation_4	0.290	3.736	0.000	[0.137; 0.443]	Yes
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2	0.179	2.385	0.018	[0.031; 0.326]	Yes
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3	-0.201	-2.551	0.012	[-0.356; -0.045]	Yes

The results of the multiple regression for the last (eleventh) model are shown in Table 34. Once the right model has been identified, it is individually recalculated using an inclusion approach so that it may be examined in further depth.

Checking the prerequisites for multiple regression is the first step. The Durbin-Watson test proves the independence of the residuals with a value of 2.092. The statistical study of collinearity reveals that all VIF values are less than 5, indicating that there is no multicollinearity among the coefficients. An evaluation of the condition index in the collinearity diagnosis reveals a value of 11,789 for seven dimensions, which is obviously less than 30, indicating that multicollinearity can also be presumed in this instance. The number of extreme cases does not reach five percent of the total. Figure 31 demonstrates that the points fit extremely well on the straight line, hence a normal distribution can be inferred.

Figure 31 Normal distribution diagram of the residuals

In Figure 32, a point cloud without trend and without funnel can be recognised, so that homoscedasticity and linearity are present.

Figure 32 Scatter plot of the predicted values against the residuals

Thus, all conditions for calculating a regression are satisfied, and the results can be examined.

In the linear regression model with the factors “AttentionalFocus_Creation_1” (Thrilling), “AttentionalFocus_Creation_5” (Background music attracts attention), “NarrativePresence_Creation_2” (Story consistency), “NarrativePresence_Creation_4” (Immersion in the main character), “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2” (Sympathy of the main character) and “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3” (Empathy with the main character) a validity of 0.512 (adjusted R-squared) was achieved, which can be considered very good for models describing human behaviour (see Table 35).

Table 35 Model overview for the Enjoyment construct

R	R ²	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
0.727	0.528	0.512	0.824	2.092

There is evidence of a significant influence for each of the six factors ($p < 0.05$ in each case – see Table 36).

Table 36 Result of the regression model for the coefficients - inclusion method

	B [95%-CI]	Beta	p-value
(Constant)	0.059 [-0.309; 0.426]		0.752
AttentionalFocus_Creation_1	0.219 [0.067; 0.371]	0.199	0.005
AttentionalFocus_Creation_5	0.169 [0.028; 0.309]	0.156	0.019
NarrativePresence_Creation_2	0.354 [0.208; 0,499]	0.311	0.000
NarrativePresence_Creation_4	0.290 [0.137; 0.443]	0.298	0.000
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2	0.179 [0.031; 0.326]	0.145	0.018
EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3	-0.201 [-0.356; -0.045]	-0.187	0.012

The strongest (standardised regression coefficient: 0.311) is “NarrativePresence_Creation_2” (story consistency), followed by “NarrativePresence_Creation_4” (immersion in the main character). With a

standardised regression coefficient of 0.199, "AttentionalFocus_Creation_1" (Thrilling) exerts a little less positive influence. The variables "AttentionalFocus_Creation_5" (background music attracts attention) and "EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2" (sympathy for the main character) have a weaker positive effect than the other variables. Surprisingly, "EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3" (empathy with the protagonist) exerts a somewhat substantial negative effect on enjoyment (standardised regression coefficient -0.201).

4 Conclusion

4.1 Summary of Findings

The objective of the quantitative study was to identify potential success criteria for commercials that affect the audience's perception of the brand or product through storytelling. Key findings from the data include: (a) the observed characteristics that reflectively measure the construct attitude change; (b) whether the constructed "creation" constructs have a significant influence on their theoretically assessable constructs (from the "Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement"); and (c) which of the variables derived from theory and personal considerations significantly "form" the respective "creation" construct in each case; (d) which of the "Narrative Engagement" constructs and whether brand impression influence attitude change, (e) if one or more of the "creation" constructs influence the construct of attitude change, (f) to what extent brand impression moderates other constructs within the measurement model, and (g) which variables influence the perceived enjoyment of watching the commercial.

The first significant finding (a) reveals that just four of the variables measured for attitude change significantly represent the construct and, therefore, comprise the overall construct of "Attitude Change". These variables are: "Attribute_6_Difference" (measures bipolar between interesting and boring), "Attribute_7_Difference" (measures bipolar between attractive and unsightly), "Attribute_8_Difference" (measures bipolar between imaginative and unimaginative) and "Brand_Impression_Difference" (measures from negative to positive).

In addition, the results demonstrate that the "Creation" constructs have a substantial impact on the related constructs of the Narrative Engageability Scale (b). As a result, convergence validity is attributed to all "Creation" constructs. Thus, the theoretically developed indicators are applicable to all "Creation" constructs and accurately characterise the real constructs.

In general, it can be stated that major indicators for each formative "Creation" construct were analysed (c). For the "Creation Understanding" construct, all assigned indicators show a significant influence. Meaning "Understanding_Creation_1" (clear structure), "Understanding_Creation_2" (characters are presented in an understandable way) and "Understanding_Creation_3" (commercial understandable overall) all have a significant influence on the construct "Creation Understanding".

“Attentional_Focus_Creation_1” (thrilling), “Attentional_Focus_Creation_2” (visually appealing) and “Attentional_Focus_Creation_4” (pleasant length) all show a significant influence on the the construct “Creation Attentional Focus”. For the “Narrative Presence Creation” construct, the following indicators show a significant influence: “NarrativePresence_Creation_3” (enjoyment), “NarrativePresence_Creation_4” (immersion in the main character) and “NarrativePresence_Creation_2” (consistent story). Finally, “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_1” (identification with the main character), “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2” (sympathy of the main character) and “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3” (empathy with the main character) influence the construct of “Creation Emotional Engagement” significantly.

On the Narrative Engageability Scale, only “Narrative Presence” has a significant influence on the construct “Attitude Change”. In addition, it has been determined that “Brand Impression” greatly influences the construct “Attitude Change” (d).

Furthermore, out of all the "Creation" constructs, only the “Creation Narrative Presence” construct indicates a significant influence on “Attitude Change” (e).

In addition, the study discovered that “Brand Impressions” significantly moderate the “Narrative Presence” construct. Lower “Brand Impression” scores correlate with lower “Narrative Presence” scores (f).

The analysis of enjoyment using multiple regression (g) showed that “NarrativePresence_Creation_2” (consistent story) has the largest significant positive effect on enjoyment followed by “NarrativePresence_Creation_4” (immersion in the main character), “AttentionalFocus_Creation_1” (thrilling), “AttentionalFocus_Creation_5” (background music entices attention) and “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_2” (sympathy of the main character). “EmotionalEngagement_Creation_3” (empathy with the main character) surprisingly shows a negative significant effect on enjoyment.

4.2 Reflection on literature review

To effectively use owned communication channels (chapter 2.2.3), this study has analysed various success factors for storytelling commercials for companies that want to distribute commercials on their own communication channels. As described in chapter 2.7, there are several scientific studies that examine the aspects that

influence narrative advertisements. Using a different theoretical framework, “The Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement” (Busselle and Bilandzic, 2008) in combination with a structural equation model analysis in the form of a PLS analysis, this study was able to corroborate the known success factors by presenting the storytelling commercials via a CMC (see chapter 2.2.5) communicational way. Thus, the findings of Karpinska-Krakowiak and Eisend (2020), Li and Liu (2020), Van Laer et al. (2018), Lee and Jeong (2017), Appel and Mara (2013), Tukachinsky and Tokunaga (2013), Bhatnagar and Wan (2011) and Addis and Holbrook (2010) on the significance of audience identification with the main character were reaffirmed. In addition, the enjoyment of watching was analysed as a significant component in accomplishing attitude change. This appears to validate the findings of Rodgers and Stemmler (2020), Su et al. (2018), Kim et al. (2017) and Ching et al. (2013) research that have highlighted emotionality as a success element. Due to the emotive nature of the advertisements, it may be assumed that this will also improve their virality (earned communication) in addition to influencing attitudes. This is supported by Dafonte Gómez (2014), Hsieh et al. (2012), Guadagno et al. (2013) and Nelson-Field et al. (2013) investigations (see chapter 2.4.3.2). The study's finding that storytelling commercials can achieve an attitude change in the viewer is also consistent with Woodside et al. (2008) finding that storytelling commercials can lead to a positive association with the brand. This can also lead to a so-called self-brand connection (Escalas, 2004) (chapter 2.3.4). In addition, the success factor of enjoyment while watching the commercials is consistent with the model of Entertainment on the Internet by Schweiger and Beck (2019) and Vorderer et al. (2004) Entertainment Experience in particular (chapter 2.2.5.1). By adhering to the mentioned success elements, corporations may generate so-called HERO content (chapter 2.3.3) for YouTube. However, this material may be shared not just on YouTube, but also on Instagram and other significant social media platforms (see Figure 15).

4.3 Implications for entrepreneurial practice

Due to their length and ease of sharing, storytelling commercials are primarily viewed online via YouTube or other social media platforms, where firms maximise their viral potential (chapter 2.4) as a below-the-line communication channel (chapter 2.2.3). Overall, the analysis revealed that storytelling commercials, as a form of computer-mediated communication (chapter 2.2.2.7) (with the advertiser as the message's sender and the viewer as its receiver), are a successful and effective advertising

strategy to impact and alter the consumer's perception of a brand or product, at least in the short term.

This study demonstrates that the value of “Brand Impression” should be emphasised in general. Naturally, it is difficult for brands with a positive brand impression to improve an already positive customer attitude towards the brand or product. This indicates, however, that this research is mainly relevant to brands that tend to have negative customer attitudes toward the brand or product. Especially for these organisations, the usage of story-based commercials created in accordance with the principles of this study has the potential to significantly improve the customer's attitude.

According to the research, the only component that has a substantial influence on attitude change is the “Narrative Presence” out of “The Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement”, it is recommended that extra attention be devoted to designing and creating the “Narrative Presence” when creating commercials that tell a narrative. To develop this "Narrative Presence", three aspects of commercials that successfully activate this construct were analysed. The viewer's enjoyment of the video, their immersion into the main character, and their perception of a consistent narrative. Having a solid understanding of your intended audience is crucial for character creation, so that viewers can identify with the primary character and see themselves in his or her position. This also indicates that animals, infants, animated characters or children should not be used as the main character, as it could be hard for the audience to immerse into them. This can inhibit the desired effect of positively affecting attitudes. Before developing content, businesses should do a thorough analysis of their target audience. This can prevent the production of content that has little or, in the worst-case scenario, a detrimental effect on the perception of a brand or product. In addition, content that is unsuited for target audiences cannot be improved through costly visual work-up, nor can their objective of altering attitudes be advanced. Creating enjoyment while watching the commercial is apparent at first glance, but a clear recommendation is lacking. Therefore, additional research has yielded clear recommendations for creating enjoyment while watching the commercial. It is crucial to give the audience a straightforward, coherent narrative that does not confuse them. A narrative lacking a coherent beginning, explanation of the characters, and conclusion is ineffective. Several research on the composition and structure of successful storytelling ads have revealed that they typically share a similar

composition and structure, resembling the hero's journey by employing different archetypes. Obviously, involving the audience with the main character is also essential to producing delight. This relates back to the earlier recommendation regarding the necessity of a target group analysis. The captivating design of the commercial and the background music that ensures the viewer's attention also contribute to this. The background music must support the story's structure and so establish the required suspense arc and support the commercial's emotionality. The main character's sympathy has a small but crucial influence in establishing satisfaction in the commercial. This is one reason why so many advertisements employ celebrities. In most cases, these are sympathetic to numerous individuals. However, in the context of storytelling commercials, celebrities can be counterproductive and are therefore rarely used. On the one hand, it is difficult for the audience to identify with and empathise with celebrities, and on the other hand, many celebrities are identified with particular characteristics or events. The research also revealed that the audience shouldn't feel too much empathy for the main character, as this can diminish enjoyment. This can be especially true if the primary character in the commercial is in peril. Most likely, empathising during these periods does not enhance the experience of viewing the commercial, but rather induces negative emotions. Creating "Narrative Presence" in the audience requires a consistent narrative as well as for eliciting viewer's enjoyment. This implies that the plot must have a logical progression and no confusing, disconnected leaps should occur. It implies that the behaviours of all characters must be explicable by the characters themselves or be logically deducible. In addition, particular schemata of the target audience should be served in order to establish a right "situation model" for the viewer more rapidly. This recommendation aligns closely with the so-called "Situation model" "Story world" of the "Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement" concept. All of these content requirements do not preclude the possibility of developing fictitious content, i.e., content that does not match to reality. For instance, as long as the aforementioned rules are followed, the advertisement that tells a narrative can also be classified as science fiction. Even in the realm of film, it is obvious that films in which the audience can easily relate do not necessarily have to be highly realistic. Lord of the Rings and Star Wars are the best examples. However, both films comply to the previously described design principles, which include likeable main characters, a clear story framework, and the creation of spectator delight, not least through well suited background music.

By adhering to the design requirements of this study, it is feasible to create Hero Content (chapter 2.3.3) that inspires Self-Brand Connection (chapter 2.3.4), which, according to academic research, can result in improved brand attitudes and, ultimately, increased purchasing behaviour (see chapter 2.3.4). Sharing the commercial can also promote virality and provide an entertainment experience for the viewer.

4.4 Implications for research and academic education

The research project's findings indicate that the research methodology is fundamentally adequate for explaining the performance of commercials that convey stories in terms of attitude change. On the basis of the outcomes and constraints of the explanatory models, content and methodology implications for future research initiatives can be derived.

In **terms of content**, the results indicate that the “Model of Narrative Comprehension and Engagement” and the corresponding “Narrative Engageability Scale” only significantly contribute to the explanation of the viewer's attitude change with one of the four elements. It could be interesting to study other theories in relation to narrative persuasion in the explanatory model, such as Green and Brock (2000) model of Transportation. In this situation, it would be necessary to develop unambiguous characteristic factors and scales that create or originate the theory.

Since the “Narrative Presence” factor was the only one to have a substantial effect on attitude change, future research should focus on this factor. Particularly pertinent are the formative factors that produce this component.

The study demonstrates that the indicators obtained from theory and self-reflection that generate the "Creation" construct have a significant and important effect on their respective factor of the “Narrative Engageability Scale”. As not all indicators were determined to be relevant for their respective "Creation" construct, it may be worthwhile to investigate more potential indicators, particularly for the “Narrative Presence” construct.

In this study, the enjoyment indicator was determined to be highly relevant to attitude change. When investigating this indicator in greater depth, it was determined that if other detected indications have a substantial effect on the feeling of enjoyment, several indicators have been discovered as having a substantial impact on enjoyment.

In future research, other indicators that have an impact on the enjoyment construct and can therefore play a crucial role in attitude change can be investigated. In the course of this, additional research should investigate if empathy with the main character actually has a detrimental effect on enjoyment and, if so, under what commercial attributes this phenomenon occurs.

Immersion in the main character was analysed as a success factor of storytelling commercials. To provide even clearer design recommendations, additional research should explore which aspects of a commercial specifically generate this emotion in the viewer.

“Brand impression” was acknowledged as a significant element. More research should be undertaken independently for each type of brand impression so that appropriate recommendations may be made for brands with a positive brand impression and brands with a negative brand impression.

It would also be interesting to determine the extent to which the content of commercials based on narratives is capable of altering consumer behaviour in terms of cognitive processes (chapter 2.1.3) in the form of schemata and habitual purchase behaviour.

Furthermore, from a **methodological** standpoint, the results offer useful insights for future research. The specification of explanatory models for the success factors of storytelling commercials in multi-equation structural models has proven to be fundamentally valuable, as the success factors are hypothetical entities that must be quantified using relevant indicators. The distinction between latent and manifest variables necessitates rigorous conception and operationalization of the model, in which the nature of the constructs has a decisive impact on the research outcomes. A considerable proportion of the constructs have a formative nature, as the purpose of this success factor study is to measure the effectiveness of storytelling commercial characteristics and design features on attitude transformation. The usage of formative structures has the benefit of deriving specific recommendations for the design of storytelling commercials. As the validity of formative conceptions is heavily dependent on content-related considerations, substantial content-related preparation is required for formative operationalisation. Through redundancy analysis, these issues can be tested with existing scales rather effectively. In the field of the formative measurement model, despite thorough examination of the content, it can be argued that not all indicators demonstrate a significant influence on their respective assigned construct.

The presence of weak or unmeasurable correlations indicates a shift in the construct's content, which must be taken into account when interpreting the results.

These findings suggest that, for future or ongoing research initiatives, the thorough formulation of the measuring model should be prioritised, particularly in the domain of success factor research. Exogenous constructs can be believed to be largely formative because this is the only way to evaluate success-enhancing measures. Therefore, preliminary content considerations incorporating validated theories, or a qualitative research stage are especially necessary for the operationalization of formative constructs, as missing or insignificant indicators result in a modification of the model's content. Inaccurate specification of constructs might lead to the omission of crucial success factor features and, consequently, to inaccurate content outputs.

Due to the usage of both formative and reflective constructs as well as the small number of examples, the partial least squares approach has proven to be the only appropriate analytical method for estimating the model. With the partial least squares approach based on the least squares estimate, the focus of the analysis is on the predictive power of the model and the assessment of the anticipated success variables' effect strength. This results in the loss of statistically desirable properties such as the consistency of the estimators and the test of the overall model, but it makes it possible to estimate complex structures without specific model assumptions and estimating statements regarding the forecasting ability of substructures.

In addition, based on the results, the virality of optimised social media advertisements can be evaluated. The chapters 2.2.5 and 2.4 provide the foundation for these investigations. The virality of ads developed based on the findings of this thesis should be greater than that of comparable commercials not designed based on the characteristics of this thesis.

Aside from the broad theory on the subdivision of communication channels, the **academic education** of marketing communication should emphasise the actual application of theories. This study might provide an initial impulse and practical consequences about storytelling. Storytelling is a topical issue in the world of marketing, not only in the academic environment but also in business settings. In academic education, students should be taught, particularly in the domain of storytelling, how storytelling may be utilised as a successful marketing technique. This is especially true for the creation of these narrative marketing strategies. Consequently, it is essential to discuss the significance of content itself and the

relevance of content marketing. Persuasion, and especially narrative persuasion, should be handled in particular in light of this. This leads inexorably to the merging of marketing and psychology. The field of narrative persuasion is underrepresented in academic teaching at present. Students should be taught the key models and theories described in this study at a fundamental level. On this basis, the conclusions of this thesis should be taught in relation to the creation of content and what should receive special attention. This study's conclusions can be used to the creation of content, notably the exact comprehension of the target audience, the consistency of the plot, and the enjoyment of the spectator. As this study demonstrates, students should be made aware that the use of children and animals in storytelling advertisements may not be beneficial. Moreover, an aesthetically pleasing commercial design cannot compensate for a convoluted plot. And throughout advertisements based on empathy, effort must be made to ensure that the main character does not undergo any negative experiences, as this can diminish the enjoyment value.

4.5 Limitations

Following the derivation of specific recommendations for the design of storytelling commercials, this part outlines the primary limitations of this study while also providing specific directions for further research.

Certainly, the sample population is a concern. The sample lacks diversity. All of the participants in the study were German, therefore the findings may be country specific. On the other hand, the bulk of participants fall within the same age bracket. Consequently, the suggestions for action in another older age group may differ from those examined in this study.

In general, the socio-demographic features of the sample are extremely specific and offer limited space for generalisation of the findings. However, this study's sample closely reflects the target market requested by many businesses: Young, highly educated, and with a decent income.

All the selected commercials were produced by large corporations, so it may be difficult to apply the action recommendations to small and medium-sized businesses.

The specification of the construct attitude change by the difference in three attributes plus the difference in brand impression is an operationalization with few indicators. Therefore, commercials that produce a change in these indicators may be given a

disproportionately large weight in the results. For future study, it should be sought to operationalize the concept of attitude change using additional indicators.

The recommendation that empathising with the main character can have a negative impact on enjoyment must be interpreted in a nuanced manner due to the fact that the advertisements in this study can occasionally be tense or contain unpleasant emotions. In the Volvo commercial, for instance, a young girl was nearly run over.

4.5.1 Limitations of formative approaches in structural equation models

By estimating the initial data as precisely as feasible, the PLS method is ideally suited for use in predicting. In contrast to machine learning algorithms, forecasting occurs in the context of a user-specified causal model based on theoretical concerns (Hair et al., 2021). Because of this, the PLS method is sometimes known as causal-predictive (Joreskog and Wold, 1982). In contrast, the covariance-analytical method is often inappropriate for predicting. This is due to the indeterminacy of the construct values in the setting of a LISREL study, which implies that the same factor model may be replicated with a variety of construct values. In theory, a factor model may therefore fully predict any variable (Schönemann and Haagen, 1987). Regarding the application of causal models to the development of practical suggestions for action, this constraint is seen as severe, as the accompanying recommendations are always predictive in nature (Sarstedt and Danks, 2022). Nonetheless, there are a number of constraints that must be taken into account in the context of formative measuring methods. This is a list of them.

Errors in measurements caused by an insufficient model definition

In the reflective method, correlations between the dependent variable and the error variable might be understood as "actual" measurement mistakes since the measurement variable correlates with the error variable, whilst the construct (independent variable) is uncorrelated with the errors. In contrast, correlations between the dependent variable and the error variable in the formative approach cannot be interpreted as measurement errors because the construct (i.e., the true value) correlates with the error variable, whereas the measured values (independent variable) are uncorrelated with the errors.

Different variances

Moreover, the basic equation of the formative measurement model predicts that the variance of the "real values" is higher than the variance of the observed values, assuming the premise. In contrast, with the reflective method, the variation of the measured values is higher than the variance of the construct, which is why Jarvis et al. (2003) refer to an extra meaning of the measured values that extends beyond the measurement of the construct (surplus meaning).

The issue of multicollinearity

Since the estimate of formative models is essentially a multiple regression, multicollinearity (i.e., a high linear dependence between the indicators) leads to both content and technical difficulties: This results in a non-robust estimation of the model on the one hand, and systematic underestimation of the regression weights for strongly correlated variables, since they "share" the explanatory content (Backhaus et al., 2021). If two indicators Y_1 and Y_2 are highly correlated and Y_1 has marginally more explanatory power for the latent construct, only Y_1 will have a significant regression weight when constructing the model using Y_1 and Y_2 . Even though the indicator Y_2 has somewhat less explanatory power, it is not assigned a substantial regression weight.

Estimation and identifiability of formative measurement models

In isolation, formative models are always empirically underidentified (Bollen and Lennox, 1991). In a pure formative measurement model, there is only one equation for measuring the parameters (Figure 33), hence it is impossible to estimate the measurement equation. Consequently, it is impossible to estimate the model parameters without integrating them into a causal model and considering them in connection to other constructs.

Figure 33 Pure formative measurement model

Due to the estimation of construct values, PLS may directly estimate formative measurement models, whereas the covariance analysis technique offers only two opportunities to experimentally estimate formative measurement models:

1. Incorporation of the construct to be assessed formatively into a so-called nomological network including additional constructs impacted by the formative construct, but which are themselves measured reflectively.
2. Multiple Indicators, Multiple Causes (MIMIC) model development, in which reflective indicators are attributed to formative constructs. Global indicators or "full" reflective measurement models are utilised.

There are two issues with the incorporation of a formative measurement model into a nomological network. First, this does not ensure the model's identifiability until at least two routes lead to reflectively measurable constructs (Diamantopoulos and Winklhofer, 2001). Furthermore, Wilcox et al. (2008) note that the selection of causally dependent constructs influences the regression coefficients of the same formative indicators and, consequently, the empirical relevance of the concept. Similarly, Aguirre-Urreta et al. (2016) demonstrate that the semantic content of a formative concept is determined by its location in a nomological network. Franke et al. (2008) demonstrate that even with similar operationalization of the formative notions, it is difficult to compare research or their results.

The use of MIMIC models, on the other hand, appears to be less problematic: since the content is assessed through the reflective indicators assigned to a construct, it is assured that the same item is constantly examined, and so research may be compared. Thus, a typical guideline for working with formative models is to constantly include reflective reference indicators (MacKenzie et al., 2005). However, the error term of the formative measurement model is dictated by the quality of the reflective reference indicators when utilising MIMIC models. In light of these and other factors, the incorporation of formative measurement models into MIMIC models is contentious in the literature (Cadogan et al., 2013, Diamantopoulos and Temme, 2013, Lee et al., 2013).

The difficulty was addressed in this study by incorporating a redundancy analysis (Figure 27) into the measurement model to establish the formative measurement model's convergence validity.

Problems in the context of formative measurement model quality testing

As the indicators are determined exogenously as independent variables, correlations between indicators cannot be explained by the model in formative measurement models. Consequently, measuring reliability and validity is more challenging than with reflective measurement techniques. Particularly, it is typically impossible to verify internal consistency reliability, hence other criteria must be utilised to determine validity. Moreover, following estimation of a formative model, totally various constellations of sign and height of the regression coefficients may arise, which cannot be justified theoretically in this manner. In the reflective model, however, all path coefficients are anticipated to have positive signs. For this reason, the evaluation of internal consistency in the formative method is inappropriate, as even negative indicators may be content-justified. If the evaluation of two indicators yields one good and one negative result, this does not imply that one indication is more content-relevant than the other, nor can it be extrapolated which indicators should be eliminated. In this instance, it simply indicates that both indicators reveal distinct elements of the construct and are not synchronised.

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6 Appendix

6.1 Questionnaire

Translated from German into English

Which gender do you belong to?

- Female
- Male
- Diverse

Which age group do you belong to?

- 17 or younger
- 18 – 20
- 21 – 29
- 30 – 39
- 40 – 49
- 50 – 59
- 60 or older

Please rank the following brands (1 Rank = best place, 5 Rank = worst place):

Participants could sort five related brands here

What would you call your rating of Brand X?

- I do not like it at all
-
-
- neither nor
-
-
- I like it very much

Please name three words that you associate with Brand X:

What is your overall impression of Brand X?

- negative
- rather negativ
- neutral

- rather positive
- positive

Brand X is markedly different from other brands:

- do not agree at all
- rather not agree
- neither nor
- I rather agree
- fully agree

Please evaluate brand X on the basis of the following bipolar characteristics:

<input type="checkbox"/>				
modern				traditional
<input type="checkbox"/>				
high quality				simple
<input type="checkbox"/>				
expensive				cheap
<input type="checkbox"/>				
self-confident				shy
<input type="checkbox"/>				
playful				adult
<input type="checkbox"/>				
interesting				boring
<input type="checkbox"/>				
attractive				ugly
<input type="checkbox"/>				
inventive				uninspired
<input type="checkbox"/>				
offensive				defensive
<input type="checkbox"/>				
extraordinary				average
<input type="checkbox"/>				
emotional				objective
<input type="checkbox"/>				
humorous				serious

PARTICIPANTS WATCHING THE COMMERCIAL AT THIS POINT

To what extent do you agree with the following statements regarding the commercial?

Construct Understanding (analogous to the Narrative Engageability Scale by Busselle and Bilandzic) – THIS WAS NOT STATED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

I have an unclear picture of the people and events in the commercial.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

At some points I found it difficult to understand what is happening.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I found it difficult to find the red thread in the commercial.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

Construct Understanding Creation – THIS WAS NOT STATED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

The commercial was clearly structured.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

The characters were clearly presented.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

The commercial was understandable overall.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

Construct Attentional Focus (analogous to the Narrative Engageability Scale by Busselle and Bilandzic) – THIS WAS NOT STATED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

My thoughts kept drifting away while I was watching.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

While looking I noticed that I was thinking of something else.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

It was hard for me to focus my thoughts only on the commercial.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

Construct Attentional Focus Creation – THIS WAS NOT STATED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

I found the commercial exciting.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

The commercial was visually appealing for me.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

For me the commercial was personally relevant.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I liked the length of the commercial.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

The background music of the commercial tempted me to follow the commercial.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

Construct Narrative Presence (analogous to the Narrative Engageability Scale by Busselle and Bilandzic) – THIS WAS NOT STATED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

While watching, my body was in the room, but my mind was in the middle of the world that the commercial created.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

In some parts of the commercial the world of the story was closer to me than the "real world".

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

The commercial created a new world for me, and it suddenly disappeared when the commercial ended.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

Construct Narrative Presence Creation – THIS WAS NOT STATED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

For me, the commercial was credibly presented.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I found the story of the commercial to be consistent.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I enjoyed watching the commercial.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I could immerse myself in the main character.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I had the feeling the commercial wanted to influence me.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

Construct Emotional Engagement (analogous to the Narrative Engageability Scale by Busselle and Bilandzic) – THIS WAS NOT STATED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

What was described in the commercial triggered emotions in me.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

The commercial touched me emotionally.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I felt with the character during the commercial.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

Construct Emotional Engagement Creation – THIS WAS NOT STATED IN THE QUESTIONNAIRE

I could identify myself with the main character.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I found the main character to be sympathetic.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

I could put myself in the main character's place during the commercial.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

The perspectives of the commercial made it easy for me to put myself in the main character's place.

Fully agree rather agree neither nor rather not agree do not agree at all

What is your highest educational level?

- No school leaving certificate
- Primary school
- Secondary school
- Grammar school
- University degree (Bachelor)
- University degree (Master)
- PhD

What is your current employment level?

- Employee
- Self-employed
- Pensioner

- Job seeker
- Student
- Pupil
- Housewife/man
- Other
- Public official

Please indicate what applies to the net income of your household:

- under 500 Euro
- 501 to 1000 Euro
- 1001 to 2000 Euro
- 2001 to 3000 Euro
- 3001 to 4000 Euro
- 4001 to 5000 Euro
- over 5000 Euro
- not specified

Afterwards, the participants received the same evaluation questions regarding the brand as those they had answered before watching the commercial.

Please rank the following brands (1 Rank = best place, 5 Rank = worst place)

Participants could sort related brands here

What would you call your rating of Brand X?

- I do not like it at all
-
-
- neither nor
-
-
- I like it very much

Please name three words that you associate with Brand X:

What is your overall impression of Brand X?

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playful				adult
<input type="checkbox"/>				
interesting				boring
<input type="checkbox"/>				
attractive				ugly
<input type="checkbox"/>				
inventive				uninspired
<input type="checkbox"/>				
offensive				defensive
<input type="checkbox"/>				
extraordinary				average
<input type="checkbox"/>				
emotional				objective
<input type="checkbox"/>				
humorous				serious

6.2 Ethics Committee Approval

19/03/2020

Dear Marcel Rohr,

Your application 9404: Identification of success factors of storytelling in commercials, submission 9176, has been approved by the Business and Creative Industries SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean